

Best Practices for Queer Metadata

by The Queer Metadata Collective

0. Table of Contents

[0. Table of Contents](#)

[1. Introduction & Background](#)

[1.1. Background & Relationship with Trans Metadata Collective](#)

[1.2. Definitions & Philosophy](#)

[1.3. Scope, Limitations & Institutional Barriers](#)

[1.4. Structure of this Document](#)

[2. History & Context](#)

[2.1. Gender, Sexuality, and Queer Nomenclature](#)

[2.2. MORGAI GLAMS Metadata](#)

[3. Broad Recommendations & Principles](#)

[4. Detailed Recommendations](#)

[4.1. Classification](#)

[4.1.1. Classifications to avoid and helpful alternatives](#)

[4.1.1.1. Classification specifics and alternatives](#)

[4.1.2. Alternative queer classification systems](#)

[4.1.3. Reclassifying/updating language](#)

[4.2. Subject Headings](#)

[4.2.1. Revision, Replacement, and Repair](#)

[4.2.1.1. Use of LCSH in describing queer works](#)

[4.2.1.2. Problematic LCSH](#)

[4.2.1.3. Proposing a new subject heading](#)

[4.2.1.4. Making a variant heading the authorised heading](#)

[4.2.2. Use of non-LCSH controlled vocabularies and ontologies](#)

[4.2.2.1. Supplementing LCSH with queer-specific identities and experiences](#)

[4.2.2.2. Replacing problematic LCSH terminology](#)

[4.2.3. Prioritisation of terms used by creators](#)

[4.2.3. Topics Requiring Special Attention](#)

[4.2.3.1. Prejudicial Language in LGBTQ+ Works](#)

[4.2.3.2. Usage of a Harmful Content Statement](#)

[4.2.4. Assigning headings for historical identity labels that are no longer commonly used](#)

- [4.2.5. Assigning headings to ambiguous materials](#)
 - [4.3 Names, Naming & Authorities](#)
 - [4.3.1. What to include in a name authority record](#)
 - [4.3.2. Updating names in name authority records](#)
 - [4.3.3. When to update or change a name](#)
 - [4.3.4. How to update or change a name](#)
 - [4.3.5. Linking names or other identities](#)
 - [4.3.6. Updating names on physical items](#)
 - [4.3.7. Wikidata](#)
 - [4.3.7.1. Wikidata's Property P21](#)
 - [4.3.7.2. Updating & Correction of Wikidata Items](#)
 - [4.3.7.1. Updating Wikidata Items](#)
 - [4.3.7.2. Correcting Wikidata Items](#)
 - [4.3.7.4. General Wikidata Recommendations](#)
 - [4.3.7.4.1. Preliminary Questions](#)
 - [4.3.7.4.3. Things to Not Do](#)
 - [4.4. Description](#)
 - [4.4.1. General Recommendations](#)
 - [4.4.1.2. When to Describe Someone as Queer](#)
 - [4.4.1.2. Modern and Historical Terms](#)
 - [4.4.2. Metadata Remediation](#)
 - [4.4.3. Discoverability](#)
 - [4.4.3.1. Aggregating Records](#)
 - [4.4.3.2. Digitisation and Digital Collections](#)
 - [4.4.3.3. Pre-existing Description](#)
 - [4.4.4. Positionality Statements](#)
 - [4.4.5. Community Collaboration and Consultation](#)
- [5. Author Information & QMDC History](#)
 - [5.1. QMDC History](#)
 - [5.2. Author Information](#)
 - [5.2.1. Classification Working Group](#)
 - [5.2.1.1. Additional Classification Contributors](#)
 - [5.2.2. Subject Headings Working Group](#)
 - [5.2.3. Names, Naming & Authorities Working Group](#)
 - [5.2.3.1. Additional Wikidata Contributors](#)
 - [5.2.4. Description Working Group](#)
 - [5.2.5. Document Structure & Ethical Recommendations Working Group](#)
 - [5.3. QMDC Reviewers](#)
 - [5.4. Glossary of Terms](#)

[6. Appendices & Resources](#)

[6.1. Sources Consulted & Further Reading](#)

[6.1.2. Recommended Name Authority Resources & Examples](#)

[6.2. Alternative Systems](#)

[6.2.1. Alternative Classification Systems](#)

[6.2.2. Alternative Subject Heading Systems](#)

[6.3. Examples, Models & Tutorials](#)

[6.3.1. Harmful Metadata Statement Examples](#)

[6.3.2. Updating and Correction of Wikidata Items](#)

[6.3.2.1. Updating Existing Wikidata Items](#)

[6.3.2.2. Correcting Wikidata Items](#)

[6.3.2.3. Additional Wikidata Considerations for GLAMS Metadata Workers](#)

[6.3.3. Identification of “romantic friendships,” “inseparable friends or companions,” “bosom friends,” “life friends,” and same-sex relationships](#)

[6.3.4. “Case” Studies/Examples](#)

[6.3.4.1. The Five Colleges of Ohio: “Flagging”](#)

[6.4. Current Options In Dominant Systems](#)

[6.4.1. Subject Headings](#)

[6.4.1.1. Problematic LC Subject Headings \(LCSH\)](#)

[6.4.1.2. Problematic LC Demographic Group Terms \(LCDGT\)](#)

[6.4.1.3. Problematic LC Children's and Young Adults' Cataloging Program \(CYAC\) Headings](#)

[6.4.1.4. Problematic Medical Subject Headings \(MeSH\)](#)

[6.4.1.5. Selected Queer LCSH](#)

[6.4.1.6. LCSH That Should Exist \(That Currently Do Not\)](#)

[6.4.1.6.1. Kink terminology](#)

[6.4.1.6.2. Queer Medical Terminology](#)

[6.4.1.6.4. Historical Terminology](#)

[6.4.1.6.4. LGBTQ+ Family Life](#)

[6.4.1.6.5. Queer Identity Terminology](#)

[6.4.1.6.6. Queer Slang Terminology](#)

[6.4.1.6.7. Relationship-based LGBTQ+ Language](#)

[6.4.1.6.8. LGBTQ+ Social Science Terminology](#)

[6.4.1.6.9. Other](#)

[6.4.2. Classification](#)

[6.4.2.1. Library of Congress Classification Numbers](#)

[6.4.2.2. Dewey Decimal Classification Numbers](#)

1. Introduction & Background

1.1. Background & Relationship with Trans Metadata Collective

This document is the result of two years of work by a group of nearly one hundred knowledge organisers, cataloguers, librarians, archivists, scholars, and information professionals with a concerted interest in improving the metadata treatment of queer people, communities, and items in GLAMS (Galleries, Libraries, Archives, Museums, and Special Collections) and other informational institutions. Their work has been supported by over 800 peer reviewers; combined, these groups make up the Queer Metadata Collective (QMDC; queermetadatacollective.org).

The QMDC builds upon earlier work done by the Trans Metadata Collective (TMDC; transmetadatacollective.org), a similarly-organised group of metadata workers and information professionals with a concerted interest in improving the metadata representation of trans and gender-diverse people. The work of the TMDC culminated in *Metadata Best Practices for Trans and Gender Diverse Resources*,¹ focusing on the description, cataloguing, and classification of information resources as well as the creation of metadata about trans and gender-diverse people, including authors, communities, and other creators. Following the publication of the Best Practices, several TMDC members founded and developed the QMDC over the summer of 2022.

Like the TMDC, the Queer Metadata Collective's primary goal was the development of a set of best practices (this document) for the treatment of queer metadata—the description, cataloguing, and classification of information resources as well as the creation of metadata about queer people, including authors, resources, and other creators.

For these reasons, the structure and language of this document take significant inspiration from the Best Practices—sometimes down to the sentence level. Like the TMDC document, this document also claims the Cataloguing Code of Ethics and A4BLiP (Archives for Black Lives in Philadelphia) as proximate inspirations and models, and echoes the A4BLiP's charge:

A4BLiP encourages white archivists and non-Black archivists of color who are combatting anti-Black archival description to first take time to familiarize

¹ The Trans Metadata Collective et al., "Metadata Best Practices for Trans and Gender Diverse Resources" (Zenodo, June 22, 2022), <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6686841>.

yourself with anti-oppressive terms, concepts, and norms in order to deconstruct the white supremacist values that permeate American society, and by extension, the archival field.²

More information about the Queer Metadata Collective, its history, and its members may be found in [Section 5](#), including short biographies of the members that contributed the most to the shaping of the present document.

This document focuses on metadata by and about queer people, communities, and resources. While there is significant overlap between queer metadata and trans and gender diverse metadata, QMDC's recommendations should not be seen as excluding or superseding TMDC's, as trans and gender diverse people, communities, and resources have specific needs. For best practices and recommendations about trans and gender-diverse resources, please consult the TMDC document. If the TMDC and QMDC recommendations conflict (we are not aware of any instances in which they do), prefer the TMDC document for trans and gender diverse resources and the QMDC for other types of queer resources.

Finally, and most importantly, this document is not meant to be a panacea. It does not free its users from other moral, legal, and ethical considerations. Nor does it free users from continued education efforts. Information is meant to be accessible and should be especially accessible to those to whom the information pertains. We urge you to centre and prioritise the needs of queer communities and individuals that your institution serves through respectful (and paid) collaboration and consultation.

1.2. Definitions & Philosophy

Due to the historical inattention paid to the needs of queer communities and metadata in GLAMS and other informational institutions, as well as in the creation and implementation of metadata standards, the QMDC realised the need for this document. In this work, we follow the precept of disability advocates, saying “nothing about us without us.”³

Often, metadata is created about us, our communities, and/or our works by people who aren't familiar with queer issues, topics, or terminology. Commonly used controlled vocabularies, metadata schemas, classification systems, and description norms under-

² Antracoli, Alexis, Annalise Berdini, Kelly Bolding, Faith Charlton, Amanda Ferrara, Valencia Johnson, and Katy Rawdon. “Archives for Black Lives: Anti-Racist Descriptions.” Philadelphia, USA: Archives for Black Lives in Philadelphia (A4BLiP), October 2019.

³ James I. Charlton, *Nothing about Us without Us: Disability Oppression and Empowerment* (Berkeley, CA: University of California Press, 1998).

and misrepresent queer people and subjects. Common policies and recommendations offer harmful suggestions. A few examples:

- The thoughtlessly conceived and poorly implemented requirement to include the gender of a creator in RDA Rule 9.7 (a GLAMS cataloguing standard) has taken over a decade to correct in cataloguing practice, despite immediate outcry and critique. Regardless of revised recommendations and ongoing corrective work, it will likely take years before all affected records are corrected. Rule 9.7 remains unchanged in the official RDA Toolkit.⁴
- Women’s work and agency women’s names were often erased by common archival description practices, which used only their married name (e.g. Mrs. John Smith) to credit any work done.
- Widely recognised, decades-long intimate partnerships are erased by descriptions describing queer couples as “good friends” or “roommates;” individuals’ multi-decade relationships with partners outside the bounds of traditional marriage structures—often with the knowledge of their ‘legal’ spouse—are described as ‘affairs.’
- As indicated by the TMDC and the [Name Change Policy Working Group](#), trans and gender-diverse people are often misnamed or misgendered in metadata, which can (and does) out them and put them at risk of harm or violence.

The aim of this document and the Collective more broadly is to centre queer metadata and ways of being, establishing them as “is” and not as “other.” In other words, the goal is to unsettle, unseat, and eliminate the WEB3CH2A2MS centre of metadata systems. WEB3CH2A2MS (pronounced ‘web-cham’ (IPA: /wɛbˈtʃæm/)) is an acronym originating from cataloguing literature meaning: White, ethnically European, Bourgeois,

⁴ While the Program for Cooperative Cataloging no longer records gender in its RDA authority records, the Official RDA Toolkit includes an element for gender and the original Official RDA Rule 9.7 remains untouched. For more information regarding the effects of this rule, consult the following resources: Amber Billey, Emily Drabinski, and K. R. Roberto, “What’s Gender Got to Do with It? A Critique of RDA 9.7,” *Cataloging & Classification Quarterly* 52, no. 4 (2014): 412–421. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01639374.2014.882465>; Kelly J. Thompson, “More Than a Name: A Content Analysis of Name Authority Records for Authors Who Self-Identify as Trans,” *Library Resources & Technical Services* 60, no. 3 (2016), 140–155. <https://doi.org/10.5860/lrts.60n3.140>; K. Adolpho, “Who Asked You? Consent, Self-Determination, and the Report of the PCC Ad Hoc Task Group on Gender in Name Authority Records,” in *Ethical Questions in Name Authority Control*, ed. Jane Sandberg, 111–131. Library Juice Press, 2019; H. Polebaum-Freeman, “Violent Cis-tems: Identifying Transphobia in Library of Congress Name Authority Records,” in *Ethical Questions in Name Authority Control*, ed. Jane Sandberg, 155–179. Library Juice Press, 2019; N. Shiraiishi, “Accuracy of Identity Information and Name Authority Records,” in *Ethical Questions in Name Authority Control*, ed. Jane Sandberg, 181–194. Library Juice Press, 2019; T. L. Wagner, “Finding ‘Miss Betty’ Joe Carstairs: The Ethics of Unpacking Misnaming in Cataloging and Biographical Practices,” in *Ethical Questions in Name Authority Control*, ed. Jane Sandberg. Library Juice Press, 2019.

Christian, Cisgender, Citizen, Heterosexual, Able-bodied, Allosexual, Monogamous, Men Settlers,⁵

It was created as a way of naming the universal, default, and assumed (yet unspoken) centre of cataloguing, classification, and description systems and practices. It is readily apparent that information infrastructure assumes a WEB3CH2A2MS centre. For example, the subject heading “Executives” (for business executives) offers “Gay executives,” “Minority executives, and “Women executives” as narrower, more specific, more specialised forms of an “Executive” (or poet, or farmer, or banker, or statistician, and so on). WEB3CH2A2MS serves the same role that more-common acronyms like LGTBQIA2S+ (Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, Transgender, Queer, Intersex, Asexual, Two-Spirit, and more(±)) do but rejects the premise that WEB3CH2A2MS perspectives are default positions that do not require labels and instead centres queer (and racialized, disabled, etc.) perspectives, people, and communities.

More specifically, the recommendations below aim to decenter the current cis-mono-allo-heteronormativity of metadata systems in order to equalise and make space for “queer” as something that can be described, even if we do not yet have language for certain things. Along with society, queer nomenclature and language are in a constant state of flux and shift, and what seems correct today may not be reflective in the future. As a result, “queer” is used throughout this document as an umbrella term to refer to subjects with Marginalised Orientations, Relationships, Gender identities, Asexualities/Aromanticisms, and/or those who are Intersex (MORGAI, pronounced “more-gay” (IPA: /mɔɪ'geɪ/)).⁶ MORGAI is inclusive of LGTBQIA2S+ (and other “alphabet soup” type acronyms like QUILTBAG) but recognizes that identity terms are multifaceted, overlapping, and purposefully resistant of definition—in a word: queer.⁷

⁵ Originally WEBCHAM from Hope Olson’s naming of the default and assumed universal centre of cataloguing and classification systems, and was expanded by Michelle Caswell to include “cis” and “citizen” at the encouragement of Marika Cifor, and later expanded by B. M. Watson to include settler status, relationship and romantic orientations. See Hope A. Olson, “Patriarchal Structures of Subject Access and Subversive Techniques for Change,” *The Canadian Journal of Information and Library Science* 26, no. 2-3 (2001): 4; Michelle Caswell, “Dusting for Fingerprints: Introducing Feminist Standpoint Appraisal,” in “Radical Empathy in Archival Practice,” eds. Elvia Arroyo-Ramirez, Jasmine Jones, Shannon O’Neill, and Holly Smith, special issue, *Journal of Critical Library and Information Studies* 3, no. 2 (2021); B. M. Watson, “Advancing Equitable Cataloging,” *NASKO* 8, no. 1 (November 12, 2021): 8; B. M. Watson, “Critiquing the Machine: The Critical Cataloging Database,” *TCB: Technical Services in Religion & Theology* 31, no. 1 (January 24, 2023): 6.

⁶ Originally modelled off MOGI, an acronym in use in New Zealand and Australia meaning Marginalised Orientations and Gender Identities, MORGAI was coined and first used in the Catalogue & Index cited above as well as in the TMDC document.

⁷ To paraphrase Drabinski, classification and subject language can never be “corrected” once and for all, GLAMS metadata workers will have to continually engage with marginalised identity groups and knowledge areas to build shared understanding and knowledge about terminology and terminology use over time. Prompted by a reviewer of this document, it is worth noting here that this term focuses on and privileges intersectionality—i.e. we are not arguing that otherwise straight (cisgender heterosexual

We have attempted to ensure that the best practices in this document apply to resources about MORGAI individuals, but not every recommendation below can be applied to every person, resource, or community in the MORGAI umbrella—nor should they be, nor is it desirable for them to be. Wherever distinctions arise with regards to the applicability of specific practices, we have chosen to incorporate them into the document narrative. Because these kinds of crucial nuances are not always universally known and often change over time, these best practices will continue to be periodically updated and revised.

For specific best practices for metadata about transgender people, non-binary people, trans and gender diverse people, trans and gender diverse peoples' experiences, gender identity, and gender and naming, please consult TMDC's Best Practices. In this document, we follow the TMDC's use of the term "trans and gender diverse" as an umbrella phrase to refer to individuals and communities who do not identify with the gender they were assigned at birth. Our usage of the term equally includes gender expressions and schemas that fall outside of the binary conceptions of man and woman central to Eurocentric culture.

We also follow TMDC's use of the term "resources" to refer to anything for which metadata is assigned in a GLAMS context. Examples include: books, audiovisual materials, archival collections, paintings, artefacts, individuals, communities, organizations, etc.

When we use the word "harm" in this document we are using it in a literal sense of epistemic and physical violence. As minority stress research demonstrates, improper description can have measurable health impacts: when an individual encounters feedback from society that is incompatible with their self-identity, it is compounded with everyday stress and causes an increase in the likelihood that the individual will experience negative psychological consequences, including anxiety, depression, and suicidal ideation.⁸ For queer communities, simple considerations like 'what goes into the box' are always higher and always have real-life consequences.

allosexual) polyamorous couples are queer; however, nonmonogamy or polyamory is 'queering' of typical relationship structures. Furthermore, alternative relational structures are more common among queer communities.

⁸ Ilan H. Meyer, "Prejudice, Social Stress, and Mental Health in Lesbian, Gay, and Bisexual Populations: Conceptual Issues and Research Evidence," *Psychological Bulletin* 129, no. 5 (September 2003): 674–697. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-2909.129.5.674>; Annesa Flentje, Nicholas C. Heck, James Michael Brennan, and Ilan H. Meyer. "The Relationship between Minority Stress and Biological Outcomes: A Systematic Review," *Journal of Behavioral Medicine* 43, no. 5 (October 2020): 673–694. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10865-019-00120-6>; Stephen T. Russell and Jessica N. Fish. "Mental Health in Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, and Transgender (LGBT) Youth," *Annual Review of Clinical Psychology* 12 (March

1.3. Scope, Limitations & Institutional Barriers

This document is designed to serve as a resource for workers in cultural heritage institutions who create metadata about queer people, communities, resources and/or topics. As the Collective is primarily made up of authors working in libraries and archives, significant portions of this document are based in those contexts. However, the authors have made a conscious effort to supplement this document with museum, gallery, and special collections-relevant advice, and have invited supplementation of this advice from reviewers of this document.

These best practices recognize that the concept and structure of GLAMS is Euroamerican and colonialist, and while there is room for critique of these institutions from those (and other) perspectives, this document is not designed as a comprehensive critique.

We also recognize that some institutions and consortia restrict a metadata worker's ability to use their own judgement when assigning metadata to resources materials. We have a few recommendations if you cannot follow these guidelines due to role limitations or administrative policies.

If you can not properly update, revise, or redescribe resources in your institution because of administrative restrictions, these are long-term changes worth advocating for. Start conversations about how to change the policies and standards set forward by your institution or consortium; if the guidelines you use are no longer serving your patrons, then they need to be changed. Library catalogers can also contact DDC, LCC, or NACO / SACO funnels to address classification gaps, outdated language, or inappropriate hierarchies. Institutions can also create public-facing notes like statements or explanations about where cataloguing language comes from, or they can integrate harmful language and classification feedback forms to help address patron concerns.

At the very least, metadata workers can advocate for a harmful metadata statement on their institution's website to acknowledge the reality of the systems within which we work, while also expressing opposition to the harmful and incorrect contents of these systems and offering a way for users to report harmful metadata or an appropriate institutional contact to remedy any issues encountered.

28, 2016): 465–87. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-clinpsy-021815-093153>; Ilan H. Meyer, John E. Pachankis, and Daniel N. Klein, "Do Genes Explain Sexual Minority Mental Health Disparities?" *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 50, no. 3 (April 2021): 731–737. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10508-020-01909-2>.

Finally, we realise that not everyone has the authority, power, or funding to perfectly implement everything recommended below. Perfect adherence to any singular set of rules or recommendations - even our own - is not always possible, nor is it ideal for every context. Respectfully engaging in and with our communities through an intersectional lens requires attention to the interwoven cultural contexts and identities affected by our work. As these things are neither fixed nor immutable, modifications will always be necessary to reduce additional harm. In other words, these guidelines cannot stand in for asking about and prioritising the specific needs and contexts of your users and the communities your institution serves.

Perfection is not always possible, and sometimes you just have to do your best and remember that the ultimate priority is people, not perfection. Each of the sections below are aimed to provide tools towards justice.

1.4. Structure of this Document

The rest of this document is divided into 5 main sections and several subdivisions. [Section 2. History & Context](#), offers 1) a very brief summary history of the origins and development of gender and sexuality terminology and nomenclature and 2) a brief overview of the purposes of knowledge organisation in GLAMS. [Section 3. Broad Recommendations & Principles](#) can serve as an executive summary of the QMDC recommendations as it is the most accessible and easily distributable section of this document. [Section 4. Detailed Recommendations](#), serves as an in-depth explanation of the recommendations found in Section 3, and includes the bulk of the [Classification](#), [Subject Headings](#), [Names, Naming, and Authorities](#), and [Description](#) reports. Where possible, Section 4 includes detailed instructions on the implementation of these recommendations or recommendations drawn from interviews with over fifty GLAMS knowledge organisers, more than two dozen finding aids for queer collections, and the experience and knowledge of hundreds of authors and reviewers.

[Section 5. Author Information & QMDC History](#), offers a list of this document's authors and their backgrounds, as well as reviewers and contributors to this document. The individuals listed in the "Authors" section have elected to appear in it in alphabetic order, whereas those in the "Reviewers" section added their names in roughly chronological order (i.e. no order).

For cisgender/heterosexual readers of this document, it is worth emphasizing that there are more than one hundred individuals who did not wish to be or could not be listed in these sections due to concerns of being outed, personal danger, employment termination, and/or prosecution due to their local political context, especially in the

southern United States. The QMDC honors their contributions and extend our thanks for their participation and wisdom.

[Section 6. Appendices & Resources](#) is given over to appendices, including resources, sources, bibliographies, lists of relevant queer subject headings, classifications, alternative systems, and a glossary of terms used in this document.

2. History & Context

2.1. Gender, Sexuality, and Queer Nomenclature

Ideas about what gender or sexuality are vary by time and place and are both cultural and individual. These ideas often relate to bodies, social roles, relationships, power dynamics, and personal expression. A culture's gender schema may include ideas about how many genders there are, social roles, modes of dress, how fixed or dynamic gender is, how people of differing genders relate to each other, and how to treat people who don't fit into the gender schema. Sexuality schema might include acceptable or unacceptable types or styles of sex, the number, age, or gender of partners.⁹

Culture is a complex interplay of many factors including, but not limited to, economics, geography and migration, race and Indigeneity, religion, language, politics, and more. Within any given place, there is usually a dominant culture that exerts power and influence over the other co-existing cultures. The dominant culture in GLAMS is usually referred to as "Western culture," a term which is inaccurate and erases many cultures in the West that aren't dominant, particularly Black and Indigenous ones. We will refer to this as WEB3CH2A2MS culture in this section.¹⁰

The epicentre of this culture is the present-day United States, and it also predominates in Canada, Western Europe, Australia, and New Zealand. WEB3CH2A2MS culture specifically witnessed several important shifts in the way gender and sexuality are conceptualised over the course of the late twentieth and early twenty-first centuries. These were not the first shifts in ideas about what gender and sexuality are and they will not be the last.

⁹ "Schema" here, as in "gender schema" or "sexuality schema" is being used as shorthand to talk about things like gender roles and all associated concepts. We are not using it as a reference to Sandra Bem's cognitive theory about how individuals become gendered in society,

¹⁰ For more information on the acronym, see the third paragraph of Section 1.2.

A high-level understanding of the recent shifts in ideas about gender and sexuality and their roots in WEB3CH2A2MS culture is important for ethical decision-making in the creation of metadata about queer people and topics. Below is a brief overview of the history of gender and sexuality terminology and nomenclature as it relates to queer people and some of the major shifts in dominant gender ideas in the late twentieth/early twenty-first century. This account, although written by a historian of sex and sexuality is deliberately expansive, broad-brush, and generalizing and should be used as a starting place for personal and institutional education.

Generally speaking, much of WEB3CH2A2MS culture's attitudes and nomenclature for individuals or objects belonging to MORGAI communities have post-Roman Judeo-Christian origins or derive from (earlier) theological or (later) medical terminology

For example, the ancient Greek term *porneia* (πορνεία) captured a vast range of sexual behaviours considered unethical/immoral within ancient Greek culture and was widely used by early Christian theologians as a stand-in for behaviour that they did not approve of.¹¹ *Porneia* also demonstrates how some terms have a long and continuous history as via a circuitous route, *porneia* survives today in many Western languages as the root of the word "pornography."¹²

In the Early Modern period, terms like "sodomy," "buggery," "gross indency," and others arose in the same literature to refer to specifically-sexual behaviour. These terms were used in many Western European countries to describe a range of "undesirable" behaviours: anal penetration, crossdressing, masturbation, fellatio, cunnilingus—even theatre in particularly strident morality literature.¹³ While sodomy initially referred to anal penetration between any gender or sex by the seventeenth century it began to stabilise on an activity that would be described today as anal penetration involving two cisgender homosexual (or "gay") men. Likewise, buggery was initially a stand-in for 'bestiality' but took on a broader meaning after the sixteenth century.

¹¹ The most comprehensive account of this is Kyle Harper, *From Shame to Sin: The Christian Transformation of Sexual Morality in Late Antiquity* (Cambridge, Massachusetts: Harvard University Press, 2013), which builds upon Kathy L. Gaca, *Making of Fornication - Eros, Ethics, and Political Reform in Greek Philosophy* (University Of California Press, 2017, orig. 2003).

¹² The word pornography in English however, comes from ancient Greek *πορνο-* for prostitutes + *-γράφος* for drawings (prostitute drawings). This word is only found once in Hellenistic Greek, where Athenaeus comments on an artist that painted portraits of courtesans. Then the word fell out of use for 1500 years until it was used in 1842 to describe a proposal on how to regulate prostitutes, but it was more commonly used as a coded word to refer to the wall murals depicting sex workers uncovered at Pompeii.

¹³ The most significant recent interpretation is Chitty's posthumous work: Christopher Chitty, *Sexual Hegemony: Statecraft, Sodomy, and Capital in the Rise of the World System*, Duke U.P., 2020.

In *A Practical Guide to Searching LGBTQIA Historical Records* (a highly useful resource for any archives), Norena Shopland documents terminology used for queer people, such as lesbians (“tribade” and “Sapphic,” both post 1850), intersex/trans and gender diverse people (“hermaphrodite,” “gusset” “effeminate” “androgynus”), and gay men, from several sources and centuries:

Catamite, an Ingle, or Boy kept for sodomy.

Pederast (Gr.) a Buggerer.

Pederasty, a lusting after Boys, Sodomy, Buggery.

Sodomit [sic], one that commits Sodomy, a Buggerer...

Back Gammon Player. A sodomite.

Indorser. A sodomite. To indorse with a cudgel; to drub or beat a man over the back with a stick, to lay cane upon Abel.

Molly. A Miss Molly; an effeminate fellow, a sodomite.

Twiddle-Poop. An effeminate looking fellow.

Windward Passage. One who uses or navigates the windward passage; a sodomite.¹⁴

These are only two examples of English terms—as demonstrated by works like Francis Grouse’s *Classical Dictionary of the Vulgar Tongue*, hundreds of other local and provincial terms (not to mention non-English nomenclature) existed, many of which survive today (for example, “queer”).¹⁵

Until the so-called Enlightenment, the majority of Europeans (and later, Americans) followed what historians of sexuality and the body label as the “one-sex model.” This model understood bodies as representations along a male to female spectrum. Contrary to biological essentialism, this spectrum was one that was open to a significant degree of change. Many texts reflected a beliefs about ‘mannish’ women or ‘effete’ men literally becoming the opposite sex.¹⁶ Most people assumed gender based

¹⁴ Norena Shopland, *A Practical Guide to Searching LGBTQIA Historical Records*, 1st ed. (Routledge, 2021), <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003006787>, p. 6-9.

¹⁵ Trumbach has written the most about this, i.e. Randolph Trumbach, “Sex, Gender, and Sexual Identity in Modern Culture: Male Sodomy and Female Prostitution in Enlightenment London,” *Journal of the History of Sexuality* 2, no. 2, (1991): 186–203, but other relevant work includes Hamilton’s work on Paris Tom Hamilton, “Sodomy and Criminal Justice in the Parlement of Paris, ca. 1540–ca. 1700,” *Journal of the History of Sexuality* 29, no. 3 (2020): 303–34, doi:10.7560/JHS29301; D. M. Halperin, “How To Do The History Of Male Homosexuality,” *GLQ*: 6, no. 1 (2000): 87–123, doi:10.1215/10642684-6-1-87.

¹⁶ This theory, largely advanced by Thomas Laqueur, has been limited and critiqued by several later historians such as Laura Gowing, Karen Harvery, Robert Nye and others, but remains influential (and convincing). Recent reassessment of the debate has tended to lend more support to Laqueur’s argument. See Katherine Crawford, “The Good, the Bad, and the Textual: Approaches to the Study of the Body and Sexuality, 1500–1750,” in *The Routledge History of Sex and the Body* (London ; New York: Routledge, 2013), 23–37, and Harry G. Cocks, “Approaches to the History of Sexuality since 1750,” 38–54 in the same text for a review of the debate.

on a person's name, outward physical appearance, clothing, pronoun usage, etc.¹⁷ Since these are all external signs, someone's gender was considered public information. In the realm of sexuality, most people grew up in rural areas with a lot of close contact with animals and agricultural breeding and would have been very familiar with breeding; even in urban areas, bedrooms were passageways into other bedrooms (hallways were a rather recent invention) and lower class and rural families very often shared a single bed. There is greater evidence for queer sexualities and communities in these urban areas, many often living alongside cisgender heterosexual communities, but they often faced prosecution by church, state, or particularly bigoted neighbours—a situation not too dissimilar from modern times.¹⁸

Following the so-called Enlightenment and until the mid-twentieth century the majority of Euroamericans moved towards understanding sex and gender as a roughly binary system, where popular conception maintained that sex and gender were more or less the same thing and determined by “biological” factors (body parts, hormones, chromosomes, etc.). While earlier generations saw sexual activity between “same-sex” youth as part of a “normal” development ending in the adoption of procreative marital sex upon adulthood/maturity or marriage, post-eighteenth century WEB3CH2A2MS culture became obsessed with the purity of children and preoccupied by anti-masturbation campaigns and the prevention of the spread of sexual knowledge amongst younger generations.¹⁹

The nineteenth and twentieth centuries witnessed the rise of a professionalised field of medico-scientific doctors, psychologists, sociologists, and sexologists who used these credentials to subsequently pathologize, marginalize, and even criminalize various communities of people who fell outside their pre-determined vision of normalcy.²⁰

¹⁷ This is most notable and remarkable (to modern-day readers) in the literature around figures such as Antonio de Erauso, who was seen and understood to be a man even when stripped naked.

¹⁸ See chapters by Laura Gowing and Tanya Evans on Knowledge and Experience in *The Routledge History of Sex and the Body*, ed. Kate Fisher and Sarah Toulalan (London: Routledge, 2013).

¹⁹ Paige Donaghy, “Before Onanism: Women’s Masturbation in Seventeenth-Century England,” *Journal of the History of Sexuality* 29, no. 2 (May 2020): 187–221, <https://doi.org/10.7560/jhs29203>; Stefano Rossi, “Female Onanism: Condemned Pleasures, Medical Probes, and Late-Victorian Pornography,” *Victoriographies* 11, no. 2 (July 2021): 148–64, <https://doi.org/10.3366/vic.2021.0420>; Diane Elizabeth Mason, *The Secret Vice: Masturbation in Victorian Fiction and Medical Culture* (Manchester, UK; New York: New York: Manchester University Press; Distributed exclusively in USA by Palgrave Macmillan, 2008); Alan Hunt, “The Great Masturbation Panic and the Discourses of Moral Regulation in Nineteenth- and Early Twentieth-Century Britain,” *Journal of the History of Sexuality* 8, no. 4 (1998): 575–615; Deana Heath, *Purifying Empire: Obscenity and the Politics of Moral Regulation in Britain, India and Australia* (New York: Cambridge University Press, 2010); Greta LaFleur, *The Natural History of Sexuality in Early America* (Baltimore: Johns Hopkins University Press, 2018); Tim Hitchcock, “Redefining Sex in Eighteenth-Century England,” *History Workshop Journal*, 20; B. M. Watson, *Annals of Pornographie: How Porn Became Bad*. 2017.

²⁰ Jeffrey Weeks, *Sex, Politics and Society: The Regulations of Sexuality since 1800*, 2015.

Authors such as Richard von Krafft-Ebing, Magnus Hirschfeld, Karl Heinrich Ulrichs, and Havelock Ellis, made notable contributions to this shift and general societal ideas followed to make distinctions between sex (bodies) and gender (internal sense of self).²¹ For example, Ulrichs drew on Linnaean biological classification, as well as his reading of Plato's Symposium, to create Urning and Dioning for homosexual and heterosexual males, then added a suffix to produce Urningin and Dioningin for females, and then finished off by combining the four prior words into Uranodioning and Uranodioningin to refer to bisexuals of either sex. Later additions included Mannlings for masculine-presenting individuals attracted to feminine men and its opposite Weiblings; Zwischenstufen for those attracted to underaged males, and the (incorrect) term Hermaphrodites to refer to intersex people.²² Krafft-Ebing generally located the "origins" of "psychopathic" sexuality in the societal environment and the immoral decisions made by his subjects, whereas Hirschfeld argued that human embryos began as sexually neutral and then developed into types as influenced by hormones, including people who were "anders als die andern" (different from the others).²³

The purpose of this background is to contextualize the ways that these sexological processes influence the cataloguing, classification and description of queer people in GLAMS, especially the ways that sexological literature influences literary warrant, which then influences controlled vocabularies, classifications, authorities, ontologies, and other aspects of knowledge organization.

2.2. MORGAI GLAMS Metadata

As this document is aimed at metadata professionals and it is not meant to serve as an introductory or an educational work, the history of the fields is best left elsewhere for fuller treatment. However, it is important to note that library cataloguing, archival

Donna J. Drucker, *The Classification of Sex: Alfred Kinsey and the Organization of Knowledge* (Pittsburgh, Pa: University of Pittsburgh Press, 2014); Benjamin Kahan, *The Book of Minor Perverts: Sexology, Etiology, and the Emergences of Sexuality* (University of Chicago Press, 2019), <https://doi.org/10.7208/chicago/9780226608006.001.0001>; Alain Giami and Sharman Levinson, eds., *Histories of Sexology: Between Science and Politics, Global Queer Politics* (Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2021), <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-65813-7>.

²¹ Paul A Robinson, *The Modernization of Sex: Havelock Ellis, Alfred Kinsey, William Masters, and Virginia Johnson* (New York: Harper & Row, 1976); Lucy Bland and Laura L. Doan, eds., *Sexology in Culture: Labelling Bodies and Desires* (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 1998); Heike Bauer, *English Literary Sexology: Translations of Inversion, 1860–1930* (Houndmills, Basingstoke, Hampshire New York, NY: Palgrave Macmillan, 2009); Angela Willey, *Undoing Monogamy: The Politics of Science and the Possibilities of Biology* (Durham: Duke University Press, 2016).

²² Ralph M. Leck, *Vita Sexualis: Karl Ulrichs and the Origins of Sexual Science* (Champaign, Illinois, United States: University of Illinois Press, 2016).

²³ R. von (Richard) Krafft-Ebing and Francis Joseph Rehman, *Psychopathia Sexualis, with Especial Reference to the Antipathic Sexual Instinct, a Medico-Forensic Study*; (New York: Rebman, 1886), <http://archive.org/details/psychopathiasexu00krafuoft>; Leck.

description, and museum description represent three distinct approaches institutions have taken to organise and provide access to their collections. While all three share the common goal of making their resources discoverable and accessible to users, they have developed unique methods and standards to achieve this objective. However, the digital age and the development of online library catalogues, digitised collections, and virtual museum exhibits has had a major impact on all three fields.²⁴ Standards and tools have begun to merge or see use in other fields, such as archivists' frequent use of Library of Congress Subject Headings (LCSH) in finding aids, the Dublin Core and MODS standards used to describe digitised materials, or ensure consistency and interoperability across digital platforms. There is a growing trend towards collaboration and standardisation across these fields, sometimes forced by austerity and sometimes brought about by the merging of institutions (for good or ill). Collaborative initiatives like Linked Data aim to create more interconnected and accessible networks of cultural heritage information, and in turn accelerate this standardisation process. By using common data models, vocabularies, and platforms like Wikidata, libraries, archives, and museums are increasingly sharing and linking their metadata, enabling users to discover and explore resources across institutional boundaries.

It is important to remember that all of these standards prioritise text-based resources which implicitly undervalues other formats based on images or sound.²⁵ One way this prioritization manifests is through the privilegisation of literary warrant as the basis for descriptive vocabularies. Literary warrant refers to the idea that the terms used in subject headings and classification schemes should be based on the language used in the resources being described. The intention is that resources in a catalogue, finding aid, or digital platform should reflect the terminology used by authors, and (therefore) familiar to users. While well-intended, literary warrant privileges texts and terminology developed by WEB3CH2A2MS authors, both because of the greater presence of those authors in earlier literature, and because those authors often presented new concepts, ideas, and terminology about “others” (i.e. non-WEB3CH2A2MS individuals or communities), in anthropological, sociological, sexological texts, thus necessitating new terms in knowledge organization systems.²⁶

²⁴ Sometimes “digital collections” are referred to as “digital archives” or “e-resources”, some institutions refer to all three. For example, [NYPL's digital collections](#) include anything digitised from physical archives, special, or non-circulating collections, which could include archival material, (mostly rare) books/periodicals, audio/moving image, photo/picture collections, artworks, and more. [NYPL's e-resource collection](#) includes e-resources/e-materials (e=electronic) like article databases, e-books, and streaming media. Finally, [NYPL's digital archives](#) include born-digital material collected through archival acquisitions.

²⁵ “Undervalues” here is meant in the sense that non-text formats are often under-supported and/or over-complicated by standards intended for objects of a different medium.

²⁶ Melissa Adler discusses this in great detail in *Cruising the Library: Perversities in the Organization of Knowledge* (New York: Fordham University Press, 2017).

To return to the present day and the purpose of this document, we argue that the concept of community warrant should be prioritized over literary when creating queer metadata. That is, the best-placed person to consult in the creation of metadata is the creator or community themselves. If individuals/communities use specific terminology to describe themselves terms, there should be matching terms in the systems used to describe that individual/community or their resources. Ergo, when a term, such as queer, finds itself used in a literary work, then the classification system seeking to categorise that work must have “queer” as an available descriptor.

To put it bluntly, if there are books written about queer concepts, they need queer metadata to describe them; if there is art made by queer people there needs to be queer metadata to describe them; if there are records of queer communities, queer metadata is needed to describe them; and for all of these mediums, the specific queer individuals or community affected and/or described should be consulted.

The point of all this: for living people gender and sexuality should be considered private, un-assumable, potentially fluid, and self-determined. While this way of conceiving gender and sexuality is not applicable to everyone, it is disproportionately applicable to MORGAI people and should therefore guide your decision-making regarding creating metadata about MORGAI individuals, communities, and resources. It's best not to make assumptions about someone's gender based on their clothing, appearance, or pronoun usage. You don't know someone's gender until they tell you (and what they told you in the past may have changed). An individual may prefer to keep the information private for many reasons, including safety. Ideas about the binary and fixed nature of gender are also being challenged and ideas about multiplicity and fluidity are emerging. This approach is designed to reduce harm to those described and targeted within the metadata itself, and manifests in the recommendations and policies below.

For the creation of metadata about deceased subjects, follow the Collective's Chain of Trust, by considering consultation with the following groups (if possible) in this order of preference: public statements by the individual, correspondence, partner(s) at time of death, chosen family members, community members, children (adopted or biological), and if all other options are exhausted, family of origin. The Description Working Group's [Section 4.4.1.2. When to Describe Someone as Queer](#) is an excellent starting place for the creation of metadata about deceased people.

3. Broad Recommendations & Principles

These recommendations should be seen as building upon and extending from the Trans Metadata Collective's Recommendations. Indeed, several of the below recommendations share or copy language outright from the TMDC. Despite sharing language with TMDC, QMDC arrived at the principles represented in these recommendations independently and their repetition should be understood as adding emphasis.

- The best-placed person to consult is the creator or community themselves. Trust and promote community warrant where possible, consult creators and communities and use their preferred terminology, even when it is historical or uses potentially reclaimed slurs.
 - In a museum or archival context, give depositors or donors the opportunity to submit self-description, co-create description, or review/approve description, if applicable.
 - In a library context, give creators the opportunity to provide feedback on catalogue records and holders of this data should simplify this process to make it as accessible and approachable as possible.
 - One specific recommendation: The Library of Congress should provide creators the opportunity or ability to provide feedback on Cataloging-in-Publication data.
 - In an authorities context, creators should have the ability to provide feedback on or to correct information about themselves. Holders of this data (including NACO institutions, VIAF/OCLC, ULAN/the Getty, Wikidata and others) should simplify this process to make it as accessible and approachable as possible. Institutions that lack the ability to revise authorities databases should consider the use of local authorities.
 - Prioritise terms used within a community, which may include reclaimed or self-ascribed slurs or otherwise sensitive language, and retain community terms alongside controlled vocabularies or otherwise authoritative terms.
 - Practise respectful and reciprocal collaboration with communities when possible to avoid uncritical application of terms. Follow community protocols as part of this process.
 - Prioritise using the terms the creators of the work have used in subject descriptor fields, even if those terms aren't found in controlled vocabularies.

- When creating metadata about deceased people, follow the Collective's Chain of Trust or develop one for your own collection and context.
 - Chain of Trust: In the event that the creator is deceased or no appropriate cultural contact is found, consider consultation with the following sources or groups (if possible) in this order of preference: public statements by the individual, correspondence, partner(s) at time of death, chosen family members, community members, children (adopted or biological), and if all other options are exhausted, family of origin.

- Make the process of metadata creation transparent and have harmful / historical language statement policies and procedures, including a form or an email address through which communities or creators can reach out.
 - Indicate term changes over time and be clear about if a particular term is from the source, or if a more recent term has been applied in your metadata.
 - It is likely that previous descriptive practices resulted in some descriptions that may be upsetting and insensitive to users. As the majority of organisations rely on their users to advise them of this type of description in their collections, it is recommended that all organisational websites have a harmful materials statement and an easily located space for user feedback. Some examples are listed in [Section 6.3.1. Harmful Metadata Statement Examples](#)

- Use culturally and contextually appropriate labels for queer communities, subjects, and resources.
 - There are a multiplicity of queer communities. Collaborate with the specific community that is impacted, and be aware that even individuals within a community may have terminology that differs from other members within their communities.
 - Different cultures and languages have terms and systems for classifying and understanding genders and sexuality or sexuality concepts that may not translate into the primary language of description or the dominant culture.
 - Include terms in the original language (original script and transliterated) alongside added translations and descriptions.

- Be explicit about queerphobia in collections, items, and metadata.
 - Identify WEB3CH2A2MS in catalogues and descriptions where possible. In the most radical form, this would look like adding local subdivisions for

“--Heterosexual” “--Man” “--Able-Bodied” “--Allosexual” and so on. A less radical version would be making a conscious effort to add the identities of marginalised individuals, following some of the examples in [Section 4.2 below](#).

- When describing incidents of intentional harassment, harm, and/or violence, both perpetrators and victims should be identified, including using active voice to embed responsibility within the metadata.
 - Work to proactively identify sensitive language and content, including coded language, rather than relying solely on patron reports.
 - For sensitive language that is self-ascribed or directly in the material itself (e.g. title, caption, text), include a contextualising statement and/or content warning either before the user encounters the description, or in each place the description may be encountered.
 - Correct offensive or inaccurate language provided by other metadata creators, unless it falls under the criteria detailed below.
- Give preference to alternative systems and practices that prioritise local control and authority when possible.
 - Interrogate conflicting needs in knowledge creation and discovery. There can be tension between diverse identities and discoverability to enable people to find resources by and about diverse identities. There can be challenges to assisting users in finding materials with the language they use now.
 - Make a variant heading the authorised heading. Many queer LCSH headings have variants that are a better fit than the authorised heading.
 - Use non-LCSH controlled vocabularies and ontologies where appropriate and possible.
 - Create local Cutter numbers for any orientation, identity, or topic that is not represented. Not every system indexes the same topics, and it is almost impossible for one system to index every topic. For more information on this, see [Section 4.1.1.1](#).
 - Creating a subject guide or collection tag can also help gather without having to group on the shelf. Local subject headings, signage, or other communication is better than collocating by classification.
 - Identify queer content and metadata through regular assessment and prioritise for ongoing remediation.
 - Plan proactively for periodic assessment and remediation, including the identification of resources related to queer communities and individuals,

especially when they exist within larger collections where they are not the focus.

- Avoid using machine learning, “AI”, or automation for batch replacement of terms. Only use them as a tool to aid assessment, alongside qualitative analysis around the rationale and impact of existing description.
- Encourage, support, or develop advocacy in your institutions and contexts for better and more sensitive metadata.
- If you are queer, trust in your own authority, knowledge, community warrant, and your “queer cataloguer’s judgement.”
 - If relevant to the resource, feel comfortable assigning headings for historical identity labels that are no longer commonly used such as “Invert.” The language used within queer communities to describe ourselves has changed and will continue to change as our communities evolve and grow.
 - Important caveat: use careful consideration in applying terms that are typically considered slurs in contemporary MORGAI communities. This can sometimes mean balancing conflicting needs: for example, older people are more likely to consider the word “queer” a slur and object to its use in describing a project, and perhaps a broader (or more specific) term would be better.
 - If you are not queer: avoid applying queer terminology or classification to a resource if the resource has nothing to do with queerness. Don’t apply queer terminology to authority files if they are not relevant.

4. Detailed Recommendations

This section contains in-depth explanations for the broad recommendations listed in the previous section as well as the bulk of working group reports.

4.1. Classification

This section discusses best practices and topics to keep in mind for metadata workers who are classifying queer materials in the context of libraries, including academic, public, and special libraries.²⁷ Some libraries, as well as most other cultural heritage institutions, tend to classify their materials by accession, a process which does not involve the same kind of biases and considerations.

Queerness inherently falls outside the standard which raises a lot of questions when trying to fit queer materials within a heteronormative classification system. This section highlights several of these questions and our suggestions for addressing them. Our topics are ranked by ease of implementation at a local institution.

In [Section 6.4.2](#), we have also provided an update to a table entitled Library of Congress Classification Numbers Applicable to Materials for LGBTQIA Studies by Sara A. Howard and Steven A. Knowlton in their article “Browsing through Bias: The Library of Congress Classification and Subject Headings for African American Studies and LGBTQIA Studies.”²⁸ We have expanded their original focus to also include call numbers in the Dewey Decimal System.

Queer resources in library collections can either be collocated apart from all other library resources or interspersed with other materials in the same topic area. For example, a book about healthcare for queer people could be shelved in a separate queer collection or with other healthcare topics. There can be benefits and biases involved in either option, so it is important for metadata workers to be aware of the choices and implications.

Borrowing from Eve Sedgwick’s *Epistemology of the Closet*,²⁹ Ben Christensen applies the terms “minoritization” and “universalization” to describe these two options for

²⁷ The corresponding section in TMDC’s Best Practices is Section 3.3, which offers brief recommendations and general principles for classifying resources using the Library of Congress Classification (LCC) or Dewey Decimal Classification (DDC).

²⁸ Sara A. Howard and Steven A. Knowlton, “Browsing through Bias: The Library of Congress Classification and Subject Headings for African American Studies and LGBTQIA Studies,” *Library Trends* 67, no. 1 (2018): 74–88, <https://doi.org/10.1353/lib.2018.0026>.

²⁹ Eve Kosofsky Sedgwick, *Epistemology of the Closet* (Berkeley: University of California Press, 1990).

classification. “Universalization” refers to emphasising concepts as a part of a whole and de-emphasising difference while “minoritization” refers to emphasising concepts as distinct and separate from a universal whole.³⁰

Early researchers supported a “minoritization” approach where resources about minorities could be separated from the whole to increase visibility.³¹ While this stance could still be useful for public libraries with specific queer collections or queer youth collections, it “others” queer communities, treating them as non-standard or abnormal. Separating materials also makes it easier for people to opt-out of finding these voices. Unless there is a significant or institution-specific reason, we highly recommend following an approach of “universalization,” which moves against the idea of creating separate “queer” collections.

The thrust of our recommendations is to integrate queer resources into the library’s full collection rather than creating a distinct “queer” area at the general call number. Further rationale for this approach (mirroring TMDC’s recommendations for trans and gender-diverse resources):

- It acknowledges that queer people are more than just our gender/sexual/relationship identity and that we lead multi-faceted lives.
- It brings queerness, transness, and other diversity to more specific areas of a library’s collection and to the attention of people who may not otherwise seek them out.
- It may protect queer resources outside the general classification number from censorship challenges or legislation.

There are also alternatives to consider that allow for collocation without classification separation. Creating a subject guide, collection tag, or applying local subject headings can also help gather resources without having to group on the shelf. Signage or other communication is better than collocating by classification.

Some libraries may not “minoritize” these materials by classifying them separately and instead may put stickers on queer resources to identify them. Putting stickers on queer resources increases one’s ability to find items in a universalised system, but could make people feel uncomfortable or unsafe using resources.

³⁰ Kristine Nowak and Amy Mitchell, “Classifying Identity: Organizing an LGBT Library,” *Library Philosophy and Practice* (e-Journal), January 1, 2016, <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/1452>; Ben Christensen, “Minoritization vs. Universalization: Lesbianism and Male Homosexuality in LCSH and LCC,” *Knowledge Organization* 35, no. 4 (December 14, 2008): 229–38, <https://doi.org/10.5771/0943-7444-2008-4-229>.

³¹ Christensen, “Minoritization vs. Universalization.”

Based on interviews with librarians serving youth, teen, and young adult populations we highly recommend NEVER physically labelling queer or MORGAI materials in teen- and youth-specific collections due to safety concerns. For adult collections, we also recommend that libraries avoid physically labelling these materials to best serve the safety and comfort of users. Metadata workers should weigh these decisions in consultation within their institutions and their local queer communities.

4.1.1. Classifications to avoid and helpful alternatives

4.1.1.1. Classification specifics and alternatives

Below are outlined some places in classification systems where you can put certain materials and cause the least harm. There are also some alternatives to consider if any of these suggestions are not feasible at your institution.

Class any materials about a specific group of people (ex. Bisexual people, Asexual people, etc.) in their related number and not with the general group number whenever that option is available. When using LCC (or other systems, where applicable), default to “LGBTQ people” followed by “Queer people” and only reluctantly “Sexual minorities” when classing materials about queer people as a group. Avoid putting non-heterosexual materials under numbers with “Gays” or “Homosexuality” as the only option. Previously “Gays” was used for any non-heterosexual person, occasionally breaking out into “Lesbians.” With the inclusion of “Sexual minorities” or “LGBTQ people” as subject headings and captions, this is where to class anything about queer people as a group, no matter the topic.

Create local Cutter numbers for any orientation, identity, or topic that is not represented. Not every system has the same topics, and it is almost impossible for one system to have everything in it. As long as the schedule allows it, local Cutter numbers are an easy way to tackle any exclusion of orientations, topics, or identities that are represented in catalogued materials.

- If your workplace or consortium does not allow catalogers to create local Cutter numbers, see [Section 4.1.4. Institutional Barriers & Consortia](#).

Do not class any material about transgender people under numbers with the captions “Transvestism” or “Cross-dressing.” This is an extremely harmful and completely false assumption that should not be perpetuated. Transgender people and cross-dressers are not the same, and they should not be classed under the same number. If the classification system has these topics under one number, create a separate Cutter or see [Section 4.1.4. Institutional Barriers & Consortia](#).

- For more details on cataloguing transgender resources, see [Metadata Best Practices for Trans and Gender Diverse Resources](#).

Separate any classification that conflates gender or identity with sex, eroticism, or pornography. Previously, anything having to do with non-heterosexual sex or any media featuring non-cisgender people was often classed under erotica or pornography, even if it was not sexual in nature. This is being remedied, but sometimes the system has not changed the numbers or separated these topics out. Do not automatically catalogue non-heterosexual/non-cisgender topics with numbers about sex unless they are legitimately about those topics.

- Keep in mind: The headings “Sex role” and “Sex differences” are also often classed under Sex, and both the headings have references about gender. This means that the numbers for gender-related terms are also classed under Sex by default. Classification systems lump these two ideas together, but they should have two different Cutters.

Add subject headings or keywords to mitigate some of the harm caused by classification. If there does not seem to be a good way to class something, or if your institutional or consortial situation prevents it, adding relevant and appropriate subject headings can help. Avoid adding works to classes that imply that queerness is a result of perversion, mental illness, or some other medical issue. For example, make use of updated subject headings by the Library of Congress Subject Headings, or search Homosaurus for more nuanced and specific headings. For more information about using headings, see [Section 4.2. Subject Headings](#).

These are suggestions to help mitigate any potential harm that current versions of classification systems might cause. Metadata workers should be as proactive as possible about expanding numbers, altering captions, and making overall adjustments to systems to align them with respectful and diverse cataloguing of MORGAI resources, individuals, and communities. If metadata workers are restricted to specific systems they should follow the recommendations below as starting points and advocate to make overall change.

4.1.2. Alternative queer classification systems

Thanks to the work of librarian activists, queer people and concepts are, for the most part, well-situated in Dewey and LC classification systems.

Classification systems inevitably reflect the biases and limitations of their creators and the era in which they were developed. While there have been many specialised queer

classification systems, many of them are not currently being actively developed, or they are utilised within closed collections and archives. The exceptions to this rule (OOTS, LPC/GSLO and LLACE), along with information about the historical systems are listed in [Section 6.2.1. Alternative Classification Systems](#). Moreover, since the 1970s, librarians have endeavoured to integrate queer concepts into the frameworks of systems like Dewey Decimal Classification (DDC) and Library of Congress Classification (LCC), making specialised systems less necessary for general collections.

In [Section 6.2.1](#) of the appendix, we have included a few examples for further exploration and articles for further reading. There you may find ideas for shelf organisation, potential inspiration for the creation of classification systems, or for use in a permanent special collection. Each of these systems was created for a specific collection to improve access for their patrons. Regardless of the classification system that you use, these systems and case studies highlight the importance of working with your local community in order to improve shelf order and resource discovery.

4.1.3. Reclassifying/updating language

As mentioned above, classification systems and controlled vocabularies will always be imperfect products of their time, place, and creators, which means that opportunities for reclassification and revising the language applied to records will always abound. These endeavours, however, are time-intensive and highly demanding of resources. Lack of time, lack of resources, and lack of personnel to take on such projects are often real barriers to this work, as is the understanding that it is only a matter of time before more records (or the same records) will need additional updates.

However, if metadata workers are committed to improving the description and classification of queer people in GLAMS and other information systems, it is important to consider taking on reclassification and language update projects.

If a metadata worker is taking on a reclassification/language update project, either in an ad hoc, as-needed, as-reported/encountered basis or as a strategic, comprehensive project for their library, the following guidelines are available:

1. Update both subject headings and classification, where needed. Though it may be easier and less time- and resource-intensive to adjust only the subject headings and not update call numbers as originally assigned, that often leaves resources in a classification hierarchy that is just as harmful as the original language in the subject headings, thus it is still a problem that needs to be addressed.

- a. When and if multiple classifications may work well for a resource being (re)classified, strive to centre your patrons and their needs, and class the item in the section you believe your patrons are most likely to find it.
2. If your institutional system uses MARC, use an 09X field (locally assigned call number) when possible to assign a more appropriate classification number or to adjust the language of a topical cutter to be more accurate. Using the 09X will make it clear that you have made a library-specific decision based on your shelflist. The PCC Guiding Principles for Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion in Metadata Creation support this choice. For more information on assigning institution specific classification, please see [MARC 09X - Local Call Numbers](#).
3. If you have replaced the cover of a trans author's book in the catalogue and on the shelf, you should also reclassify it under the new name. There are two primary strategies to consider when considering an existing book with the author's former name. When developing your policy, ensure that the perspectives of trans and gender diverse members of your communities are represented in the discussion:
 - a. Update the call number on the spine and in the library catalogue if needed
 - b. Buy a new copy if it's released under the new/current/chosen name
4. When classifying queer identities or topics that current systems don't address (e.g. some systems don't have "Indigiqueer" or "Cripqueer" for example) consider the following options:
 - a. Add in description fields that display in your OPAC Discovery Layer, for example [500](#) or [590](#), to more clearly describe the topic. For more information, see [Section 4.4.3. Discoverability](#)
 - b. For Library of Congress Classification, use the main category that the work belongs to and then create up a topical cutter alphabetically that best fits and prioritises the language used by the people. Make sure it fits in the shelf-listing. For Dewey or Universal Decimal Classification—which use numbers instead of letters—use the general number and devise an appropriate Cutter.
 - c. In a consortial environment, where it may be the case that your library can only use what LC offers/provides, consider adding a standardised public note to your library's holding record to acknowledge the error and harm in the LC schedule and offer a brief explanation as to why the classification still exists/why it cannot be changed in your institution's catalogue.
5. For potentially problematic historical/medical topics, consider the following:

- a. If it is intended for a general non-medical audience, then it doesn't make sense to be in medicine and should be elsewhere with queer or MORGAI topics.
 - b. Things about medicine go in medicine-related classifications, things that are more general in nature and/or about culture, go with gender-related classifications.
6. To explore currently available classification options for resources on topics related to queer or MORGAI people and their experiences, please see Sections [6.4.2.1. Library of Congress Classification Numbers](#) and [6.4.2.2. Dewey Decimal Classification Numbers](#). However, remember that these currently “established” classification notations may not be adequate, so keep in mind the recommendations above.

4.2. Subject Headings

This section provides best practices on how catalogers and other metadata workers can inclusively and accessibly create and revise metadata for cultural heritage materials centred on queer people, communities, histories, and contexts. As stated in the document's introduction, we use “queer” as an umbrella term for non-MORGAI, relationships, genders, and (a)sexualities.

We hope that providing guidance on the subject assignment of queer subjects and contexts, that metadata creators will be better equipped to:

1. make queer collections more visible and discoverable for the folks that want to access them,
2. ensure that the history, culture, and identity of queer people are reflected respectfully within the subject headings and other descriptive metadata assigned or created for them, and
3. create pathways for patrons to contact the organisation with any instances of queerphobic and queer-antagonistic language in descriptive metadata so that anti-oppressive changes can be made.

4.2.1. Revision, Replacement, and Repair

This section serves as an overview of Library of Congress Subject Headings (LCSH) that can be used for queer resources. LCSH is the most widely-used subject heading thesaurus in the world, and most commonly used in archival and library contexts. It is often supported by additional subject headings; for example, in Canada, GLAMS institutions often use Canadian Subject Headings alongside LCSH.

4.2.1.1. Use of LCSH in describing queer works

This section provides best practices on the use, revision, and replacement of LCSH for the bibliographic and archival description of works centred on queer subjects. Because LCSH and its translations are arguably the most ubiquitous subject vocabulary used in GLAMS institutions, it is important to provide guidelines on how workers who are assigning metadata to queer people and topics can use LCSH in a way that centres queer perspectives as much as is currently possible. In this section we have also included resources for metadata professionals who want to propose new queer LCSH, revise existing LCSH, or supplement LCSH with alternative vocabularies such as Homosaurus or the Gender, Sex and Sexual Orientation (GSSO) health sciences ontology.

4.2.1.2. Problematic LCSH

For the purpose of this document, we are defining problematic LCSH terminology as terminology showing attitudes (such as homophobia, cisnormativity, transphobia, or racism) or ideas that are offensive, outdated, euphemistic, or otherwise inappropriate and harmful. Additionally, there are instances where the terminology itself is not problematic, but the usage of that terminology in a particular instance is. This would include using only broad umbrella terms or subject headings to describe materials about queer topics when there exist more appropriate and specific terms that would improve access for users. For example, using the heading “Sexual minorities” rather than the more specific headings “Lesbians” or “Gay men” when a resource is about a particular group. Use of a broad term over existing more accurate terms can have multiple consequences. It can conflate identities that have their own unique experiences and challenges, and on a metadata level it can reduce the discoverability of materials that are about specific people and groups. At the same time, it is worthwhile to include multiple ways for users to find a work, and so when a work is about a specific queer person or group, including both narrower and broader terms is recommended.

A full list of problematic LCSH, Library of Congress Demographic Group Terms ([LCDGT](#)), LC Children and Young Adult Cataloging ([CYAC](#)), and Medical Subject Headings ([MeSH](#)) can be found in [Section 6.4.1. Subject Headings](#). Please note that these headings are current as of [June 2024], and have been brought to the attention of the [Gender & Sexuality SACO Funnel](#) for their current and/or future revision projects.

4.2.1.3. Proposing a new subject heading

Most LCSH are created by the Library of Congress (LC) or members of a Subject Authority Cooperative Program (SACO) funnel.³² However, it is possible and recommended for people outside of LC/SACO to propose new topical LCSH through their formal proposal process. Proposals for new subject headings are reviewed monthly. Lists of proposed headings [can be found here](#) and comments about them can be sent to listcomments@loc.gov.

When looking to make a proposal for a new or existing queer related subject heading or group of headings, metadata workers should first consider if this work is already being done at the funnel level. Reach out to Gender & Sexuality Subject Authority Cooperative (SACO) Funnel through the email on LC's [Gender and Sexuality Funnel Project](#) with the subject heading or group of headings that you are looking to create or revise. If it is not being worked on by the funnel, you can connect with the Cataloging Lab at cataloginglab.org to begin a collaborative project, or to work on the proposal on your own. A guide for navigating the LC proposal process can be found in Beck Schaefer's [How to Propose a New Topical LCSH](#).

4.2.1.4. Making a variant heading the authorised heading

Many queer LCSH headings have variants that are a better fit than the authorised heading. These variant headings can be found by navigating to the subject heading's authority file and looking through the [450 fields](#). When proposing a revised heading to LC, consider referencing the variant and requesting that be the preferred terminology.

Metadata workers can also consider using [CYAC](#), which is sometimes more current than LCSH. Some CYAC headings are listed as variants of the LCSH authorised heading. Some headings are only in one or the other. Because CYAC and LCSH have separate creation processes, there are some inconsistencies.

- Coming out (Sexual orientation) (LCSH) vs. Coming out (CYAC)
- Transsexuals (LCSH) vs. Transsexual people (CYAC)
- [Sexual minorities](#) (LCSH) vs. [LGBTQ+ people](#) (CYAC)

³² SACO Funnels are groups within SACO that contribute subject headings with a particular focus. The Gender and Sexuality SACO Funnel Project creates proposals for new LC authority records and revisions to existing authority records “used in the cataloguing of resources about, for, and by transgender, gender diverse, intersex, asexual, and other queer, non-heteronormative or non-heterosexual people.” In addition to Library of Congress Subject Headings, the group also makes proposals for other Library of Congress controlled vocabularies such as the Library of Congress Demographic Group Terms. If you have an idea for a new subject heading or a revision to an existing one, it's best to get in touch with the Gender and Sexuality Funnel at <https://www.loc.gov/aba/pcc/saco/gender-sexuality-funnel.html>.

4.2.2. Use of non-LCSH controlled vocabularies and ontologies

If LCSH, CYAC, or other Library of Congress controlled vocabularies do not meet the level of specificity necessary for a work's description, there are a few other controlled vocabulary options that can be used, as well as best practices around the use of local terms.

A primary solution to many of the problems currently experienced in queer subject assignment will be to use Homosaurus, a linked data controlled thesaurus for the description and retrieval of queer resources. While the infrastructure of regularly updating Homosaurus terms in bibliographic records is still being developed, the currency, flexibility, and specificity of Homosaurus terms over LCSH will arguably lead to greater inclusivity and discoverability of queer library materials.

4.2.2.1. Supplementing LCSH with queer-specific identities and experiences

When the LCSH term is not sufficient in specificity or clarity, metadata workers should consider adding additional terminology from alternative thesauri while retaining the LCSH term(s). [Homosaurus](#) can be assigned for works of any subject. The [Gender, Sex, and Sexual Orientation ontology](#) (GSSO) can be assigned to works in the health sciences and should also be paired with [MeSH](#) when appropriate. These are the best known options for alternative thesauri for a current, continuously maintained vocabulary that cover a large scope of terms from queer communities, for both historical and contemporary use.

A third option that may be useful particularly for special collections, museums, and archives is the [Getty Research Institute's Art & Architecture Thesaurus](#) (AAT), which also supports linked data.

4.2.2.2. Replacing problematic LCSH terminology

When an LCSH term is identified as problematic, consider the following:

1. Use a Homosaurus or GSSO replacement term. Using an existing controlled vocabulary that is collaboratively maintained is easier for metadata workers and provides clarity and consistency across institutions. The Cooperative Computer Services (CCS) in Illinois' guide to [Homosaurus Subject Headings](#) is a helpful example.
2. If an appropriate term can't be found in an existing controlled vocabulary and it is necessary to apply a local authority, contact Homosaurus or the GSSO and request that term be added to the vocabulary. This can help other institutions

who might also want to use that same term. A local term can be applied while that new term is being developed by the vocabulary.

3. Reach out to QMDC members. QMDC will follow up with the most appropriate funnel and bring the term to their attention, if it has not been brought to them already.
4. Allow suggestions from patrons. This could take the form of a formal audit process, a submission form, or focus groups with individuals in the community.
5. Create an internal working group to review problematic terms and explore options. When recruiting members for this group, place emphasis on centring marginalised experiences and identities.

4.2.3. Prioritisation of terms used by creators

Prioritise using the terms the creators of the work have used in subject descriptor fields, even if those terms aren't found in controlled vocabularies. Controlled vocabularies are never going to keep pace with a living language, and so if subject headings are lacking, then metadata workers can and should find other places in the metadata to provide accurate and clear description.

A few ways to add uncontrolled terms to a MARC metadata record include:

- [MARC field 650](#) _7 with a \$2 local
- [MARC Field 653](#), as an uncontrolled index term. Uncontrolled index terms are subject terms that do not belong to a controlled subject heading system or thesaurus
- [MARC field 690](#), as a local subject term.

A few other places to add preferred language in the MARC record include:

- [MARC 246](#), a variant title field for when the subtitle contains the term
- [MARC 505](#), a formatted contents note for when the contents do
- [MARC 520](#), a summary notes field

Archival collections also support subject analysis, and topical subjects are not out of compliance with DACS. For DACS compliant finding aids, these terms can generally be included in the scope and content note ([MARC tag 520](#)) or biographical and historical note ([MARC tag 545](#)). However, your institution's DACS → MARC crosswalk may differ so check compliance with your local context.

For more information about LCSH, including how subject headings are used and assigned, see the Library of Congress' [Subject Headings Manual](#); particularly helpful is [H 180 Assigning and Constructing Subject Headings](#). There are also instruction sheets for various formats and topics.

4.2.3. Topics Requiring Special Attention

4.2.3.1. Prejudicial Language in LGBTQ+ Works

There are a few strategies metadata workers can use to address the outdated, discriminatory, or otherwise problematic ways that non-queer authors describe queer subjects and topics. People who are the subjects of these works should be described how they would most want to be described. If a non-LGBTQ+ author has dominated the work with their idea of who their subjects are, then that self-identification piece can be difficult.

4.2.3.2. Usage of a Harmful Content Statement

Another approach that many institutions have begun using in the last decade is to include a harmful content or harmful language statement in their library catalogues, finding aids, and digital collections platforms. These statements have several components. The statement first informs the user about the outdated/offensive language that they may encounter in the catalogue and that the institution is aware it is present. Next, they explain where that offensive language came from, be it from the archival material itself, a controlled vocabulary (i.e. Library of Congress Subject Headings), or language added by past metadata workers of the institution. Then, they make it clear that the library is in the process of remediating and revising what harmful language they can, and make it clear that remediation work is iterative and ongoing. These statements are not an opportunity to hand wave responsibility on the part of the library, but instead serve as a place of accountability and goal setting. It is also common for some institutions to include mechanisms in their statement or in their Ask a Librarian chat features to submit feedback and suggestions.

The first recommended step in considering crafting a Harmful Content Statement is to review the work that has already been completed by GLAMS institutions. Violet Fox's Cataloging Lab includes a non-exhaustive [list of statements on bias in library and archives description](#), which includes a wide range of institutions including archives, academic libraries, museums, and public libraries. We have included examples from Collective members in [Section 6.3.1. Harmful Metadata Statement Examples](#).

When a harmful language warning is needed for a specific work, we recommend the addition of a harmful language warning in the bibliographic record's notes field. This harmful language warning should be visible on the discovery layer when possible. Depending on your ILS/discovery layer, cataloger permissions, and user base, these advisories may be placed in a few different fields: the [500 General Note Field](#), [520 4/](#)

[Content Note Field](#), or [590 Local Note Field](#). It is also possible to create an alert to the content separate from the MARC record, but embedded in the discovery layer itself—we recommend you choose the one with the most visibility, and that you consider advocating for both.

Examples:

- 520 4/ \$a Author uses homophobic slurs throughout text.
 - Displays as “Content advice: Author uses homophobic slurs throughout text.” Something to keep in mind with this option is that your ILS/discovery layer will need to be set up correctly for the 1st indicator to insert the “Content advice” note.
- Variant coding options:
 - 500 // \$a Content warning: Author uses homophobic slurs throughout text.
 - 590 // \$a Content warning: Author uses homophobic slurs throughout text.
- Alert in discovery layer, as in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Alt Text: Image of an example of an item record with a content statement link that users could click to learn more

Finally, we recommend having an action plan in place in the case of individual, local, or political pushback for its inclusion. Here are some broad recommendations from Collective members:

- Have a working group. It is easier to address internal or external pushback/feedback when the work is distributed as a group, especially with members distributed across your institution.
- Keep in constant communication with your administration and affirm/demand for specifics on why there is or may be pushback.

- Use external resources, like the Cataloging Lab list mentioned above, or statements at similar institutions in your local area, to strengthen your argument. External standards are also helpful.
- If rejected – keep going. Archive your efforts and return to the issue in a defined amount of time (preferably soon.)

4.2.3.3. Adding Controlled Prejudicial Language Vocabulary Terms

Another way of addressing or otherwise informing users of prejudicial or otherwise outdated language in a work is to include genre headings that reflect that prejudicial language. The [Controlled Vocabulary for Rare Materials Cataloging](#) includes a broad genre/form term for [prejudicial works](#), under which can be found terms for “Anti-LGBTQ+ works”, “Homophobic works”, and “Transphobic works”, as well as other discriminatory terms. While this vocabulary is maintained by the Rare Books and Materials Section, a work does not have to be an archival or rare work to use the vocabulary for it.

The Homosaurus also has terms that name cis/heteronormative ideologies or otherwise discriminatory perspectives, such as “Amatonormativity”, “Anti-LGBTQ+ violence”, “Compulsory monogamy”, “Heterosexism”, and other examples.

The only other difference is that these vocabularies occupy a MARC 655 field (i.e. 655 /7 \$2 rbmscv or \$2 homoit). CVEG co-editors can be reached at vocabularies@rbms.info and accept proposals for terms via their [Controlled Vocabularies Proposal Form](#). Homosaurus editors can be reached and accept new terms via their [contact form](#).

4.2.4. Assigning headings for historical identity labels that are no longer commonly used

The language used within queer communities to describe ourselves has changed and will continue to change as we grow and evolve. When describing works in a historical context, it is recommended to use the language the queer creator used for themselves at that time. When that language is outdated, applied by someone not explicitly queer, or is offensive, consider using Homosaurus or RBMS CV [prejudicial materials](#) terminology.

4.2.5. Assigning headings to ambiguous materials

Some materials may contain ambiguous or undefined queer subjects. It is important to be inclusive of those who existed prior to our current understanding of gender/sexuality, and to recognize that our understandings of gender/sexuality evolve over time and across different cultures. While prioritising the self-identification of

historical figures is important, we also want to make materials findable for a modern audience. In order to balance these two needs, we recommend adding queer subject headings using modern terms to make these materials findable, while also including descriptive or summary notes that clarify the nature of the material and the ambiguity therein.

4.3 Names, Naming & Authorities

This section covers updating or changing name authority records (NARs) created as part of the Name Authority Cooperative Program (NACO), but also physical items, and Wikidata items.³³ This section also includes a list of recommended resources with templates that can be amended to fit most institutional needs.

Most importantly, creators are the ultimate authority on their name. Publications (both digital and print), websites, and other sources may have outdated information that cannot be used as the source of authority. The creator is the source of authority on their name, and it is important that confirmation of a current name is received from either the creator directly if possible, or a channel managed by them. In the event the creator is deceased, consider consultation with the following groups (if possible) in this order: public statements by the individual, correspondence, partner(s) at time of death, chosen family members, community members, children (adopted or biological), and if all other options are exhausted, family of origin. If conflicting information is received, try to prioritise this order to the extent possible, always documenting your decision.

The recommendations listed in this document are not exhaustive, nor will it be possible to apply all of them in every metadata scenario. There may be limitations in areas such as communication and requested privacy. The Naming Authorities Working Group acknowledges these limitations and encourages metadata workers to follow these recommendations to the best of their ability without sacrificing quality for completeness. In addition, the recommendations offered may not fit within existing cataloguing guidelines for every institution; please use this document as a foundation when updating documentation.

4.3.1. What to include in a name authority record

First, consider that name authority records are meant to disambiguate between individuals. The goal of an authority record is therefore not to comprehensively

³³ Section 3.2 of the TMDC's Best Practices offers the most comprehensive guidance on name and gender changes in/to NARs and should be read alongside or as a companion to this section.

biography an individual. If including personal information is not possible or consented to, the metadata worker can include other identifying information such as: university attended, university publishing for, field of work, etc.³⁴

When it is deemed necessary to add information such as organisational affiliation or partners / spouses to an authority record, only include this information in consultation with the creator if possible or if it is publicly available—whether by existing authority records, or via the creator’s social media or website.³⁵ Linking partners or spouses to authority records will not be necessary for all metadata instances, and should be left to the discretion of each institution based on existing practices.

Finally, metadata and technical services professionals should keep in mind the guidelines stated by the Program for Cooperative Cataloging (PCC) and not include gender in an authority record.³⁶

4.3.2. Updating names in name authority records

When considering making significant changes to a name authority record, consult the creator, if possible, regarding the proposed change. While obtaining explicit permission from the creator is best, if that is not possible, the information may be retrieved from a site or source that the creator controls. This keeps the updated information within the creator’s realm of control, and comes from a public outlet so as to not out the creator.

Also consider the best practices set forth in the Trans Metadata Collective’s [“Metadata Best Practices for Trans and Gender Diverse Resources”](#):

If you do not know the author’s wishes, follow these principles:

- Someone’s full body of work should be accessible using their current name.³⁷
- Former names that they have previously published under should be used as little as possible and coded not to display publicly to users.
- Former names that the author has not published under should not be included.
- Do not include pronouns in 670s if possible.

³⁴ Please consult the NACO Participant’s Manual at <https://www.loc.gov/aba/pcc/naco/doc-updates.html> for further guidance on what identifying information can be included.

³⁵ See “Recommended Resources” section at the end of the document for an example on personal affiliations.

³⁶ Revised Report on Recording Gender in Personal Name Authority Records PCC Ad Hoc Task Group on Recording Gender in Personal Name Authority Records (April 7, 2022): <https://www.loc.gov/aba/pcc/documents/gender-in-NARs-revised-report.pdf>

³⁷ This is a quotation from TMDC and also <https://publicationethics.org/news/vision-more-trans-inclusive-publishing-world>

- If you are required to, correct incorrect pronouns from source materials quoted in 670 fields, taking especial care with 678 fields to note if a pronoun is cataloger judgement or derived from the source material.³⁸

Be sure to include relevant information, and how it was obtained, from your communication with authors in the [670](#). This will include the author's wishes around name usage (e.g. "author requests that former name not display in public catalogue"). Consider making a [667](#) for specific instructions from authors (e.g. "Do not add a [400](#) for former name as per author's request. Former name was used on publications until 1984." or "Author requested former name be kept in the authority record, do not remove".) (TMDC 3.2.4.1)

One option is to follow George Mason University's practice of not adding linkage to former names. If no response is received from an informational request for name authority, a separate local name authority record will be created instead of updating the name in the existing record and including the former name as a variant. This policy is an option to follow locally, but it does prevent the author's full body of work from being accessible under their current name.

More information on creating records below in [Section 4.3.4. How to update or change a name](#).

4.3.3. When to update or change a name

If the creator requests a name change, even before publishing a new work, the metadata worker should honour that request and cite personal communication in the record. If there is noticed evidence of a name change, it is best to contact the creator to confirm the change. The PCC has established a [contacting contributors guide](#) that includes sample templates for emailing creators about name authority records.

If you are working at a museum, archives, or similar cultural heritage institution where donor relations is a key function, it is recommended that the preferred public name is asked of the potential donor as part of the donation process. This prevents staff from having to repeatedly contact the donor after deeds of gift have been signed. Following

³⁸ Cases such as the Public Universal Friend demonstrate that 670s using incorrect pronouns have sometimes been updated to neutralize the pronouns (a possibly even more inaccurate change) without a note as to whether the source material had changed or if this was a cataloger-induced change (with thanks to Tess Amram for this example). Chevalier d'Eon is another example of a historical figure where some institutions have made a deliberate choice to use he/him pronouns.

this step, if the donor requests a name change, follow the guidance in the paragraph above.

4.3.4. How to update or change a name

As a general guideline, this Working Group recommends following the guidance of the Trans Metadata Collective's ["Best Practices"](#) document on how to make changes in an authority record:

- "Use the same form of name throughout the bib record" (the most likely scenario is to replace any former names with the current name in brackets)
- Prioritise purchase of new editions etc. with current names
- "Change the name on the book" (TMDC 3.2.6)

When working within a local system, there are several ways to include an author's former name for enhanced searching and linking from the former name to the current name. Per the TMDC, including an author's former name should begin, if possible, with consulting the author for their wishes on the inclusion of said name. For institutions which use MARC, one potential option (if the author does not already have an authority record) is to code the former name in a [4xx field](#) and add a non-public note or [667 field](#) explaining the inclusion of the former name/former name.

Also in institutions which use MARC an author's former name can be coded as a [4xx](#) or [5xx](#) heading, though this is not a core requirement. To code this as a reference point or not to display the name, a "w" subfield can be added to the front of the field, which includes up to four characters. To ensure the former name will not be displayed, an "a" can be coded as the fourth character. (TMDC 3.2.4.2)

It is possible that a creator may request their current name not be linked to their former one. In this case, an option would be to create separate name authority records in the library's local system but not contribute these separate records to a larger database. However, it is important to consider that data that is hidden in a local system may appear and be publicly available if contributed to a larger system like NACO, VIAF, Wikidata, etc. Information suppressed in NACO records will still appear as publicly available linked data on id.loc.gov ([NACO Participants' Manual](#), page 93). We recommend removing these suppressed fields from a record before contributing it to a larger database like NACO.

4.3.5. Linking names or other identities

According to the cataloguer's discretion on a case-by-case basis, one may choose to link identities such as drag or ball identities or former names.³⁹ Metadata workers must consider the extent to which a creator uses a name or persona publicly before linking any identities to the authority record.⁴⁰ Take especial care with the linking of historical authorities as examples and follow the Collective's Chain of Trust in guiding your decision.

4.3.6. Updating names on physical items

Following the updating of the creator within the metadata, best practical efforts to update the name on the physical item should be made as well.

In the case of circulating materials, if there exists an edition of the item with the creator's preferred name, it is recommended to prioritise purchasing this edition if it is within the institution's budget to do so.

In the event no updated edition exists, or if one cannot be acquired, and if it is feasible for staff based on the quantity of materials and staff time, it is recommended to relabel the item itself with the creator's preferred name. This does not necessarily mean covering the previous name in every location it appears, as this is likely not feasible when this can include page headers, the title page, title page verso, cover, and more. A label on the material connecting the updated name to the previous name is recommended, such as:

Authority Heading: Stevenson, N. D.
Alternate Name: Stevenson, Noelle

In the case of special collections, archives, and other non-circulating materials, there are considerations to give with regards to the rarity of the item. In these cases, a call slip or correction sheet can be inserted into the item.

Again, the creator is the ultimate authority on their name, and so if they do not want the two identities connected, follow their wishes and avoid doing so. For deceased creators, the best practice is to follow their last wishes for how they preferred to be

³⁹ For example, the Public Universal Friend often has their birth name added as a 400. The Friend abandoned that name and never published under it (or signed legal documents with it), although many people writing about the Friend even today use it. This is incorrect. Many other historical figures' authority files such as Antonio d'Erauso's have similar errors.

⁴⁰ See authority records for Shangela (<https://lccn.loc.gov/no2020093795>) and Bianca del Rio (<https://lccn.loc.gov/no2018142363>) as examples of drag identities being the primary name.

referred to and what identities they connected themselves to publicly. If this is unclear, or if there is conflicting information, consider consultation with the following sources or groups in this order: public statements; public or private correspondence; partner(s) at time of death; chosen family members; community members; children (adopted or biological); and if all other options are exhausted, family of origin. Utilise best judgement and discretion and consider how certain labels could affect still-living individuals connected to the deceased creator.

Regardless of how else the name is replaced on the material, call numbers using the creator's correct name as an accessibility point should be updated to reflect the creator's preferred name as it displays in the metadata.

4.3.7. Wikidata

Wikidata acts as central storage and the data backbone of the Wikimedia ecosystem by providing structured data to its Wikimedia sister projects, which include Wikipedia, Wikivoyage, Wiktionary, Wikisource, and so on.⁴¹ It also serves as an important identifier and metadata hub for other GLAMS linked data aggregators and triplestores on the Semantic Web including the Library of Congress linked data Service, OCLC's VIAF, and Google.

Wikidata publishes linked open data entities in the form of internationally-shared Wikidata "items," across language and cultural boundaries, which and anyone on the Web can access and edit the item database. Human editors can edit items in Wikidata by hand, or they can create bots to do it for them.

4.3.7.1. Wikidata's Property P21

Among other entities, Wikidata items are created to describe individuals, communities, and resources they serve many of the same purposes authority records from traditional name authority databases. However, Wikidata is particularly problematic when used to record metadata about MORGAI individuals, communities, and resources, particularly because of property [P21, "sex or gender,"](#) also known as "gender identity, gender expression, gender, biological sex, and sex," which conflates concepts of sex, orientation, gender identity, and gender modality.⁴²

⁴¹ https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:Main_Page

⁴² The name P21 comes from the fact that it is the 21st property in Wikidata. It is also the property's URI: <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Property:P21>. P21 also lists three [related properties](#): "[Grammatical gender](#)," "[Sexual orientation](#)," and "[Personal pronoun](#)." The relationship P21 and these other properties is problematic because related properties bidirectional and they are used to indicate that other properties provide additional information. This means that Wikidata editors are using the values of "sex or gender" to infer the values of grammatical gender or personal pronoun. For example, a Wikidata editor examining

The property's talk (documentation) page indicates that allowed property values includes things like "male, female, intersex, trans woman, trans man, non-binary," etc."⁴³ While some non-English values are included, the options are not encompassing of trans and gender diverse identities nor the diverse sociolinguistic representations of gender more broadly and (also) conflates concepts of sex, orientation, gender identity, and gender modality.

Qualifiers (limiting statements) for P21 include "[start time](#)" and "[end time](#)," among others, but these too are often applied inconsistently and conflate concepts of sex, orientation, gender identity, and gender modality.

References are not required for P21, and when they are used, they are often insufficient. Generally speaking, Wikidata statements are supposed to include references, the exceptions being a) when the value of a statement is common knowledge b) when it refers to an external source of information, or c) when the item itself is a source for the statement.⁴⁴

Wikidata is rife with assumptions that sex or gender can be assumed as common knowledge inferred from an individual's characteristics. For example, Wikidata contributors use private database information, old social media posts, and other information without the consent of the person.

Worse, contributor-created bots use problematic heuristics to infer binary gender identities and apply to Wikidata items for human beings on massive scales.⁴⁵ Some of the problematic heuristics used by bots include:

- "[inferred from pronoun used](#)"
- "[inferred from grammatical gender used in text](#)"
- "[inferred from given name](#)"
- "[image and pronoun used](#)" and
- "[inferred from honorific](#)."

[B.M. Watson's page](#) may use "male" in P21 assign the (incorrect) pronoun "he" to Watson. Conversely, editors use grammatical gender, sexual orientation, and/or personal pronouns to infer an individual's sex or gender. These inferences are wrong and do disproportionate harm to queer and trans communities.

⁴³ <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Property:P21>. The page also indicates that it is meant to apply to [humans](#) or [animals](#), but it has been used in the past for [imaginary characters](#), [abstract beings](#), [alter egos](#), [fossils](#), [organisms](#), [robots](#), [sex dolls](#), [synthetic voices](#), [taxons](#), [kunya](#), [dolls or action figure models](#), [fictional creatures](#), and [fictional taxons](#).

⁴⁴ https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Help:Sources/Items_not_needing_sources

⁴⁵

https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:Project_chat/Archive/2021/05#Bots_using_Labels_to_Potentially_Misgender_Humans

Finally, individuals are referred to by their former name⁴⁶ in Wikidata labels, particularly in the “Also named as” sections. Other Wikidata properties which contain or indicate the presence of former names include:

- [Name \(P2561\)](#)
- [Married name \(P2562\)](#)
- [Name in native language \(P1559\)](#)
- [Nickname \(P1449\)](#)
- [Pseudonym \(P742\)](#)
- [Family name \(P734\)](#)
- [Second family name in Spanish name \(P1950\)](#)
- [Given name \(P735\)](#)
- [Official name \(P1448\)](#)
- [Short name \(P1813\)](#)
- [Alternative name \(P4970\)](#)
- [Birth name \(P1477\)](#)

Intentionally using a person’s former name is a cruel and inaccurate metadata practice and should be avoided in order to protect the people who are the subjects of description. The TMDC recommendations has much more information on this topic.

Users have repeatedly asked for restrictions and best practices to be put in place surrounding this issue, but no common best practices exist for applying this property to living or deceased persons with regard to privacy or consent, and policies are unclear and inconsistently enforced. As the authors of [Findings on Knowledge Equity in Linked Open Data](#) point out, P21 “functionally marginalizes accurate knowledge about LGBTQ+ and Queer communities and peoples.”⁴⁷

Difficulty with the use of Property 21 (a property conflating sex and gender) and lack of clear policy and enforcement of policy describing living people were described by almost all of the participants. The attempts to address these concerns end up in unresolved conversations and no solution for a long time. Lack of resolution of issues like this results in the potential of proliferation of incorrect information and mis-identification of people, and harms. For example, harms like dead naming, misgendering and outing people can occur. It is not safe for people to be identified in a certain way, and there is no consent process

⁴⁶ Sometimes these are referred to as “deadnames,” but generally speaking usage is trending away from that and “former name” also connects with other non-trans, but gender diverse uses, including people who change their name in marriage or for Indigenous reasons. See TMDC’s discussion of this as well as the work of the Name Change Policy Working Group (NCPWG; <https://ncpwg.org>).

⁴⁷ See [Summary of findings on Knowledge Equity in Linked Open Data, submitted to Wikimedia Deutschland](#)

for biography or description of living people. If a LGBTQ+ or Queer person is living somewhere where it is illegal to be who they are, being outed in the LOD ecosystem can be very dangerous.⁴⁸

Wikidata's sex or gender (P21) property, its lack of specific guidance against using former names, and its unclear policies and dispute resolution guidelines surrounding consent, privacy, and living people set Wikidata editors up to fail by making false and harmful inferences—inferences which disproportionately affect queer communities. More information about Wikidata and Wikipedia guidance and governance is available in [6.3.2.3. Additional Wikidata Considerations for GLAMS Metadata Workers](#).

4.3.7.2. Updating & Correction of Wikidata Items

This subsection is meant to serve as a “ready reference” for metadata workers undertaking Wikidata updates or corrections. These processes are described and documented in greater detail (with screenshots!) in [Section 6.3.2. Updating & Correction of Wikidata Items](#)

4.3.7.1. Updating Wikidata Items

This is an overview of the process of Wikidata editing; a more detailed guide to the editing process (including screenshots) is available in [Section 6.3.2. Updating Wikidata Items](#). [The Training Resources section](#) of the Practical Wikidata for Librarians page is also useful. To update existing authorities in Wikidata use the following steps.

1. In the search menu at the top right of the page search for the name you want to edit.
2. Search First name Last Name e.g. “Billy Porter” to find the actor's entry, which is at the URI <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q4913177>
3. In the upper right of his entry click the “Edit” link
4. The first box contains the main form the person's name and you may place the cursor in the field and make desired changes
5. Following are a set of “statements” about the person such as sex, gender, sexual orientation, given name (which may contain a person's former name) and others. Each may be edited by clicking the “Edit” link in the top right corner of each box.
 - New information may be added to each statement by clicking “+Add Value” at the left.

⁴⁸ Ibid.

- You may also insert references justifying your choice of entry by clicking “+Add Reference”
 - New Statements may be added as well by scrolling to the end of the statements list and clicking “+Add Statement”
6. When finished editing, return to the top of the entry and select “Publish” to save the changes.

4.3.7.2. Correcting Wikidata Items

While some metadata professionals and Wikidata editors have proposed solutions to the issues caused by P21, as of the writing of this document there no consensus.

However, there are three helpful options:

1. Option 1: Talk it out.

When you see a piece of harmful or incorrect information, find where the information came from via the item history. Once found, go to that editor’s talk page and kindly but firmly describe how their edit was harmful and that you are removing / changing it, and then do so. Option 1 is the most emotionally taxing and time-consuming approach, but also the most effective.

2. Option 2: Undo

Find the problematic edit, hit the “undo” button, enter a brief explanation of why you are undoing the edit, correct the information, and move on. This option is less obtrusive to the person who did the initial edit, but it is also easier for them to reverse.

3. Option 3: Directly edit

Unreferenced statements can be deleted without any conversation, but they can be just as easily added back with no justification. However, deleting referenced statements with no justification is considered bad manners in Wikidata and is not recommended. Always leave a note. You can edit incorrect statements and replace them with referenced, correct statements if you have the information available

These (especially Option 1) are described in greater detail in [6.3.2.2. Correcting Wikidata Items](#). Information on what constitutes good references is available in [Section 6.3.2.3. Additional Wikidata Considerations](#).

4.3.7.4. General Wikidata Recommendations

4.3.7.4.1. Preliminary Questions

Questions to consider before adding information about a person's gender identity or modality to Wikidata:

- Does recording a value add value to the item record?
- Does it increase representation of underrepresented groups in a particular field?
- Is the person's gender identity or modality important to build context about the individual's life and contributions to a field?
- Is the person's gender identity or modality an important piece of information as it relates to the person's work (i.e. are they an author who writes about gender diverse characters)?
- Do I have the cultural competency and language fluency to adequately record the gender identity or modality of the individual?
- Could recording gender information result in harm toward the person?
- Is there a direct, public record of the individual stating their own gender identity or modality?

4.3.7.4.2. P21 "sex or gender"

- P21 should only be used when the gender modality and gender identity provide context about why the person is notable.
- When using P21, only use the gender identity and gender modality as stated by the individual publicly in their own words.
- Use only culturally and linguistically appropriate terms for gender identities and modalities as stated by the individual in P21.
- All gender-related property values in P21 should have a reference that points back to the individual's statement. References should be both public and up-to-date.
- Correct P21 statements that are incorrect. Consider reaching out to the individual if you are able to inform them of the error and correction.

Additional caveat: the intersex value should only be used in P21 if stated by the person as part of their identity or work.

4.3.7.4.3. Things to Not Do:

- Do not use bots or Quickstatements to assign gender identity, gender modality, or sex to individuals based on heuristic means or anything other than public self-identification.

- Do not modify gender modality or gender identity to fit the sociolinguistic background of the Wikidata editor rather than that of the individual (no one-to-one mapping).
- Do not infer and assign gender identity or modality from absence of evidence (for example, assuming someone to be cisgender if they do not publicly identify as transgender).
- Do not provide values for gender identity, gender identity, or sex without a reference.
- Do not use “announcement” or “start date” statements (i.e. do not say someone “announced as transgender” or “started as non-binary” at such-and-such a date.
- Do not record assigned sex at birth.

4.4. Description

Description is the “body” of how GLAMS collections are contextualised in library catalogues, finding aids, digital platforms, and other sources of information about GLAMS materials. Description is essential for conveying the usefulness of a collection or asset, providing its core identifying information. Description can contain biographical or personal information, as well as broader historical, physical, or other details. As description fields are key for search and reuse in cultural heritage systems, it is vital that queer people and communities are represented properly in them. Descriptive standards, from across the cultural heritage spectrum, often do not have provisions for queer identities, with little consideration for privacy nor for plurality of being or changes in cultural understandings of queerness across time. These recommendations serve to fill those gaps and guide towards better descriptive work.

We define description in this section as any of the following:

- Alternative text
- Bibliographic records:
 - Abstracts/Scope
 - Biography and History
- Captions
- Digital collections:
 - Descriptions
 - Notes
 - Preservation descriptive fields
- Exhibit labels or curator descriptions
- Finding aids:
 - Abstracts
 - Scope and Content Notes

- Biography and History
- Record Group / Series / Fond / Folder / Item
- Processing notes
- Titles (Digital collections, exhibits, etc.)

These description types frequently contain information that identifies or describes individuals, locations, and/or appearances, often in free-text. These fields will be the subject of analysis in this section of the best practices.

These recommendations consider detailed analysis of specific descriptive standards and metadata schemas as out of scope due to their large number and their varying usage levels across GLAMS institutions.⁴⁹ Instead, the recommendations are intentionally broad in order to apply to any institution or descriptive practice in archives, libraries, museums, digital collections, and visual resource collections. This section provides recommendations based on current literature, internal documentation that was shared with QMDC by our colleagues, research interviews of queer knowledge workers, and the professional experience of Collective members.

4.4.1. General Recommendations

4.4.1.2. When to Describe Someone as Queer

“As community archives are often created under the desire to be visible, known, represented—and celebrated—the concept of representational subversion reminds us that, alongside a person, family, or group’s right to be remembered, is their equally important right to be forgotten or to forget....The right to be forgotten/unseen or to forget surfaces alongside the right to be remembered or visible.”⁵⁰

— Joyce Gabiola, Gracen Brilmyer, Michelle Caswell, Jimmy Zavala

Describing individuals in collection descriptive fields can be complicated. Sometimes, subjects make their identities clear through the ways in which they describe themselves. But, often you will be in the position of needing to describe an individual who has not clearly defined their own identities in any of the materials in front of you, and you will need to come up with your own language to use in collection and item titles, captions, alt text, biographical notes, and other areas of description records.

⁴⁹ As pointed out by a peer reviewer, DACS and Dublin Core are very widely used and also quite generic, so many other systems are similar or are based on them, so recommendations may have broader-than stated applicability.

⁵⁰ Gabiola, Joyce, Gracen Brilmyer, Michelle Caswell, and Jimmy Zavala. 2022. “It’s a Trap’: Complicating Representation in Community-Based Archives.” *American Archivist* 85 (1): 60–87. doi: <https://doi.org/10.17723/2327-9702-85.1.60>

Describing someone as queer can be fraught, because it assumes what queerness must be when it can look very different for everyone. In addition, outing or identifying someone as queer without their consent can cause harm and have negative repercussions.

Out-ness is not a binary wherein any explicit self-identification of queerness found in a collection (for example, in letters to friends or partners) means that an individual was out or would be comfortable with being out more publicly. Someone might be out personally but not in their professional life, or be out to some people in their lives but not others. An individual's right to privacy around their identity does not expire, description workers should strive to respect the agency, self-identification, and subject's wishes as best as possible.⁵¹ Considerations may include:

- What evidence is there that the subject was or was not out?
 - If there is evidence they were out, to whom were they out? Is there anyone to whom they were not out?
- Is there any indication that the subject would like to be identified as queer?

In situations where it is clear that the subject is queer but it is not clear if they were out or how they would like to be described, the decision should be made in consultation with others. Who should be consulted and what this consultation might look like will be discussed later in this section.

Describing a person as queer in a finding aid, exhibition label, or similar should always be done with purpose and care. Sometimes this will require doing research to establish the identity of the person. Before doing so, determine if this information is relevant to the material and how the items will be used. Some questions to ask can include:

- Is there evidence of any kind outside your perception of the subject?
- Would a similar description be given if the person being described was straight/cis/etc.?
- Will including this information enhance understanding of this object in context?
- Has the person being described consented to the inclusion of information on their queerness?
- Would a researcher on queer history be interested in and find relevant materials within the collection?
- Is this person out (i.e. publicly queer) or is it a resource by an "out" person?

⁵¹ Note that we are not referring to legal rights here, but instead are speaking to our ethical obligations to the donors and subjects of our collections. Something being legally permissible does not mean that it is ethical.

If you cannot justify a purpose or intention in a queer description, reevaluate if one is necessary.

Once you have established that including queerness in a description is important and relevant, the next step is to figure out how the person would want to be described. Consultation is the best way to avoid assumptions or misrepresentations of a person's identity. Depending on if the individual in question is living or deceased, the consultation process will look different. For living subjects, ask the individual directly how they would like to be identified and described. Be sure to explain the context in which the description will be used. If they ask for their queerness not to be included, it is critical that their wishes are respected. If they do not answer, consider that a no.

For deceased subjects, consider consultation with the following groups (if possible) in this order: public statements, correspondence, partner(s) at time of death, chosen family members, community members, children (adopted or biological), and if all other options are exhausted, family of origin. [Section 6.3.3. Identification of “romantic friendships,” “inseparable friends or companions,” “bosom friends,” “life friends,” and same-sex relationships](#) may also be useful to metadata workers or users of archives or museums.

In some cases, the consultation on how to describe an individual's identity will be fairly direct, such as in cases where an individual is/was out and/or there is explicitly queer content in the material(s) being described. In other instances, some materials may contain ambiguously queer or unidentified subjects. In these cases, the consultation should be less direct in order to avoid making assumptions. For example, imagine you were processing an archival collection that contained evidence that two women lived together their whole lives and that their relationship was one that may have gone beyond that of friendship or roommates, such as if one of the women inherited the other's house upon her passing and received letters of sympathy similar to those one might receive if a spouse died. In this instance, it is important neither to assume they were merely friends/roommates nor partners. In this case, you could ask the surviving person “how would you prefer we describe your relationship with [subject]?” leaving the question as open as possible. If you are not in a position to ask, simply describe the situation with facts without putting a label on the relationship.

If it is not clear from documentation, the collection materials themselves, or from donor conversations how the individual identified, it is best to avoid making any assumptions.⁵² We recognize that gender and sexuality hegemony is so embedded in culture that it can take a shift in mindset to avoid this. A person wearing a dress should

⁵²Descriptions can be limited, as they are only one access point into a person's entire life, and in turn, will always carry bias. This leaves space for future interventions.

not, in fact, be assumed to be a woman, nor should two women who appear to modern eyes to have had a romantic relationship be assumed to be lesbians, and neither should two men who lived together for decades assumed to merely be roommates. What may seem “obvious” should not be assumed without context and evidence, to avoid mis-labelling people.

Body-oriented cataloguing, as proposed by Travis Wagner, is one example of a method of avoiding making assumptions about the gender of individuals who are being described. In body-oriented cataloguing, you describe what Wagner refers to as the “gendered ways of being” rather than the gender.⁵³ For example, you can describe a photograph as being of a “person wearing a dress who is standing in a field” rather than a “woman in a field.”

The understanding of queerness in all its forms has changed over time, as has the willingness to be identified in any particular way. Cultural differences must also be respected, as different cultures describe and define queerness in different ways. Free text description, such as biographical and scope and content notes in finding aids, allow the ability to use historically, culturally, and individually appropriate terms.

4.4.1.2. Modern and Historical Terms

As a guiding rule, describe people using the names, language, and identity terms that individuals use or used for themselves.⁵⁴ Terminology can be community-based as well as individual, and it is vital to follow any knowledge practices communicated in the resource or in consultation.⁵⁵ Description fields, with the exception of titles, are also a useful place to provide further context about these terms, especially if they have changed in meaning over time, having the advantage of often being free text.⁵⁶

Do not allow your views on “correct” language or grammar to keep you from using language and terms that someone has described themselves. This may include reclaimed or self-ascribed terms otherwise understood as slurs. As such, this work necessitates flexibility, humility, and care.

⁵³ Wagner, T. (2022). Body-Oriented Cataloging as a Method of Inclusive Gender Representation. *Cataloging & classification quarterly*, 60 (6-7), p. 30.

⁵⁴ Mitchell, Benjamin. “Collections Services Manual: Inclusive Description Style Guide.” Edited by Racine Amos, Kevin Clair, Lexy deGraffenreid, and Gideon Goodrich. Penn State University Libraries, July 21, 2021.; GLBT Historical Society. “GLBT Historical Society Style Guide for Processing,” December 7, 2021.

⁵⁵ Indian Arts Research Center. 2019. Guidelines for Collaboration (website). Facilitated by Landis Smith, Cynthia Chavez Lamar, and Brian Vallo. Santa Fe, NM: School for Advanced Research. <https://guidelinesforcollaboration.info/>.

⁵⁶ Rawson, K. J., Cailin Roles, Eamon Schlotterback, and Nicole Tantum. “Metadata Application Profile.” Digital Transgender Archive, Summer 2021. https://www.digitaltransgenderarchive.net/ckeditor_assets/attachments/347/DTA_MAP_3.0.pdf, p. 26.

If the creator is living, ask the individual directly how they would like to be identified and described. Consult with them about how they would like to handle pronoun and name changes, offensive terms, content warnings, or legacy descriptive practices.⁵⁷ For example, offensive terms found in folder and box titles or in materials themselves could be put in quotes or replaced with new terminology put in brackets, depending on the individual's preference.

If they are deceased, consult the list of resources, individuals and groups listed in the previous section. As always, if it is not clear from documentation or from consultation, it is best to avoid making any assumptions. For more guidance, the [Subject Headings section](#) includes recommendations regarding the use of terminology now considered historical or offensive.

4.4.2. Metadata Remediation

It is likely that previous descriptive practices have resulted in descriptions that are harmful and insensitive to users. It is recommended that organisational websites all have a harmful materials statement and consider content warnings for descriptions where they are needed. Additionally, institutions should provide either a feedback form or an email address for users who would like to provide feedback or draw attention to harmful description. The Cataloging Lab provides many examples of these types of statements and feedback mechanisms.⁵⁸

It is generally recommended to save previous versions of description fields, like descriptions, titles, or exhibition labels, for transparency and accountability.⁵⁹ There are, however, some instances in which providing access to earlier forms of description or providing public notes on what changes have occurred would be harmful to queer and trans people. For example, if names of trans people have been updated or if the descriptive content available could be considered outing by you or other metadata workers in your institution, this type of information should not be made available to the public.

⁵⁷ Mitchell, Benjamin. "Collections Services Manual: Inclusive Description Style Guide."

⁵⁸ "List of Statements on Bias in Library and Archives Description," The Cataloging Lab, May 2024. <https://cataloginglab.org/list-of-statements-on-bias-in-library-and-archives-description/>.

⁵⁹ Antracoli, Alexis A., Annalise Berdini, Kelly Bolding, Faith Charlton, Amanda Ferrara, Valencia Johnson, and Katy Rawdon. "Archives for Black Lives in Philadelphia: Anti-Racist Description Resources." October 2020. https://archivesforblacklives.files.wordpress.com/2020/11/ardr_202010.pdf

4.4.3. Discoverability

Make note of how your patrons can access and search for materials. For archives, for example, are collections accessible through a library catalogue, a finding aid portal, both, or somewhere else? If your records are accessible online, are they keyword searchable? While some description fields can offer a level of flexibility in how we format collection descriptions, it is important to know if and how that affects patron searches. If the full metadata of your finding aid, catalogue record, or digital collections record is not keyword searchable, it might be necessary to put more emphasis on controlled vocabulary as a descriptive tool. An additional possibility is to consider adding community-derived terms.⁶⁰ These community-based keywords could also be implemented in bibliographic records as local authorities.

4.4.3.1. Aggregating Records

If you are aggregating your records, such as with a finding aid consortium or with a digital collections aggregator, such as the Digital Public Library of America (DPLA), review how your descriptive metadata is displayed on these different sites. Is all of the information you need to give context to the materials being aggregated? Is that information displayed in the fields and website views that you expect? For example, additional descriptive notes may be mapped to description fields, but then do not appear in browse list results or your aggregator may only harvest one description field. Within Texas Archival Resources Online (TARO), finding aid abstracts do not fully display on browse list views. To accommodate this, the University of Texas at Austin adapted other fields to include additional descriptive notes.⁶¹ This may be something you will need to work with your stakeholders on.

4.4.3.2. Digitisation and Digital Collections

Additional considerations should be made during digitisation. Ask yourself if queer materials should be digitised, and if so, what level of granularity and types of information should be included in the description.⁶² Questions to ask oneself include, but are not limited to:

- Could digitisation result in harm to anyone named or represented in the materials?

⁶⁰ Baucom, Erin. "An Exploration into Archival Descriptions of LGBTQ Materials." *The American Archivist*, 2018, 81, 1: p. 80.

⁶¹ Murphy, Devon. "Content Statements." *UT Libraries Metadata Documentation*. University of Texas at Austin, March 13, 2024. <https://wikis.utexas.edu/display/utlmetadata/Content+Statements>.

⁶² As a case study, see the debate that followed Reveal Digital's digitisation of the 1984–2004 lesbian porn magazine *On Our Backs* (OOB); Tara Robertson, "Not All Information Wants to be Free: The Case Study of *On Our Backs*," in *Applying Library Values to Emerging Technology: Decision-Making in the Age of Open Access, Maker Spaces, and the Ever-Changing Library* (Publications in Librarianship #72), ed. Peter D. Fernandez and Kelly Tilton (Chicago: American Library Association, 2018), 225–239.

- Does the material being considered for digitisation identify (or could lead to the identification of) any queer or trans individuals who are not out (or were not out when they were alive)?
- Was the material created in a public or private setting (was there an expectation of sharing when the material was created)?
- Are any materials depicting or describing activities that could be used as evidence in a trial (particularly relevant for activist materials)?⁶³

Sometimes it may be possible to digitise an object without identifying individuals in order to keep them unfindable, but if there is a possibility of identification or harm to represented individuals, not digitising the object(s) in question may be the safer route. These same considerations should be made for digital preservation of queer materials. While representation is important, it is not more important than safety and privacy.

4.4.3.3. Pre-existing Description

Be cautious when relying upon pre-existing descriptions for items, such as text written on the backs of photographs or original creator’s descriptions or titles. Unless you are certain that the description was written by the individual(s) described, you should not assume the recorded information is accurate. If a full collection is using the original creator’s description or title and offensive language is used, consider elaborating on the source of the language, put offensive terms in brackets,⁶⁴ or re-consider the practice.

4.4.4. Positionality Statements

While some institutions have considered or used positionality statements (notes that clarify how metadata workers are positioned, generally in terms of identity, to the item or collection being described), we do not recommend this as a general descriptive practice. Including positionality statements in records can create search noise for users. This is particularly true for sites that employ full-text/keyword search functionalities. Considering how many controlled vocabularies are inadequate for describing marginalised people and topics, description workers and researchers often

⁶³ Considerations were pulled from Seeman, Dean. “Naming Names: The Ethics of Identification in Digital Library Metadata.” Knowledge Organization, 2012, 325–331; the forthcoming Southern Trans Archives Guide from Invisible Histories (citation forthcoming once it is published).

⁶⁴ Mitchell, Benjamin. “Collections Services Manual: Inclusive Description Style Guide.” Edited by Racine Amos, Kevin Clair, Lexy deGraffenreid, and Gideon Goodrich. Penn State University Libraries, July 21, 2021; Wilson Special Collections Library. “A Guide to Conscious Editing at Wilson Special Collections Library.” The University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill University Libraries, 2022. <https://library.unc.edu/project/conscious-editing-initiative/#:~:text=Guide%20to%20Conscious%20Editing&text=The%20guide%20contains%20articles%20on.about%20racist%20and%20harmful%20content>, p. 42-50.

rely on keyword searching in free text fields to find relevant materials. Additionally, requiring positionality statements can result in some metadata workers having to choose between outing or incorrectly identifying themselves, or otherwise place workers in difficult situations. Description should focus on the content and context of the resource, rather than on the identity or identities of the metadata worker.⁶⁵

4.4.5. Community Collaboration and Consultation

Community collaboration and consultation can be helpful for descriptive work, especially if you are not familiar with the community and/or the materials being described. This is supported by the view that metadata workers should be facilitators rather than the voice of under-represented communities.⁶⁶ Community in this context can mean donors, individuals or organisations represented by collection materials, a university-based research community, local organisations, estates, or other institutions. However, consultation must be done thoughtfully and with sensitivity. Before contacting potential partners, institutions must review their ability and resources to conduct reciprocal collaboration, carefully defining boundaries and what items they can realistically support. In turn, asking people for a consultation is asking them to perform labour. Do not expect people to perform this labour, or feel entitled to their work. If appropriate, consider compensating people for their time.⁶⁷

Existing relationships may have already been established with community partners through outreach or through one's own contacts. If they have not, start with research on appropriate individuals or organisations in order to establish these relationships. Plan how you will reach out to the community, making sure that any collaboration is reciprocal and respects the community's knowledge practices. Again, consider compensation, financial or in kind.⁶⁸ Collaborations work best when they are not ad-hoc, but rather focused on particular descriptive projects. Creating an advisory board locally within your institution before building relationships farther afield can assist in focusing potential projects, as well as formally defining these relationships which can

⁶⁵ Lee, J. A. (2021). Producing the Archival Body. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780429060168>

⁶⁶ Mitchell, Benjamin. "Collections Services Manual: Inclusive Description Style Guide." Edited by Racine Amos, Kevin Clair, Lexy deGraffenreid, and Gideon Goodrich. Penn State University Libraries, July 21, 2021, p.4. https://docs.google.com/document/d/101wf8WiJBx_DY3JXrv5VvivrKa8TI8ZJ/edit#heading=h.gjdgxs.

⁶⁷ Caswell, M., Douglas, J., Chow, J., Bradshaw, R., Mallick, S., Karthikeyan, N., ... & Robinson-Sweet, A. (2021). "Come Correct or Don't Come at All:" Building More Equitable Relationships Between Archival Studies Scholars and Community Archives. <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/7v00k2qz>
It is good practice to offer compensation, but be understanding if people refuse or do not consider it appropriate.

⁶⁸ Indian Arts Research Center. 2019. Guidelines for Collaboration (website). Facilitated by Landis Smith, Cynthia Chavez Lamar, and Brian Vallo. Santa Fe, NM: School for Advanced Research. <https://guidelinesforcollaboration.info/>.

better cement their longevity.⁶⁹ Advisory boards can also be used to establish best practices at your institution, setting uniform expectations that can ensure consistency across partners.⁷⁰

Be prepared for a wide range of reactions to your outreach and requests for collaboration. Not everyone has positive relationships with cultural heritage institutions, while materials can have difficult histories; engagement with records and those that hold them can be traumatic.⁷¹ In turn, there may be resourcing issues, recognizing that communities may have other priorities or needs at the time of your request. Occasionally, the answer from the community may be simply “no” or “not right now.” Let them know that you respect their wishes and refocus on other materials.⁷²

If you need to complete the descriptive metadata within a particular timeframe, rely on existing recommendations and provide avenues for metadata feedback, documenting this approach in your work. In these circumstances it is necessary to evaluate whether the existing recommendations are enough for your particular case or if the item(s) need a focused review/wait on publication.⁷³ Once any changes have been made to the descriptive content, be sure to make these changes apparent in the metadata by describing the intervention or providing your general descriptive policy.⁷⁴

Some instances where you may want to consult other parties include:

- Material from other locations. Identify the country/state/local community and do some initial research regarding the terminology used in that area before reaching out. A number of countries have organisations that have produced their

⁶⁹One example is the Reparative Archival Description Working Group at Yale Library, <https://guides.library.yale.edu/reparativearchivaldescription>, which creates separate advisory boards for each descriptive project.

⁷⁰University of California Irvine’s Orange County and Southeast Asian Archive Center provides a good example of community collaboration best practices, as well as example standard forms for potential partners. <https://ocseaa.lib.uci.edu/partnerships>

⁷¹Indian Arts Research Center. 2019. Guidelines for Collaboration (website). Facilitated by Landis Smith, Cynthia Chavez Lamar, and Brian Vallo. Santa Fe, NM: School for Advanced Research. <https://guidelinesforcollaboration.info>; Caswell, Michelle, & Robinson-Sweet, Anna, (2023) ““It Was as Much for Me As for Anybody Else”: The Creation of Self-Validating Records,” *Journal of Contemporary Archival Studies*, 10(10). Available at: <https://elischolar.library.yale.edu/jcas/vol10/iss1/10>.

⁷²“Working at the speed of trust” is a concept from OCLC’s Reimagine Descriptive Workflows report. This emphasises that working at the pace of the community is paramount. Frick, Rachel L., and Merrilee Proffitt. 2022. Reimagine Descriptive Workflows: A Community-informed Agenda for Reparative and Inclusive Descriptive Practice. Dublin, OH: OCLC Research. <https://doi.org/10.25333/wd4b-bs51>;

⁷³Ibid.

⁷⁴Mitchell, Benjamin. “Collections Services Manual: Inclusive Description Style Guide.” Edited by Racine Amos, Kevin Clair, Lexy deGraffenreid, and Gideon Goodrich. Penn State University Libraries, July 21, 2021, p. 4; also see Trans Metadata Collective guidelines <https://zenodo.org/records/6686841>

own glossaries/terminology, which could be a good starting point. Also, be aware that meanings of the same word may vary regionally.⁷⁵

- Working with a donor (whether during accessioning or after the fact). Discuss how the individual or organisation would like things to be described. This strategy is most relevant if the collections describe themselves/their organisation/estate, etc. In this discussion, you can provide examples of thesauri like the Homosaurus or other records you have created previously to help generate ideas. Another option proposed by Erin Baucom for archival materials is to create a “related topics” or “keyword access” section within finding aids. This would include non-standardized, community-based keywords contributed by respective community members.⁷⁶ This strategy can be easily repurposed for descriptions, where community-derived terms can be reused within descriptive text across the record.
- Large assessment projects of descriptions or exhibit labels. If you are considering revising large sections of your materials’ descriptive contents, it is vital to include community partners’ help to advise these broader changes due to their large impact on users. As community partners can be variously defined, you can invite campus departments and partners as well as local organisations to assist in this effort. Developing an advisory board or working group with a defined set of best practices is a good strategy for organising this work.

⁷⁵Some international resources can include the International Organization for Migration’s Sexual Orientation, Gender Identity, Gender Expression, and Sex Characteristics glossary <https://www.iom.int/sites/g/files/tmzbdl486/files/documents/IOM-SOGIESC-Glossary-of-Terms.pdf> and the Digital Transgender Archive at <https://www.digitaltransgenderarchive.net/learn/terms>.

⁷⁶Baucom, Erin. “An Exploration into Archival Descriptions of LGBTQ Materials.” *The American Archivist*, 2018, 1: 5-83.

5. Author Information & QMDC History

5.1. QMDC History

The QMDC builds upon earlier work done by the [Trans Metadata Collective](#), a similarly-organised group of metadata workers and information professionals with a concerted interest in improving the metadata representation of trans and gender diverse people. The work of the TMDC culminated in [Metadata Best Practices for Trans and Gender Diverse Resources](#),⁷⁷ focusing on the description, cataloguing, and classification of information resources as well as the creation of metadata about trans and gender-diverse people, including authors, communities, and other creators.

Following the publication of the Best Practices, TMDC members B.M. Watson, Adrian Williams, Devon Murphy, Keahi Adolpho, and Rachel Newlin, along with some other TMDC volunteers and reviewers founded and developed the QMDC over the summer of 2022. Early QMDC members launched website and a broad call for participation on social media, GLAMS-relevant listservs, and elsewhere. The response to this call was large and several hundred GLAMS (Galleries, Libraries, Archives, Museums, and Special Collections) workers (and professionals from other fields) expressed interest in participation.

Like the TMDC, the Queer Metadata Collective's primary goal was the development of a set of best practices (this document) for the treatment of queer metadata—the description, cataloguing, and classification of information resources as well as the creation of metadata about queer people, including authors, resources, and other creators. A couple of large-scale meetings were held to discuss action plans, and this larger group broke out into several working groups in order to allow individuals to play to their own expertise. The initial working groups were called Description, Classification, Subject Headings, Name Authorities and Ethical Recommendations / Document Structure.

The TMDC's preexisting Slack workspace was utilized and the working groups began meetings to develop individual documents. These groups and their documents took a variety of forms, including lists, bibliographies, formal reports and others. Over the course of this two-year long process and on an as-needed basis a representative from

⁷⁷ The Trans Metadata Collective et al., "Metadata Best Practices for Trans and Gender Diverse Resources" (Zenodo, June 22, 2022), <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6686841>.

each working group met in a Coordinating Committee, and individuals participated as they were able to—several people were involved in the initial work, and others were not involved until the later stages. As working groups "finished" their self-assigned work or goals the documents were "rolled up" into a shared document that B.M. Watson of the Ethical Recommendations / Document Structure Working Group edited together. The Broad Recommendations section was derived from shared recommendations in each group's documents, as well as ~50 interviews of queer metadata workers by Watson.

In June 2024 the QMDC undertook an internal review where all current and previous authorial or contributing members of the TMDC and QMDC were offered the opportunity for final revisions over the course of one week and nearly 60 individuals did so. Following this period, a two week peer review process was opened to all ~800 members of the QMDC more broadly and 400 of these participated by emailed comments (~150 individuals), suggestions on the Google document (~70 individuals), or reading (the remainder).

The individuals listed in the "Authors" section have elected to appear in it in alphabetic order. The ordering of those in the "Reviewers" section are listed unordered. There are several individuals who did not wish to be listed in both sections due to concerns of outing or personal danger. We would like to extend our thanks for their participation and wisdom.

5.2. Author Information

5.2.1. Classification Working Group

- Chloe Misorski - Cataloging Librarian, Cleveland Museum of Art. White, queer, cisgender woman residing in what is now called Ohio and is the ancestral land of many Indigenous people including Haudenosaunee, Anishinaabeg, and others.
- Dominique Dixon - Metadata Librarian, Princeton University.
- Tiffany Day - Metadata & Catalog Librarian/Asst. Professor, University of Memphis.
- Sasha Frizzell - Catalog/Metadata Management Librarian at Binghamton University, a white, queer, chronically ill person living on the ancestral lands of the Onondaga.
- B. L. Hendrickson, MLS - Cataloging Librarian and Assistant Professor, Pittsburg State University (KS).
- Emily Croft - Systems and Technology Librarian, University of Redlands. (ORCID:[0009-0008-2349-5022](https://orcid.org/0009-0008-2349-5022)).

5.2.2. Subject Headings Working Group

- Adrian Williams - Cataloging & Metadata Librarian at the University of Kentucky. Black, queer, non-binary person residing on unceded Shawnee and Eastern Band Cherokee land. Editorial board member of the Homosaurus.
- Rachel Newlin - Cataloging Librarian at the Schaumburg Township District Library. White queer person residing on the unceded and ancestral lands of the people of the Council of Three Fires: the Ojibwe, Odawa, and Bodéwadmiakiwe.
- Em Ricciardi - Cataloger and LGBTQ+ Subject Specialist at the Library Company of Philadelphia.
- Mara Caelin - Cataloging/Metadata Librarian at Yale University's Beinecke Rare Book and Manuscript Library.
- Allison Bailund - Monographs Cataloging Coordinator at San Diego State University. Chair of the CSU Inclusive Description Task Force residing on unceded Kumeyaay land.
- Abby Springman - Special collections cataloger & Library Assistant at the University of Minnesota Twin Cities.
- Abby Dover - Linked Data Librarian at Northwestern University.
- Abbey Thompson - cis, white, queer, disabled, fat, and neurodivergent woman; Assistant Library Director, head of Access Services & Spaces at Mount St. Mary's University-Los Angeles (former special collections & music cataloger at multiple institutions).
- Jennifer Bradshaw - Cataloging/metadata librarian at the University of Iowa.

5.2.3. Names, Naming & Authorities Working Group

- Ellis Butler - transmasculine cataloger and metadata librarian in New England.
- Bianca Bárcenas - Latina/x/o & white, queer Metadata Associate at The Barack Obama Foundation living on the land of the people of the Council of Three Fires: the Ojibwe, Odawa, and Bodéwadmiakiwe.
- Garth Tardy - cis white gay; Special Collections Catalog Librarian at the University of Missouri-Kansas City.
- Mary Cornell - Queer, white, and genderqueer person living on the ancestral lands of Peoria, Kaskaskia, Piankashaw, Wea, Miami, Mascoutin, Odawa, Sauk, Mesquaki, Kickapoo, Potawatomi, Ojibwe, and Chickasaw Nations ; Cataloger at Cataloging Maintenance Center at Illinois Heartland Library System.

5.2.3.1 Additional Wikidata Contributors

- Crystal Yragui (cec23@uw.edu) – white, cisgendered metadata librarian at the University of Washington Libraries.
- Arielle Rodriguez (ariellerodriguez@pugetsound.edu) - Latinx, cisgender humanities & interdisciplinary studies librarian at University of Puget Sound.

5.2.4. Description Working Group

- Devon Murphy - artist & metadata analyst at the University of Texas at Austin, a white/nonbinary/chronically ill settler based in Shawnee land (Kentucky.) My knowledge and understandings come from this positionality as well as from my mentors in Texas and at the University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill. My contributions to this project were not completed during work hours as a University of Texas at Austin employee.
- Keahi Adolpho - Processing Archivist at Virginia Commonwealth University Libraries. Mixed Kanaka Maoli (Native Hawaiian) and white, queer, and trans. Currently living on Powhatan lands. Editorial board member of the Homosaurus.
- Emma Beck - white, queer, metadata librarian.
- Alison Day - PhD student in Information Studies at Victoria University of Wellington, Te Herenga Waka, as well as a Research Assistant and Tutor. They live in Te Whanganui a Tara (Wellington) in Aotearoa New Zealand.
- Andréa Tarnawsky - poet, educator, and Digital and Outreach Archivist at Simon Fraser University Library Special Collections and Rare Books. They are a white, non-binary, queer, settler originally from amiskwaciywâskahikan (Edmonton, AB), now living and creating on unceded Sḵwx̱wú7mesh Úxwumixw, x^wməθkwəy̓əm, and sə́lilwətał territories (Vancouver, BC). (ORCID:[0009-0004-0692-0462](https://orcid.org/0009-0004-0692-0462))
- Gideon Goodrich - Processing Archivist, specializing in inclusive description, at the University of Michigan, Bentley Historical Society. White, queer, and disabled, currently living on Odawa and Wyandot lands (Ann Arbor, MI). (ORCID:[0000-0003-4402-1818](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4402-1818))
- Katy Rawdon - Coordinator of Technical Services for the Special Collections Research Center at Temple University. A romance writer and poet, and a white, queer person originally from Massachusetts land and a longtime settler on Lenape land.
- Em Ricciardi - Cataloger and LGBTQ+ Subject Specialist at the Library Company of Philadelphia.

Additional Contributors to QMDC Descriptions WG:

Taylor Diken, Nix Mendy, Stephanie Luke, Anna Marie Schuldt, Sydney Jordan, Jordi Padilla-Delgado

5.2.5. Document Structure & Ethical Recommendations

Working Group

- B.M. Watson (@brimwats) - Doctoral Candidate at the University of British Columbia iSchool. White, queer, non-binary, crip/disabled settler originally from N'dakinna and currently living in Słkwxwú7mesh, Səl ʔlwətaʔ, and xʷməθkʷəy əm. Editorial board member of the Homosaurus, Archivist and Historian for the Haslam Polyamory Collection. Administration and email for QMDC and contributor to Names and Description WGs.

Additional Contributors to Document Structure & Ethical Recommendations WG:

- Elizabeth Uchimura, MSI, MM – Music Digital Services and Special Collections Librarian at the Warren D. Allen Music Library at Florida State University, Tallahassee, Florida. Mixed race, bisexual, agender, originally from Tampa, Florida. Research interests include critical cataloging and vernacular singing practices in the United States.
- R. Carpenter - Digital Scholarship Librarian at Binghamton University. White, non-binary.
- Tim Keller - Head of Discovery and Metadata at Oberlin College.

5.3. QMDC Reviewers

- St John Karp MSLIS; Assistant Librarian, Horological Society of New York.
- Brandis Malone MLS, MA. Special Collections Cataloging Librarian, University of Tulsa McFarlin Library.
- Jeremy Berg MLIS. Cataloging Librarian, University of North Texas.
- Holly Wheeler MLIS. Cataloging & Metadata Specialist, Mt. Hood Community College.
- Elizabeth Uchimura MSI, MM. Music Digital Services and Special Collections Librarian, Warren D. Allen Music Library, Florida State University.
- D.F. Zulida MLIS Senior Librarian, Business & Career Center, Brooklyn Public Library, Brooklyn, NY.
- Caitlin Goodman; Archivist, Swarthmore College, Swarthmore PA.
- Amy Mihelich MLIS. Systems & Discovery Librarian, Washington County Cooperative Library Services, Hillsboro, OR.
- **Tess Amram** MSLIS, Special Materials and Continuing Resources Cataloging Librarian.
- **Michelle Cronquist** MLIS, Special Collections Cataloger at Wilson Library, University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill.

5.4. Glossary of Terms

- AACR2 (Anglo-American Cataloguing Rules 2nd edition): the cataloguing standard by which cataloguers provided bibliographic description for library catalogues and other bibliographic tools until the formal introduction and widespread adoption of RDA in 2013. AACR2 is still in use by some libraries.
- Cataloguing: Within the context of libraries and archives, the creation and revision of bibliographic metadata of library materials such as monographs, video recordings, archival collections, etc., within a bibliographic tool in order to connect library users with that material.
- Controlled vocabulary: An organised index of standardised terms. Controlled vocabularies are often used in GLAMS metadata. Library of Congress Subject Headings (LCSH) is an example of controlled vocabulary.
- Creator: A person or group responsible for the content in a resource, e.g. author, choreographer.
- DACS: Describing Archives: A Content Standard: DACS provides rules for description of archival materials that can be output in any format (including MARC and EAD). It includes a section for archival records and one for archival authorities. The standard is maintained by the Society of American Archivists Standards Committee's Technical Subcommittee for Describing Archives: A Content Standard.
- DDC (Dewey Decimal Classification): a library classification system first published in the United States by Melvil Dewey in 1876, currently owned and maintained by OCLC. It organizes library materials by discipline or field of study using 10 class numbers (100-900), and is used in more than 140 countries worldwide.
- Finding aid: a document containing detailed information about a specific collection of papers or records within an archives, including a description of the scope and content of the materials, their arrangement, and other metadata to help researchers locate material relevant to their work.
- GLAMS sector: An acronym for the types of cultural institutions that provide access to information. The acronym stands for "galleries, libraries, archives, museums, and special collections."
- Library of Congress (LC): the main research arm of the U.S. Congress and the

home of the U.S. Copyright Office, it is also the library which maintains and revises LCC, LCSH, and the other LC vocabularies. It is de facto (but not officially) the national library of the United States.

- Library of Congress Classification (LCC): the classification system developed in the late nineteenth century to organise and arrange the Library of Congress' physical collections; LCC is ubiquitous to most academic libraries in the United States, but is also used widely across the world.
- Library of Congress Subject Headings (LCSH): The subject indexing language developed by the Library of Congress to organise and describe their physical collections; now used widely by GLAMS institutions across the world to describe and organise their materials.
- Linked Data: structured data which is interlinked with other data so it can be read and queried by computers.
- Metadata: Broadly, data about data. In the GLAMS context, data that describes the primary resources that the institution collects and/or provides virtual access to. Metadata is found in bibliographic records, finding aids, etc. It may be created with reference to standards and controlled vocabularies or in a more locally defined manner. Metadata is used to help users find what they're looking for and for institutions to keep track of what they have.
- Metadata worker / Knowledge worker: A person who creates and maintains descriptive, administrative, and/or structural metadata within the GLAMS sector. Individuals may be employed professionals with degrees, technicians, or they may be volunteers at a community institution.
- Name Authority Cooperative Program (NACO): the cooperative project established by the Library of Congress where participating institutions contribute authority records for agents, places, works, and expressions to the LC/NACO Authority File.
- MORGAI (pronounced "more-gay"; IPA: /mɔːr'geɪ/): An acronym for Marginalized Orientations, Relationships, Gender identities, Asexualities/Aromanticisms, and/or those who are Intersex. MORGAI is inclusive of LGBTQIA2S+ and other "alphabet soup" type acronyms like QUILTBAG.
- WEB3CH2A2MS (pronounced 'web-cham'; IPA: /wɛb'ʃæm/): an acronym originating from cataloguing literature meaning: White, ethnically European, Bourgeois, Christian, Cisgender, Citizen, Heterosexual, Able-bodied, Allosexual, Monogamous, Men Settlers, as a way of naming the universal, default, and

assumed (yet unspoken) centre of cataloguing, classification, and description systems and practices.

- Program for Cooperative Cataloging (PCC): an international cooperative effort aimed at expanding access to library collections by providing useful, timely, and cost-effective cataloguing that meets mutually-accepted standards of libraries around the world. The PCC has four main programs that coordinate authority and bibliographic record creation. It also includes committees and task groups that consider a broad spectrum of cataloguing issues.
- Resource Description and Access (RDA): the cataloguing standard currently used in most libraries for the bibliographic description. In comparison to AACR2, RDA is more flexible and more suitable for use in today's digital landscape.
- Resource: anything for which metadata is assigned in a GLAMS context. Examples include: books, audiovisual materials, archival collections, artifacts, etc.
- Subject headings: A term or phrase used to find and organise resources on a particular topic or range of topics.
- Trans and gender diverse resources: Fiction or non-fiction about trans and gender diverse people, resources about topics related to trans and gender diverse experience or gender identity, resources about gender that are inclusive of trans and gender diverse identities and experiences.
- Universal Decimal Classification (UDC): a bibliographic and library classification system derived from the Dewey Decimal Classification, designed to cover all fields of knowledge using a system of auxiliary signs and symbols to indicate various special aspects of a subject and relationships between subjects.

6. Appendices & Resources

6.1. Sources Consulted & Further Reading

Adler, Melissa A. *Cruising the Library: Perversities in the Organization of Knowledge* (New York: Fordham University Press, 2017).

Adler, Melissa. "The Case for Taxonomic Reparations." *Knowledge Organization* 43, no. 8 (2016): 630–40. <https://doi.org/10.5771/0943-7444-2016-8-630>.

Adolpho, K. "Who Asked You? Consent, Self-Determination, and the Report of the PCC Ad Hoc Task Group on Gender in Name Authority Records." In *Ethical Questions in Name Authority Control*, edited by Jane Sandberg, 111–131. Library Juice Press, 2019.

Antracoli, Alexis A., Annalise Berdini, Kelly Bolding, Faith Charlton, Amanda Ferrara, Valencia Johnson, and Katy Rawdon. "Archives for Black Lives in Philadelphia: Anti-Racist Description Resources." October 2020. https://archivesforblacklives.files.wordpress.com/2020/11/ardr_202010.pdf.

Baucom, Erin. "An Exploration into Archival Descriptions of LGBTQ Materials." *The American Archivist* 81, no. 1 (2018): 65–83. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/48618001>.

Bauer, Heike *English Literary Sexology: Translations of Inversion, 1860–1930* (Houndmills, Basingstoke, Hampshire New York, NY: Palgrave Macmillan, 2009).

Beghtol, Clare. "A Proposed Ethical Warrant for Global Knowledge Representation and Organization Systems." *Journal of Documentation* 58, no. 5 (October 1, 2002): 507–32. <https://doi.org/10.1108/00220410210441>.

Billey, Amber, and Emily Drabinski. "Questioning Authority: Changing Library Cataloging Standards to Be More Inclusive to a Gender Identity Spectrum." *TSQ: Transgender Studies Quarterly* 6, no. 1 (February 1, 2019): 117–23. <https://doi.org/10.1215/23289252-7253538>.

Billey, Amber, Emily Drabinski, and K. R. Roberto. "What's Gender Got to Do with It? A Critique of RDA 9.7." *Cataloging & Classification Quarterly* 52, no. 4 (2014): 412–21. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01639374.2014.882465>.

Bland, Lucy and Laura L. Doan, eds., *Sexology in Culture: Labelling Bodies and Desires* (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 1998).

Bullard, Julia, Amber Dierking, and Avi Grundner. "Centring LGBT2QIA Subjects in

Knowledge Organization Systems.” Scholarly Papers and Articles, January 1, 2020. <https://doi.org/10.5771/0943-7444-2020-5-393>.

Caswell, Michelle. “Dusting for Fingerprints: Introducing Feminist Standpoint Appraisal,” in “Radical Empathy in Archival Practice,” eds. Elvia Arroyo-Ramirez, Jasmine Jones, Shannon O’Neill, and Holly Smith. Special issue, *Journal of Critical Library and Information Studies* 3, no. 2 (2021). DOI: 10.24242/jclis.v3i2.113.

Charlton, James I. *Nothing about Us without Us: Disability Oppression and Empowerment*. Berkeley, CA: University of California Press, 2004.

Christensen, Ben. “Minoritization vs. Universalization: Lesbianism and Male Homosexuality in LCSH and LCC.” *Knowledge Organization* 35, no. 4 (December 14, 2008): 229–38. <https://doi.org/10.5771/0943-7444-2008-4-229>.

Cifor, Marika, and K.J. Rawson. “Mediating Queer and Trans Pasts: The Homosaurus as Queer Information Activism.” *Information, Communication & Society* 26, no. 11 (August 18, 2023): 2168–85. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1369118X.2022.2072753>.

Colbert, J. L. and Matt Johnson. “GLBT Controlled Vocabularies and Classification Schemes” Accessed February 12, 2024. <http://hdl.handle.net/11213/16973>.

Dobreski, Brian, Karen Snow, and Heather Moulaison-Sandy. “On Overlap and Otherness: A Comparison of Three Vocabularies’ Approaches to LGBTQ+ Identity.” *Cataloging & Classification Quarterly* 60, no. 6–7 (October 3, 2022): 490–513. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01639374.2022.2090040>.

Donaghy, Paige “Before Onanism: Women’s Masturbation in Seventeenth-Century England,” *Journal of the History of Sexuality* 29, no. 2 (May 2020): 187–221, <https://doi.org/10.7560/jhs29203>.

Drucker, Donna J. *The Classification of Sex: Alfred Kinsey and the Organization of Knowledge* (Pittsburgh, Pa: University of Pittsburgh Press, 2014).

Drabinski, Emily. “Queering the Catalog: Queer Theory and the Politics of Correction.” *The Library Quarterly* 83, no. 2 (April 2013): 94–111. <https://doi.org/10.1086/669547>.

Drucker, Donna J. “How Subjects Matter: The Kinsey Institute’s Sexual Nomenclature: A Thesaurus (1976).” *Information & Culture: A Journal of History* 52, no. 2 (2017): 207–28.

Ewalt, Jillian. “Toward Inclusive Description: Reparations through Community-Driven

- Metadata.” New England Archivists Newsletter 46, no. 2 (April 1, 2019).
https://ecommons.udayton.edu/imri_faculty_publications/41.
- Ewing, Kai. “Beyond Dewey: Creating an LGBTQ+ Classification System at the LGBTQ Center of Durham.” In *LGBTQ+ Librarianship in the 21st Century: Emerging Directions of Advocacy and Community Engagement in Diverse Information Environments*, edited by Bharat Mehra, 45:225–42. *Advances in Librarianship*. Emerald Publishing Limited, 2019. <https://doi.org/10.1108/S0065-283020190000045017>.
- Flentje, Annesa, Nicholas C. Heck, James Michael Brennan, and Ian H. Meyer. “The Relationship between Minority Stress and Biological Outcomes: A Systematic Review.” *Journal of Behavioral Medicine* 43, no. 5 (October 2020): 673–94. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10865-019-00120-6>.
- Frick, Rachel L., and Merrilee Proffitt. “Reimagine Descriptive Workflows: A Community-Informed Agenda for Reparative and Inclusive Descriptive Practice,” April 2022. <https://doi.org/10.25333/wd4b-bs51>.
- Giami, Alain and Sharman Levinson, eds., *Histories of Sexology: Between Science and Politics, Global Queer Politics* (Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2021), <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-65813-7>.
- GLBT Historical Society. “GLBT Historical Society Style Guide for Processing” (internal document). December 7, 2021.
- “Gerber/Hart Library and Archives – Midwest LGBTQ+ History & Culture.” Accessed February 12, 2024. <https://www.gerberhart.org/>.
- Hardesty, Juliet L., and Allison Nolan. “Mitigating Bias in Metadata: A Use Case Using Homosaurus Linked Data.” *Information Technology and Libraries* 40, no. 3 (September 1, 2021): NA-NA. <http://dx.doi.org/10.6017/ital.v40i3.13053>.
- Heath, Deana *Purifying Empire: Obscenity and the Politics of Moral Regulation in Britain, India and Australia* (New York: Cambridge University Press, 2010).
- Hitchcock, Tim “Redefining Sex in Eighteenth-Century England,” *History Workshop Journal*, 20.
- Howard, Sara A., and Steven A. Knowlton. “Browsing through Bias: The Library of Congress Classification and Subject Headings for African American Studies and LGBTQIA Studies.” *Library Trends* 67, no. 1 (2018): 74–88. <https://doi.org/10.1353/lib.2018.0026>.

Howarth, Lynne C., and Emma Knight. "To Every Artifact Its Voice: Creating Surrogates for Hand-Crafted Indigenous Objects." *Cataloging & Classification Quarterly* 53, no. 5-6 (July 4, 2015): 580-95.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/01639374.2015.1008719>.

Hunt, Alan "The Great Masturbation Panic and the Discourses of Moral Regulation in Nineteenth- and Early Twentieth-Century Britain," *Journal of the History of Sexuality* 8, no. 4 (1998): 575-615.

Indian Arts Research Center. 2019. Guidelines for Collaboration (website). Facilitated by Landis Smith, Cynthia Chavez Lamar, and Brian Vallo. Santa Fe, NM: School for Advanced Research. <https://guidelinesforcollaboration.info/>.

Johnson, Matt. "Transgender Subject Access: History and Current Practice." *Cataloging & Classification Quarterly* 48, no. 8 (September 27, 2010): 661-83.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/01639370903534398>.

Kahan, Benjamin *The Book of Minor Perverts: Sexology, Etiology, and the Emergences of Sexuality* (University of Chicago Press, 2019),

<https://doi.org/10.7208/chicago/9780226608006.001.0001>;

Krafft-Ebing, Richard von and Francis Joseph Rehman, *Psychopathia Sexualis, with Especial Reference to the Antipathic Sexual Instinct, a Medico-Forensic Study*; (New York: Rebman, 1886).

LaFleur, Greta *The Natural History of Sexuality in Early America* (Baltimore: Johns Hopkins University Press, 2018)

Leck, Ralph M. *Vita Sexualis : Karl Ulrichs and the Origins of Sexual Science* (Champaign, Illinois, United States: University of Illinois Press, 2016).

Lellman, Charlotte. "Guidelines for Inclusive and Conscientious Description." Center for the History of Medicine: Policies and Procedures Manual, May 2020.

<https://wiki.harvard.edu/confluence/display/hmschommanual/Guidelines+for+Inclusive+and+Conscientious+Description>.

Mason, Diane Elizabeth *The Secret Vice: Masturbation in Victorian Fiction and Medical Culture* (Manchester, UK ; New York : New York: Manchester University Press ; Distributed exclusively in USA by Palgrave Macmillan, 2008).

McAuliffe, Bethany. "Queer Identities, Queer Content and Library Classification: Is 'Queering the Catalogue' the Answer?" *Journal of the Australian Library and Information Association* 70, no. 2 (April 3, 2021): 213-19.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/24750158.2021.1915618>.

Meyer, Ilan H. "Prejudice, Social Stress, and Mental Health in Lesbian, Gay, and Bisexual Populations: Conceptual Issues and Research Evidence." *Psychological Bulletin* 129, no. 5 (September 2003): 674–97. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-2909.129.5.674>.

Meyer, Ilan H., John E. Pachankis, and Daniel N. Klein. "Do Genes Explain Sexual Minority Mental Health Disparities?" *Archives of Sexual Behavior* 50, no. 3 (April 2021): 731–37. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10508-020-01909-2>.

Mitchell, Benjamin. "Collections Services Manual: Inclusive Description Style Guide." Edited by Racine Amos, Kevin Clair, Lexy deGraffenreid, and Gideon Goodrich. Penn State University Libraries, July 21, 2021. <https://docs.google.com/document/d/16g4XvDpBDL8ncf42balprCmEF2QJ0yti>.

Nowak, Kristine, and Amy Mitchell. "Classifying Identity: Organizing an LGBT Library." *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-Journal)*, January 1, 2016. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/1452>.

Olson, Hope A. "Patriarchal Structures of Subject Access and Subversive Techniques for Change." *The Canadian Journal of Information and Library Science* 26, no. 2–3 (2001): 4.

Polebaum-Freeman, H. "Violent Cis-tems: Identifying Transphobia in Library of Congress Name Authority Records." In *Ethical Questions in Name Authority Control*, edited by Jane Sandberg, 155–179. Library Juice Press, 2019.

Robinson, Paul A. *The Modernization of Sex: Havelock Ellis, Alfred Kinsey, William Masters, and Virginia Johnson* (New York: Harper & Row, 1976).

Rossi, Stefano "Female Onanism: Condemned Pleasures, Medical Probes, and Late-Victorian Pornography," *Victoriographies* 11, no. 2 (July 2021): 148–64, <https://doi.org/10.3366/vic.2021.0420>.

Russell, Stephen T., and Jessica N. Fish. "Mental Health in Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, and Transgender (LGBT) Youth." *Annual Review of Clinical Psychology* 12, no. 1 (March 28, 2016): 465–87. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-clinpsy-021815-093153>;

Seeman, Dean. "Naming Names: The Ethics of Identification in Digital Library Metadata." *Knowledge Organization* 39, no. 5 (September 2012): 325–31. <https://doi.org/10.5771/0943-7444-2012-5-325>.

Sedgwick, Eve Kosofsky. *Epistemology of the Closet*. Berkeley: University of California

Press, 1990.

Shiraishi, N. "Accuracy of Identity Information and Name Authority Records." In *Ethical Questions in Name Authority Control*, edited by Jane Sandberg, 181-194. Library Juice Press, 2019.

Shopland, Norena A *Practical Guide to Searching LGBTQIA Historical Records*, 1st ed. (Routledge, 2021), <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003006787>.

Snow, Karen, and Anthony W. Dunbar. "Advancing the Relationship between Critical Cataloging and Critical Race Theory." *Cataloging & Classification Quarterly* 60, no. 6-7 (June 24, 2022): 646-74.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/01639374.2022.2089936>.

Unique Material in the SILS Standing Group and Archives West Standing Group.
"Guidelines for Addressing Bias in Archival Description and Catalog Records."
Orbis Cascade Alliance, Unique and Local Content Program, 2021.
<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1JspfIXDqhK6PnDj2ew-SAkVDzk3Q3iSn/view?pli=1>.

Vaughan, Crystal. "The Language of Cataloguing: Deconstructing and Decolonizing Systems of Organization in Libraries." *Dalhousie Journal of Interdisciplinary Management* 14 (April 11, 2018). <https://doi.org/10.5931/djim.v14i0.7853>.

Wagner, T. L. "Finding 'Miss Betty' Joe Carstairs: The Ethics of Unpacking Misnaming in Cataloging and Biographical Practices." In *Ethical Questions in Name Authority Control*, edited by Jane Sandberg. Library Juice Press, 2019.

Wagner, Travis. "Body-Oriented Cataloging as a Method of Inclusive Gender Representation." *Cataloging & Classification Quarterly* 60, no. 6-7 (October 3, 2022): 620-45. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01639374.2022.2089795>.

Wagner, Travis L. "'She Started Wearing Men's Clothes and Acting More Masculine': Queering Historical Knowledge, Gendered Identity Making, and Trans Potentialities in Visual Information." *The International Journal of Information, Diversity, & Inclusion* 5, no. 4 (2021): 21-42.
<https://www.jstor.org/stable/48641978>.

Watson, B. M. "Advancing Equitable Cataloging." In *Proceedings from North American Symposium on Knowledge Organization*, Vol. 8. (November 12, 2021).

Watson, B. M. "Critiquing the Machine: The Critical Cataloging Database." *TCB: Technical Services in Religion & Theology* 31, no. 1 (January 24, 2023): 6.

Watson, B.M. "'There Was Sex but No Sexuality*': Critical Cataloging and the Classification of Asexuality in LCSH." *Cataloging & Classification Quarterly* 58,

no. 6 (August 6, 2020): 547–65.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/01639374.2020.1796876>.

Watson, B. M. “A Finding Aid to the Pornographic Imaginary: Implications of Amateur Classifications on/by Reddit’s NSFW411,” *Porn Studies*, January 13, 2021, 1–23, <https://doi.org/10.1080/23268743.2020.1830590>.

Weeks, Jeffrey *Sex, Politics and Society: The Regulations of Sexuality since 1800*, 2015.

Wiley, Angela *Undoing Monogamy: The Politics of Science and the Possibilities of Biology* (Durham: Duke University Press, 2016).

Wilson Special Collections Library. “A Guide to Conscious Editing at Wilson Special Collections Library.” The University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill University Libraries, 2022. <https://library.unc.edu/project/conscious-editing-initiative/#:~:text=Guide%20to%20Conscious%20Editing&text=The%20guide%20contains%20articles%20on,about%20racist%20and%20harmful%20content>

6.1.2. Recommended Name Authority Resources & Examples

- Example of a personal affiliation in an authority record from MIT Libraries: <https://archivesspace.mit.edu/agents/people/975>
- For templates on contacting creators: [Library of Congress Authority Control FAQs for Catalogers Contacting Creators/Contributors](#)
- For information on how authority control works for authors and creators: [Authority Control FAQs for Authors and Creators](#)
- PCC Ad Hoc Task Group on Recording Gender in Personal Name Authority Records, “Revised Report on Recording Gender in Personal Name Authority Records” (2022) <https://www.loc.gov/aba/pcc/documents/gender-in-NARs-revised-report.pdf>.
- The Trans Metadata Collective, Burns, J., Cronquist, M., Huang, J., Murphy, D., Rawson, K. J., Schaefer, B., Simons, J., Watson, B. M., & Williams, A. (2022). *Metadata Best Practices for Trans and Gender Diverse Resources* (1.4). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6773159>
- Program for Cooperative Cataloging, “NACO Participants’ Manual” (2020) <https://www.loc.gov/aba/pcc/naco/documents/NACOParticipantsManual.pdf>

6.2. Alternative Systems

6.2.1. Alternative Classification Systems

For an annotated bibliography of GLBT classification systems, please see “[GLBT Controlled Vocabularies and Classification Schemes](#),” released in 2007 and updated in 2017 by the Rainbow Round Table of the American Library Association.

Current Systems:

The Collective welcomes the submission of other currently-developed systems, but the ones that we are most aware of are:

- The Lavender Library, Archives, and Cultural Exchange (LLACE) system.
 - More info: Diana Wakimoto, Debra Hansen, and Christine Bruce, “The Case of LLACE: Challenges, Triumphs, and Lessons of a Community Archives,” *The American Archivist* 76, no. 2 (September 2013): 438–57, <https://doi.org/10.17723/aarc.76.2.kqv813v23vl24741>.
- The Gay and Lesbian Services Organization (GLSO) System (now part of the Lexington Pride Center Library)
 - More info: Nowak, Kristine, and Amy Mitchell. “Classifying Identity: Organizing an LGBT Library.” *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-Journal)*, January 1, 2016. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/1452>.
- [The Out On the Shelves Classification System](#) of the OOTS Library in Vancouver, British Columbia, Canada, originally published in 2018 and updated in 2024. These are included below.

2018 System:

ERO	Erotica	BIO	Biography
FIC	Fiction - English	HIS	History
FIC-FR	Fiction - French	HIS-Geo	Geographic History
FIC-DE	Fiction – German	HIS-CPA	Civil Rights, Politics, and Activism
FIC-ES	Fiction - Spanish	HIS-Law	Legal History
FIC-JA	Fiction - Japanese		
FIC-ZH	Fiction - Chinese		
LIT	Literature	LIV	LGBTQ2IA+ Lives
LIT-Poe	Poetry	LIV-H	Health
LIT-Dra	Drama	LIV-F	Family
LIT-Ess	Critical Essays	LIV-RRS	Relationships - Romantic and Sexual
ART	Arts and Entertainment	LIV-RSel	Relationships - with Oneself
ART-Vis	Visual Arts	LIV-RSpi	Relationships - Spiritual
ART-Fil	Film and Television	YOU	Youth Fiction
ART-Per	Performance Art	YOU-NF	Youth Non-Fiction
ID	Identity	CHILD	Children’s
ID-L	Lesbian	GRA	Graphica
ID-G	Gay men	DVD	DVD’s
ID-B	Bi and Pansexual		
ID-T	Trans and Genderqueer		
ID-Q	Queer		
ID-2	Two-Spirit		
ID-I	Intersex		
ID-A	Asexual and Aromantic		

More info: Bullard, Julia, Amber Dierking, and Avi Grundner. “Centring LGBT2QIA Subjects in Knowledge Organization Systems.” Scholarly Papers and Articles, January 1, 2020. https://scholarworks.gvsu.edu/library_sp/68.

2024 Update by Kira Razzo:

Out On The Shelves Library Classification System

6.2.2. Alternative Subject Heading Systems

- The Homosaurus International LGBTQ+ linked data vocabulary (<http://homosaurus.org>)
 - More information on [Homosaurus' About Page](#)
 - Published information:
 - B.M. Watson, Chloe Noland, and Amber Billey, “The Homosaurus,” *Catalogue and Index*, no. 202 (March 2021): 44–47.
 - Rachel Fischer, “Using the Homosaurus in a Public Library Consortium: A Case Study,” *Library Resources & Technical Services* 67, no. 1 (2023), <https://doi.org/10.5860/lrts.67n1.4>.
- GSSO - the Gender, Sex, and Sexual Orientation ontology
 - Lookups:
 - <https://gssoresearch.cchmc.org/#!/home>
 - <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ols4/ontologies/gssoresearch>
 - More info: Clair Kronk, Giao Q. Tran, and Danny T. Y. Wu, “Creating a Queer Ontology: The Gender, Sex, and Sexual Orientation (GSSO) Ontology,” *MEDINFO 2019: Health and Wellbeing e-Networks for All*, 2019, 208–12, <https://doi.org/10.3233/SHTI190213>.

6.3. Examples, Models & Tutorials

6.3.1. Harmful Metadata Statement Examples

Violet Fox’s Cataloging Lab includes a non-exhaustive [list of statements on bias in library and archives description](#), which includes a wide range of institutions including archives, academic libraries, museums, and public libraries. Here are some examples from QMDC contributors’ institutions:

This example from the [NC Digital Heritage Center](#) contains a harmful materials statement at the item level, with specifics on the kind of sensitive imagery contained within.

Another example, from the [Portal to Texas History](#), employs a harmful materials statement with instructions on how to report graphic content. Each collection record includes a prompt for feedback.

More harmful content statements from QMDC Members:

- <https://library.umkc.edu/policies/harmful-content>
- <https://www.schaumburglibrary.org/about/about-us#harmful>
- <https://library.princeton.edu/statement-harmful-content>

6.3.2. Updating and Correction of Wikidata Items

6.3.2.1. Updating Existing Wikidata Items

To update existing items for people found in [Wikidata](#) use the following steps.

- In the search menu at the top right of the page search for the name you want to edit. Search the person’s name as it would appear in a sentence e.g. “Billy Porter” to find the [actor’s entry](#) (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Alt Text: Screenshot of a web browser showing the homepage of Wikidata (https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:Main_Page). The text in the search bar on the top right of the page shows a search for “Billy Porter” in progress. In the search menu at the top right of the page search for the name you want to edit. Search First name Last Name eg. “Billy Porter” to find the actor’s entry

- To make changes to a person’s name, alternative names, or description, click the “Edit” link at the upper right of the Wikidata item entry (Figure 3)

Figure 3 Alt Text: Image shows the Wikidata item for Billy Porter. Circed in yellow, is the edit link, which allows you to make changes to a person’s name, alternative names, or description. The “Edit” link is located at the upper right of the Wikidata item entry

- The “Label” box contains the main or preferred form of the person’s name in addition to other forms (“Also known as”) and a basic description of the person, and you can place the cursor in the field to make desired changes. You can also change the description and “Also known as” fields in the same way to add or alter the description or alternative forms of the person’s name
- To edit more than the first couple of languages, you can click the “All entered languages” button at the bottom of the Label box
- When you are finished making your changes, click the “publish” button to save your work. Your changes will appear in the Wikidata item immediately (Figure 4)

Figure 4: Alt Text: After you have edited the Wikidata item's label, description, and/or "Also known as" sections, you can click publish, on the upper right, to publish your changes.

- Outside of the box containing the labels and descriptions for the item in each language, the Wikidata item consists of a series of statements and identifiers created by adding Wikidata properties via the “add statement” button at the bottom right of each item (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Alt Text: To add a statement to a Wikidata item page, click the "add statement" button at the bottom right of each item.

- Statements about a person may include personal demographic information or information that may violate privacy,⁷⁸ such as sex or gender (P21), personal pronoun (P6553), sexual orientation (P91), birth name (P1477) (which may contain a person’s former name), and other characteristics. Statements may be edited by clicking the “Edit” link with a pencil icon in the top right corner of each statement box

⁷⁸ https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:Living_people#Statements_that_may_violate_privacy

- New values may be added to existing statements by clicking “+Add value.”
- You may insert references justifying your choice of entry by clicking “+Add reference.” While all statements should generally include references, some properties will display a (!) icon to indicate a “citation-needed constraint” that a reference needs to be added.
- Values for statements may be qualified by clicking the “Edit” button in the statement box, then clicking “+add qualifier” and adding an appropriate property and value. Wikidata will display an error message upon publishing changes if you have chosen a qualifier that is not allowed for a given property.
- More advanced users may also create bots or use batch editing tools to create many statements in Wikidata at one time. Bots creating statements about living people must adhere to a few restrictions outlined in the Wikidata Policy for Living People.⁷⁹

6.3.2.2. Correcting Wikidata Items

The three primary options are:

Option 1: Talk it out.

- When you see a piece of harmful or incorrect information, find where it came from by exploring the item history (Figure 6 and 7).

⁷⁹ https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:Living_people#Bot_interaction_with_items_for_living_people

Figure 6: Alt-Text: To access the item's revision history select the 'view history' tab found on the item's page.

Figure 7: Alt-Text: a screenshot of the revision history for Billy Porter's page. Each revision has its own row on the screen including a time stamp and the name of the user who made the edit, click on the user name to go to their page

- Once you find the edit that caused the problem, find the link to the user's talk page and click on it (Figure 8).
 - There, you can choose to "Edit" or "Add topic". This random example is a good example of how to use Wikidata markdown to converse about an edit (click the "edit" button to check out the markdown, and then cancel

your edit session when you are finished to leave the conversation unchanged). Kindly but firmly describe to the person who made the edit how their edit was harmful and that you are removing/changing it, and then do so.

Figure 8: Alt-Text: on that user's page select either the 'edit' or 'add topic' tab to leave a message or comment for that user that communicates why their edit was harmful and that you are changing it. Comments should be kind, but firm.

1. Replace the false or harmful information with correct information when possible.
 - For example, if someone's sex or gender is not publicly known, you can enter "[undisclosed gender](#)" as the value or click the stack of three rectangles to the left of the empty value box next to the property, select "unknown value", save, and save again when Wikidata asks if you are sure (Figure 9).

Figure 9: Alt-Text: A screenshot of an edit in progress. The location of the three rectangles is circled in yellow.

2. Edit wars are not encouraged, and getting into arguments can suck your soul out of your eyeballs. If someone changes something back or is confrontational, start a conversation in the [Project chat](#) and alert your friends in the above groups. You can also add it to the [Collection of discussions list](#) on the WikiProjectLGBT/gender page.
 - “Most of the participants, after working to change or update a property or focus on policy for how to describe living people, at some point, decided to move on and not attempt to change it. Only a few participants continue in the effort to evolve the WD ontology as humanity evolves.”⁸⁰

Option 1 is the most emotionally taxing and time-consuming approach, but also the most effective.

6.3.2.3. Additional Wikidata Considerations for GLAMS Metadata Workers

References:

A major philosophical difference between the Wiki community and GLAMS metadata is Wikidata’s policy of needing a "source" but individual themselves is not considered a source. If references are used or required, the things which constitute an acceptable

⁸⁰ See [Summary of findings on Knowledge Equity in Linked Open Data, submitted to Wikimedia Deutschland](#)

reference must be verifiable. They must be “trustworthy, up-to-date, and free of bias”⁸¹ and can include:

- books, academic, scientific, and industry-specific publications, news sources, policy and legislation, and media;
- webpages may be used, especially if they are published by government agencies, companies, or organisations.

However, self-published sources should never be used as references for other living people. Self-publications may be used as a reference if a person is writing about themselves, but the reference needs to meet some other verifiability and notability criteria.

According to Wikidata’s [Notability Criteria](#), a Wikidata item needs to fulfil at least one of the two goals of Wikidata:

- Centralise interlanguage links across Wikimedia projects, or
- Serve as a general knowledge base for the world at large

It also needs to meet one of the three criteria:

- Contain at least one valid sitelink to another Wikimedia project,
- Refer to an instance of a clearly identifiable conceptual or material entity that can be described using authoritative and publicly available references,
- Fulfils a structural need such as making statements in other items more useful.

Wikidata and Wikipedia have some policies which also address these issues. English Wikipedia’s [Policy on biographies of living people](#) states:

“Biographies of living persons (“BLPs”) must be written conservatively and with regard for the subject’s privacy. Wikipedia is an encyclopedia, not a tabloid: it is not Wikipedia’s job to be sensationalist, or to be the primary vehicle for the spread of titillating claims about people’s lives; the possibility of harm to living subjects must always be considered when exercising editorial judgment.”

Wikidata’s [Living People Page](#) begins with:

“As we value the dignity of living people, the information that we store about them deserves special consideration. Instead of striving to provide all possible information about living people we strive to provide only information in whose veracity we have a high confidence and which doesn’t violate a person’s reasonable expectations of privacy. Statements that can reasonably be expected to be challenged should be supported by a reliable source. When exercising

⁸¹ https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:Verifiability#Authoritative_sources

editorial judgement we should always consider the possibility of harm to living people.”

The policy is meant to cover any and all harms that might come to living persons from being described in Wikidata, and the issues described above are not specifically addressed. It appears to those who believe that deadnaming violates a person’s reasonable expectations of privacy, and who believe that misgendering in cisnormative ways generates inequitable harms to queer communities, that current widespread practices in Wikidata are in violation of the Living People policy.

However, Wikidata policies are created and enforced using a difficult-to-define version of consensus and encourages the use of the Project chat to hash out differences. This framework represents a significant hurdle for marginalised voices to be heard and respected, because Wikidata has no shortage of bigoted editors or contributors:

“There have been and continue to be many attempts to address the issues with Property 21 [sex and gender]. The minoritized group has strong feelings about it with good reason, but the decision making process around it is made by the majority so the people most affected by decisions, or lack of decision making, are overridden” - Participant⁸²

Because consensus is required for decision making in the WD community, prevailing power structures remain in place. Sometimes when a large majority of participants in a discussion agree to make a change, one person can disagree, and then the decision is never made.⁸³

“The idea of consensus is unclear. Once having disagreement - and not finding complete consensus - there is no referee - it is space for a bully to win.” - Participant⁸⁴

The issue of Property 21 is a prime example of this. For years, there have been, and continue to be, numerous discussions about and proposals to change Property 21 to more accurately describe people in WD. No change has been able to be made. A complicating factor about Property 21 is that it is required for describing an “instance of” a human being. A warning error is thrown if a WD item is being created and this identifier is not added. This furthers the problem by making it required to, in some cases, misidentify an instance of a human being contributed to WD, because the

⁸² See [Summary of findings on Knowledge Equity in Linked Open Data, submitted to Wikimedia Deutschland](#)

⁸³ Ibid.

⁸⁴ Ibid.

person contributing the property does not know the status of the person being described and guesses. The status quo can remain in place with a lack of ability for equitable decision making about properties like Property 21.⁸⁵

[Wikimedia Foundation Governance Wiki](#) is outdated, but points to an up-to-date [Human Rights Policy](#) which expressly includes “LGBTQ+ communities” in its scope but does not address any specific protections against specific harms. The Wikimedia Foundation has a [Resolution on Living People](#) which also does not protect against the specific harms that are being done in Wikidata.

6.3.3. Identification of “romantic friendships,” “inseparable friends or companions,” “bosom friends,” “life friends,” and same-sex relationships

In *A Practical Guide to Searching LGBTQIA Historical Records*, Norena Shopland offers a guide to common indicators to help identify same-sex relationships, which we reproduce here for use of metadata workers.

There are common indicators which can be applied to identify same-sex relationships:

- Same-sex couples wanted to spend more time together than romantic friends did, sometimes to the point of obsession. Queen Anne (1665–1714), before she came to the throne, could hardly bear to let Sarah Churchill, Duchess of Marlborough (1660–1744), out of her sight.
- Excessive letter writing is a clue, particularly if the letters were subsequently destroyed.
- One of the familiar themes in same-sex couples is the desire to live together. While romantic friends, or the other variant terms, may express a vague desire to live together, they rarely make or carry out plans. The Ladies of Llangollen ran away together because they wanted to live together, not because they were fleeing from forced marriages, as is often claimed...Many single women did live together in companionship, but without their diaries or letters it is impossible to know the true nature of the relationship.
- In the late eighteenth and early nineteenth centuries, women often lived together in ‘cottage ornées’, decorated or stylised ‘cottages’ inspired by

⁸⁵ See [Summary of findings on Knowledge Equity in Linked Open Data, submitted to Wikimedia Deutschland](#)

the Romantic Movement, which represented a move away from formal, heavy architecture to a more 'natural' way of living. They were built mainly by the wealthy, even royalty, as retreats or additions to their estates. The term was coined to distinguish structures that turned a labourer's cottage into aesthetic artefact, and the cottage ornée was seen as a pure, back-to-nature way of living where children could be brought up in a heterosexual and wholesome environment. However, by the early nineteenth century, the cottage ornée was also being utilised by women living together...As more women moved into them, the term began to fall out of favour.

- Excessive gift giving is another indicator of same-sex couples, as opposed to romantic friendships. Whilst romantic friends did give gifts, they tended not to be as frequent as those exchanged by couples and would often be accompanied by letters explaining the significance of the gift to their relationship.
- 'Couple speak' is a good indicator of same-sex relationships. Samesex couples describe themselves as 'we', 'our' or 'us', whereas romantic friends rarely do. Frances Power Cobbe peppered her own writings with 'our house', 'our garden', 'we' and other joint terminology about her partner Mary Lloyd: 'We gave afternoon tea to our friends under the limes ... We often had ... as many as fifty or sixty guests. In short, I had once more a home, and a most happy one; and my lonely wanderings were over.'
- Friends would write inclusively to couples. For example, letters to Frances Power Cobbe would be addressed to 'you and Miss Lloyd'. In various letters to John Gibson (1790–1866), writers asked him to pass on their 'kindest regards' to Penry Williams (1802–1885), and another asked to be remembered to Penry.
- Writings by friends should also be examined, as many individuals and couples were friends with other same-sex couples. Frances Power Cobbe and Mary Lloyd were part of a large group of friends that included Charlotte Cushman (1816–1876) and her various 'wives' as well as John Gibson and Penry Williams. Other people may have written about the couple, referred to them living or travelling together, or just gossiped about them.
- A significant inheritance left to someone who shared an individual's life may also be an indicator. While romantic friends often left bequests to each other, these rarely involved leaving an entire estate, as John Gibson did for his partner Penry Williams.

- Partners in same-sex couples may have left instructions to destroy material. For example, Mary Lloyd told her partner, Frances Power Cobbe, to destroy all of her written material. Frances did so. Posterity only has Frances's voice and silence from Mary.

Singly, the[se] criteria cannot be used to evaluate a relationship. However, by combining several, it is easier to raise the possibility and probability that individuals were in a same-sex relationship.⁸⁶

6.3.4. “Case” Studies/Examples

This section offers a “laundry list” style of examples or case studies which QMDC members or reviewers found interesting but there was convenient place to include in the text of our document.

- SFMOMA is an example from art museum world where they reached out to verify names with artists:
 - www.sfmoma.org/march-2022-update-artist-identities-data-program/
 - www.sfmoma.org/connecting-people-to-the-art-of-our-time/
- Aviary Platform: Has a plugin that checks work of catalogers / students; it is not perfect but terms from marginalized vocabs like Homosaurus terms can be added as suggestions of additions.
- Oklahoma State University Libraries has been developing a process to consult agents directly to receive their input on what an agent would want on their Wikidata item: <https://osf.io/63hrd>

6.3.4.1. The Five Colleges of Ohio: “Flagging”

The Five Colleges of Ohio, a consortium of private liberal colleges and universities consisting of Denison University, Kenyon College, Oberlin College, Ohio Wesleyan College, and the College of Wooster began conversations and planning around dealing with problematic metadata during a 2019 Collection Services Subcommittee meeting. With the Change the Subject documentary and its subsequent efforts, we discussed several examples of additional problematic subject terms, typically those dealing with racist or homophobic terms and acknowledged that subject headings can be difficult for researchers to navigate. Many researchers may use outdated or offensive terms in

⁸⁶ Norena Shopland, *A Practical Guide to Searching LGBTQIA Historical Records*, 1st ed. (Routledge, 2021), <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003006787>, p. 41-3.

their desire to be comprehensive in their search, even when they understood the harm inherent in the use of these terms. Our subcommittee discussed the challenges of changing subject headings locally, striving to strike the balance between removing these terms from the catalog and retaining the terms to ensure retrieval of information when an outdated or offensive term is present.

Inspired in part by the actions of Twitter on President Donald Trump's tweets in late 2020, where Twitter assigned labels to tweets that included misinformation, warning of false, misleading, or disputed information, we considered a similar approach for acknowledging problematic subject headings and fostering a habit of critical evaluation of online information. Through a flagging system, we believe there is an opportunity to invite patrons into a dialogue about the role of subject headings, the biases and problems they reflect, and continued discussion about inclusive language.

Since there is a lack of an authoritative list of problematic, vague, or harmful terms, we discussed developing and maintaining a local list of terms, but instead of reinventing the wheel, started our terms list with the list found on the community-driven initiative The Cataloging Lab. Using this list, we proposed this resources to the Director of Consortial Library System, Ben Daigle, who developed a lightweight script for Innovative Interfaces (III) Sierra WebPac, our public library interface. The script checks for the presences of each heading in the list of known problematic terms and if a match occurs, displays a red flag next to the subject heading. When a patron clicks the flag for more information, they see a panel signifying that the term is recognized as problematic and gives a brief description of the purpose of subject headings and how changes are made in a "learn more" link. The link to "learn more" leads to a page that is framed as a set of questions and answers. We view this page as a resource for providing more context about the kinds of biases that exist in our library systems, how these issues arose in the first place, and processes for changing them. This resource is framed as a pedagogical springboard for discussions with students, colleagues, and campus partners about systemic bias in a system which is conventionally considered neutral, and it offers a concrete example of how authority of information is constructed and fluid, particularly as a more diverse set of voices lend their perspectives and knowledge to those constructs.

6.4. Current Options In Dominant Systems

6.4.1. Subject Headings

Subsection Contents:

[6.4.1.1. Problematic Library of Congress Subject Headings LCSH](#)

[6.4.1.2. Problematic LC Demographic Group Terms \(LCDGT\)](#)

[6.4.1.3. Problematic LC Children's and Young Adults' Cataloging Program \(CYAC\) Headings](#)

[6.4.1.4. Problematic Medical Subject Headings \(MeSH\)](#)

[6.4.1.5. Selected Queer LCSH](#)

[6.4.1.6. LCSH That Should Exist \(That Currently Do Not\)](#)

6.4.1.1. Problematic LC Subject Headings (LCSH)

- [Androgyny \(Psychology\)](#): The parenthetical on this limits its typical usage and should be replaced with terms such as “Androgynous people.”
- [Bisexual men--Relations with women](#)
- Bisexuals’/Gays’/Lesbians’/Transsexuals’ writings (and other variants): There is not a subject headings for heterosexuals’ writings, establishing it as a default and LGBTQ+ writings as the exception from the norm; also often used in cases where the story may have LGBTQ+ characters yet the author’s identity is not known.
- [Coming out \(Sexual orientation\)](#): The current scope note only covers homosexuality; it needs an updated scope note to include more sexualities and gender identities along with the social context of coming out.
- [Gay men--Relations with heterosexual women](#): Focuses only on heterosexual relationships with individuals of other sexualities. Narrower term “Man-woman” further normalises cis identities.
- [Gay men--Relations with lesbians](#): Focuses only on relations with one identity; narrower term “Man-woman” further normalises cis identities.
- [Gay pride celebrations](#): All the pride celebration/parade terms start with “Gay pride.” While there are probably specifically gay pride events, it’s more common for it to be a general non-hetero pride.
- [Gays](#): Reductive term; preferable to use Gay people. While LC revised this in November 2023, it was a long-existing heading and libraries should check that the change is reflected in their local catalogues.
- [Gender identity disorders](#): Outdated psychological term that treats transness or gender nonconformity as a medical disorder. Not all transgender or gender diverse people experience gender dysphoria and the term was removed from the DSM by the American Psychiatric Association in 2013.

- [Gender nonconformity](#): The scope note of this term is problematic in that it emphasises behaviours or manifestations (i.e. cross-dressing, transsexualism, male or female impersonation) that express gender nonconformity rather than describing the identity itself and internal experiences of gender nonconformity. In describing gender nonconformity in only this way, it reduces nonconforming gender experiences to what can be physically seen or experienced.
- [Gender-nonconforming people](#): Cataloging Lab Problem LCSH comments: “Gender-nonconformity depicts a bias that believes in the adherence to gender stereotypes of a binary gender system.”
- [Husband and wife](#): From Cataloging Lab Problem LCSH comments “LCSH redirects “Spouses--legal status, laws, etc.” to “Husband and wife”, which has a scope note that excludes same-sex spousal pairs.”
- [Man-woman relationships](#): Hetero- and cis-normative.
 - Man-woman relationships is the default subject heading to describe the coupling dynamic in romance novels. This practice has proliferated this heading in romance novels and had an adverse impact on romance novels that include mixed or queer orientation-couplings. The binary language places prime importance on the gender of the pairing, instead of the nature of their coupling. This heading flattens the reality of queer folks, inserting binary gender labels into what may be a relationship between queer/gender-diverse folks. While the recent inclusion of Man-man relationships and Woman-woman relationships introduces options for some queer folks, the continued focus on gender binaries continues to limit the ways that queer couplings can be defined and pointed towards.
- [Outing \(Sexual orientation\)](#) Needs an updated scope note to include more sexualities and gender identities along with the social contexts of outing.
- Relations with heterosexuals
 - [Bisexuals--Relations with heterosexuals](#): Focuses on heterosexual relationships with individuals of other sexualities whereas there is only one heading for queer interactions with other queer folks.
 - [Gay men--Relations with heterosexuals](#): Focuses only on heterosexual relationships with individuals of other sexualities. Narrower term “Man-woman” further normalises cis identities.
 - [Lesbians--Relations with heterosexuals](#): Focuses only on heterosexual relationships with individuals of other sexualities. Narrower term “Man-woman” further normalises cis identities.
- [Sexual minorities](#): Cataloging Lab Problem LCSH comments “The authorized heading does not reflect predominant usage of how LGBTQ people are referred

to. The authority also has the UF Gender minorities, which deserves its own heading and is in fact a separate term in LCDGT.”

- [Sexual reorientation programs](#): Cataloging Lab Problem LCSH comments “Authorized form is sanitized and not most commonly used form”. The scope note is similarly sanitised.
- [Unmarried couples](#): Includes the RT “Free love.” This related term should be removed as there are many reasons why a couple might be unmarried.

6.4.1.2. Problematic LC Demographic Group Terms (LCDGT)

- [Aromantic people](#): Should have BT Sexual minorities as well as RT Asexual people.
- [Bisexuals](#): Reductive term; preferable to use “Bisexual people.”
- [Femmes \(Lesbian culture\)](#): Should also be a heading for Femme as gender identity.
- [Parents of gays](#): A holdover from the use of Gays as a broad term, which conflates gay people with the larger LGBTQ+ identity. Should be revised to align with this year’s revisions if it hasn’t already.
- [Sexual minorities](#): NTs do not include lesbians.

6.4.1.3. Problematic LC Children's and Young Adults' Cataloging Program (CYAC) Headings

- [Gay Pride Day](#): All the pride celebration/parade terms start with “Gay pride.” While there are probably specifically gay pride events, it’s more common for it to be a general non-hetero pride.
- [Gay pride parades](#)
- [Gender nonconformity](#): Shares the same problematic scope note as the LCSH. Centres cisnormativity as something to conform to.

6.4.1.4. Problematic Medical Subject Headings (MeSH)

- [Sex Reassignment Procedures](#): Preferred term in common use is “Gender Confirmation Surgery”.

6.4.1.5. Selected Queer LCSH

Rather than being a comprehensive list of existing queer LCSH, the following appendix is a selected list of broader categories of LCSH with queer subjects and/or contexts, including example terms under each broader subject.

- Abuse: Terms dealing with intimate-partner violence within queer relationships.
 - [Lesbian partner abuse](#), [Abused gay men](#), [Same-sex partner abuse](#)
- African-American queer people: Terms that describe African-American people with marginalised sexualities.
 - [African American gay men--Identity](#), [African American transgender people](#)
- Alaska Native queer people: Terms that describe Alaskan Native people with marginalised sexualities.
 - [Alaska Native sexual minorities](#), [Alaska Native sexual minority youth](#)
- [Androgyny \(Psychology\)](#): Terms that describe behaviours and presentations that reflect simultaneously masculine and feminine gender expectations.
 - [Androgyny \(Psychology\)--Religious aspects](#), [Androgyny \(Psychology\) in art](#)
- [Asexual people](#): A Euro-American term for those who experience little or no sexual attraction and/or who self-identify with asexuality.
 - [African American asexual people](#), [Asexual people—United States](#)
- Asian American queer people: Terms that describe Asian American people with marginalised sexualities.
 - [Asian American sexual minorities](#)
- [Bible--Gay interpretations](#): The term for works on Biblical interpretations from a gay viewpoint, emphasising such matters as sexual practices and sexual identities.
- Bisexual people: Individuals who are romantically and/or sexually attracted to more than one gender and who identify as bisexual.
 - [Jewish bisexuals](#), [Asian American bisexuals](#), [Bisexuals--Relations with heterosexuals](#)
- [Boys love \(Manga\)](#): Also known as BL, a term for a narrative genre, typically created by women for women that depicts male/male romantic and sexual relations.
- Catholic LGBTQ+ people: LGBTQ+ people who practise Catholicism.
 - [Catholic gay men](#), [Catholic lesbians](#)
- [Children of same-sex parents](#): Children whose parents are or have been in same-sex relationships.
- [Children of sexual minority parents](#): Children of parents who identify as LGBTQ+.
 - [Children of gay parents](#), [Children of transgender parents](#), [Children of same-sex parents](#)
- [Coming out \(Sexual orientation\)](#): Term for the process of accepting and sharing one's sexual identity with oneself and/or others.
- [Deaf gay people](#): LGBTQ+ people who are Deaf or Hard of Hearing.

- [Drag performance](#): Term for works on performance that often involves adopting generally exaggerated personas including a different gender identity than the artist's own, for purposes of entertainment, comic effect, or political commentary.
 - [Drag kings](#), [Drag balls](#), [Drag queens in motion pictures](#)
- [Etiquette for gay men](#): Guidance for conduct of behaviour in gay spaces and communities.
- [Etiquette for lesbians](#): Guidance for conduct of behaviour in lesbian spaces and communities.
- [Ex-gay movement](#): A movement led primarily by evangelical and fundamentalist Christians that attempts to change the sexual orientations of individuals from homosexuality to heterosexuality.
- [Gay activists](#): Gay men who are working to bring about political or social change through public organising.
- [Gay adoption](#): Term for the adoption of children by people who identify as gay men or lesbians.
 - [Gay adoption--Law and legislation](#)
- [Gay and lesbian studies](#): The cross-disciplinary study of gay men and lesbians in literature, history, religion, psychology, sociology, philosophy, anthropology, medicine, law, fine arts, and other subjects.
- [Gay men's writings](#): Term for works on writings and literature of gay men.
 - [Gay men's writings, Arabic](#), [Gay men's writings, Colombian](#)
- [Gay people's writings](#): Term for works on writings and literature of homosexual people.
 - [Gay people's writings, American](#), [Gay people's writings, Chinese](#)
- [Handkerchief codes](#)
- [Heterosexism](#): Term for works on the presumption that heterosexuality is the only normal sexual orientation.
 - [Heterosexism-Religious aspects](#), [Heterosexism in literature](#), [Heterosexism in medicine](#)
- Hispanic American queer people: Terms that describe Hispanic American people with marginalised sexualities.
 - [Hispanic American gay men](#), [Hispanic American gay people](#)
- HIV-positive men: Terms for describing HIV-positive men with marginalised sexualities
 - [HIV-positive bisexual men](#), [HIV-positive gay men](#)
- [Homomonument \(Amsterdam, Netherlands\)](#)
- [Homophobia](#): Terms for works on active discrimination against homosexuals
 - [Homophobia-Law and legislation](#), [Homophobia in children](#)
- [Homosexuality](#): Term for works on same-sex sexual attraction

- [Homosexuality \(Canon law\)](#), [Homosexuality–Folklore](#), [Homosexuality and music](#)
- Indian queer people: Terms for works on indigenous people from America with marginalised sexualities
 - [Indian gay people](#), [Indian lesbians](#), [Indian sexual minority youth](#)
- [Internalized homophobia](#)
 - [Internalized homophobia in lesbians](#)
- Internet and sexual minorities: Terms for the internet and marginalised sexualities
 - [Internet and bisexual men](#), [Internet and gay men](#)
- [Intersexuality](#): Terms that describe intersex people.
 - [Intersex people](#), [Intersexuality in art](#), [Intersex people–Identity](#), [Intersex athletes](#)
- Italian American queer people: Terms for works on Americans of Italian descent and marginalised sexualities
 - [Italian American gay people](#), [Italian American lesbians](#)
- Jewish queer people: Terms for works on Jewish people with marginalised sexualities and/or gender identities
 - [Jewish bisexual people](#), [Jewish gay men](#), [Jewish lesbians](#), [Jewish transgender people](#)
- [Latter Day Saint gay people](#): Term for works describing Mormon gay people
- [Leather bars](#)
- [Legal assistance to gay people](#)
- [Lesbians](#): Term for works on lesbians
 - [Lesbian activists](#), [Lesbian bars in motion pictures](#), [Lesbian business enterprises](#)
- [Lesbian feminism](#)
- [Lesbian feminist theory](#)
- [LGBT community centers](#)
- [LGBT History Month](#)
- Libraries and queer people: Terms for works on library service to people with marginalised sexualities and/or gender orientations
 - [Libraries and bisexual people](#), [Libraries and transgender people](#)
- [Male homosexuality](#): Terms for works on same sex attraction between males
 - [Male homosexuality–Mythology](#), [Male homosexuality in the theater](#)
- [Male impersonators](#): Here are entered works on women who dress as men for the purpose of playing a theatrical role, etc.
 - [Male impersonators in motion pictures](#), [Male impersonators in literature](#)
- [Male prostitution](#)
- [Male-to-female transsexuals](#)

- [Mass media and gay people](#)
- Mexican American queer people: Terms for works on Americans of Mexican descent and marginalised sexualities
 - [Mexican American gay people](#), [Mexican American lesbians](#)
- Middle-aged queer people: Terms for works on middle-aged people with marginalised sexualities
 - [Middle-aged gay men](#), [Middle-aged lesbians](#), [Middle-aged gay people](#)
- Minority queer people: Terms for works on people with both marginalised sexualities and other marginalised identities
 - [Minority gay people](#), [Minority lesbians](#), [Minority transgender women](#)
- [Motion pictures and gay men](#)
- [Museums and sexual minorities](#)
- Music by queer people: Terms for works on musical composers with marginalised sexualities
 - [Music by gay composers](#), [Music by lesbian composers](#)
- Muslim queer people: Terms for works on Muslim people with marginalised sexualities
 - [Muslim gay men](#), [Muslim lesbians](#), [Muslim gay people](#)
- [National socialism and homosexuality](#)
- Neopagan queer people: Terms for works on neopagan people with marginalised sexualities
 - [Neopagan gay people](#)
- Older people: Terms for works on older people with marginalised sexualities
 - [Older transgender people](#), [Older gay people](#)
- [Ordination of gay people](#): Terms for works on ordination of people with marginalised sexualities.
 - [Ordination of gay people-Catholic Church](#), [Ordination of lesbians-United Methodist Church](#)
- [Ordination of lesbians](#): Terms for works on ordination of lesbians.
 - [Ordination of lesbians Presbyterian Church \(U.S.A.\)](#)
- [Outing \(Sexual orientation\)](#): Term for works on publicly disclosing the sexuality of other persons
- Pacific Islander American queer people: Terms for works on Americans of Pacific Islander descent with marginalised sexualities.
 - [Pacific Islander American bisexual people](#), [Pacific Islander American sexual minorities](#)
- Parents of queer people: Terms for works on parents of people with marginalised sexualities.
 - [Parents of gay people](#), [Parents of gender-nonconforming children](#)

- [Queer comic books, strips, etc.](#): Term for works on comic books or graphic novels that are about the queer experience.
- [Queer theory](#): Term for works on the study and theorization of gender, sexual practices, and identities that exist outside of heterosexuality and which challenge heteronormativity.
- [Same-sex marriage](#): Terms for works about marriage between people of the same-sex.
 - [Same-sex marriage--Law and legislation](#), [Same-sex marriage--Religious aspects](#)
- [Sexual minorities](#): Term for works on people with marginalised sexualities.
 - [Sexual minorities and sports](#), [Sexual minorities, Black](#), [Sexual minorities \(Islamic law\)](#)
- [Sexual minorities' writings](#): Term for works on writings and literature of people with marginalised sexualities.
 - [Sexual minorities' writings, Australian](#), [Sexual minorities' writings, New Zealand](#)
- [Sexual orientation](#): Term for works on an individual's sexual attraction towards other individuals.
- Social work with queer people: Terms for works on social work with people with marginalised sexualities.
 - [Social work with bisexual people](#), [Social work with lesbians](#)
- [Stonewall Riots, New York, N.Y., 1969](#): Term for works about the 1969 Stonewall riots.
- [Television and gay people](#): Term for works about how LGBTQ+ people affect and/or are affected by television media.
- [Two-spirit people](#): Term used by some Indigenous North Americans to describe Native people who identify as having both a masculine and a feminine spirit.
 - [Two-spirit people in literature](#), [Two-spirit people--Psychology](#)
- [Web sites for sexual minorities](#): Term for works on web sites for people with marginalised sexualities.
- [Women's music](#): Term for musical works composed, performed, and produced by and for women and often associated with the lesbian feminist movement in the United States.
- World War, 1939-1945: Terms for how gay people participated in, or were affected by, World War II.
 - [World War, 1939-1945--Gay people](#), [World War, 1939-1945-- Participation, Gay](#)
- Young queer men: Terms for works on young men with marginalised sexualities.
 - [Young gay men](#), [Young bisexual men](#)

6.4.1.6. LCSH That Should Exist (That Currently Do Not)

6.4.1.6.1. Kink terminology

Autoeroticism
BDSM and related terminology
Bootblacking
Breast fetishism
Chemsex
Erotic massage
Leather subculture
Nipple play
Rubber subculture and related terminology

6.4.1.6.2. Queer Medical Terminology

GRID (Gay-Related Immune Deficiency)
Health care for LGBTQ+ people
Hopkins model
Intersex-related terminology
Person with HIV/AIDS

6.4.1.6.4. Historical Terminology

Ball culture
Boston marriages
Goddess movement
Inverts
Lavender Scare

6.4.1.6.4. LGBTQ+ Family Life

Biological parenthood
LGBTQ+ parenthood
LGBTQ+ parents
Children of [identity] people and related headings (ex. Children of bisexual people)
Conception by LGBTQ+ people
Desire to have children
Domestic partnerships and related terminology
Donor siblings
Egg donation
Egg donors

Family members of LGBTQ+ people
Genetic parenthood
Gestational parenthood
Gestational surrogacy
Known donors (Reproduction)
Mixed-orientation relationships, marriage and related terminology
Open identity donors (Reproduction)
Reciprocal in vitro fertilization
Second parent adoption

6.4.1.6.5. Queer Identity Terminology

Alloromanticism or Alloromantic people
Allosexuality or Allosexual people
Bioromanticism or Bioromantic people
Butches (Butch and Femme (Lesbian Culture) is the only term that exists)
Closeted queer people and related identities (There is a term for Closeted gay people, but not for any other identities)
Demiromanticism or Demiromantic people
Demisexuality or Demisexual people
Greyromanticism or Greyromantic people
Greysexuality or Greysexual people
Heteromanticism or Heteromantic people
Panromanticism or Panromantic people
Sapphic identity, sapphics and related terminology (the Term Sapphics refers to poetry in LCSH)
Queer people/identity

6.4.1.6.6. Queer Slang Terminology

Baby gay
Baby dykes
Beards (Gay culture)
Binding (Chest)
Bury your gays
Camp (Gay culture)
Chubs (Gay culture)
Clocking (Gender)
Clones (Gay culture)
Cottages (Gay culture), Cottaging (Gay culture)
Cruising (LGBTQ+ culture)

Cubs (Gay culture)
Dandies, Dandyism
Drab (LGBTQ+ culture)
Fairies (Gay culture)
Femmes
Goldilocks (Gay culture)
Outing (LGBTQ+ culture)
Passing (Sexuality)
Queens (Gay culture)
Studs
Twinks (Gay culture)
Wolves (Gay culture)

6.4.1.6.7. Relationship-based LGBTQ+ Language

Asexual couples, Asexual relationships
Bisexual couples, Bisexual relationships
Gay relationships
Lesbian relationships
LGBTQ+ couples
Non-sexual/non-romantic intimacy (There is a term for Romantic orientation and Sexual attraction under “Interpersonal attraction”)
Queer couples (mixed-orientation/broad representation of couples in general)
Queer relationships
Two-spirit couples, Two-spirit relationships

6.4.1.6.8. LGBTQ+ Social Science Terminology

Amatonormativity
Compulsory monogamy
Compulsory sexuality
Consensual non-monogamy and related terminology
Corrective rape
Ego-dystonic sexual orientation
Essentialism (exists but is not referring to Biological essentialism)
Homoeroticism
Homosociality
Internalized homophobia in gay men (There is a term for Internalized homophobia in lesbians, but no parallel term for gay men.)
Homonationalism
Mononormativity

6.4.1.6.9. Other

Internet and lesbians, Internet and bisexual women (There is a term for Internet and gay men and Internet and bisexual men, but no parallel term for women or non-binary identities)

Motion pictures and lesbians (There is a broad term Homosexuality and motion pictures and a term for Motion pictures and gay men, but no parallel narrow term for women.)

6.4.2. Classification

Subsection Contents:

[6.4.2.1. Library of Congress Classification Numbers](#)

[6.4.2.2. Dewey Decimal Classification Numbers](#)

6.4.2.1. Library of Congress Classification Numbers

[LCC numbers - working copy](#)

Last Updated: 06-14-2024

Main Class	Full Classification	Description
B - Philosophy. Psychology. Religion.		
B	B2430.F72-.F724	Foucault, Michel.
B	BF723.H67	Developmental psychology. Child psychology. Special topics. Homophobia.
B	BF1571.5.G39	Witchcraft. Special classes of persons. Gays.
B	BF1728.2.G39	Astrology. Horoscopes. Special Groups. Gay men.
B	BF1729.H66	Astrology. Special topics. Homosexuality
B	BL65.H64	Religions. Religion in relation to other subjects. Homosexuality
B	BL65.S4	Religions. Religion in relation to other subjects. Sex. Sex role.
B	BL325.B45	Religion. The myth. Comparative mythology. Topics in comparative mythology. Bisexuality. Androgyny. Hermaphroditism.
B	BL625.9.G39	Religion. Religious life. Special classes of persons. Gays.

B	BL625.9.S49	Religion. Religious life. Special classes of persons. Sexual minorities.
B	BL795.B57	Religion. Classical religion and mythology Greek. Special topics. Bisexuality.
B	BL795.H6	Religion. Classical religion and mythology. Greek. Special topics. Homosexuality.
B	BM667.S49	Practical Judaism. Liturgy and ritual. General and miscellaneous prayer and service books. Works for special classes. Sexual minorities.
B	BM729.H65	Practical Judaism Other special topics. Homosexuality. Gays. Lesbians.
B	BM729.T65	Practical Judaism Other special topics. Transgenderism.
B	BP134.G43	Islam. Sacred books Qur'an Koran. Works about the Qur'an. Special Topics. Gender identity.
B	BP134.H65	Islam. Sacred books Qur'an Koran. Works about the Qur'an. Special Topics. Homosexuality.
B	BP188.14.H65	Islam. Sins. Vices. Homosexuality.
B	BP190.5.H7*	Islam. Topics not otherwise provided. Homosexuality.
B	BQ4570.A37	Doctrinal and systematic Buddhism. Special topics (nondoctrinal) and relations to special subjects. AIDS (Disease).
B	BQ4570.H65	Doctrinal and systematic Buddhism. Special topics (nondoctrinal) and relations to special subjects. Homosexuality.
B	BQ5480.G39	Practices of Buddhism. Forms of worship. Religious life of special groups. Gays.
B	BR115.H6	Christianity. In relation to special subjects. Homosexuality.
B	BR115.T76	Christianity. In relation to special subjects. Transgender people. Transvestism. Transsexualism.
B	BS680.H67	The Bible. Works about the Bible. Topics. Homosexuality.
B	BS1199.G36	The Bible. Old Testament. Works about the OT. Topics. Gender identity.
B	BS1238.H66	The Bible. Old Testament. Historical books. Pentateuch. Genesis. Other special. Homosexuality.
B	BS2545.G36	The Bible. New Testament. Works about the NT. Topics. Gender identity.
B	BS2545.L47	The Bible. New Testament. Works about the NT. Topics. Lesbianism.
B	BT708.3	Doctrinal theology. Creation. Sex. Androgyny.

B	BT708.6	Doctrinal theology. Creation. Sex. Sodomy.
B	BT83.65	Doctrinal theology, dogmatic, systematic theology. Schools of thought affecting doctrine and dogma (19th-20th centuries). Queer theology.
B	BV199.G39	Practical Theology. Worship (Public and private). Liturgy and ritual Service books. Liturgies Other special, A-Z. Gays, Services For.
B	BV4437.5	Practical Theology. Church work with special classes. Sexual minorities. Gays. Lesbians. Homosexuals.
B	BV4437.6	Practical Theology. Church work with special classes. Transgender people.
B	BV4460.7	Pastoral theology. Church work with special classes. People with disabilities, sick, etc. AIDS patients.
B	BV4596.G38	Practical Theology. Practical religion. The Christian life. Religious works for special classes of persons. Other. Gays.
B	BV4910.3	Practical religion. The Christian life. Works for special classes of persons. The sick and the crippled. AIDS patients.
B	BX1795.G46	Christian denominations. Catholic Church. Other special topics. Gender identity.
B	BX1795.H66	Christian denominations. Catholic Church. Other special topics. Homosexuality. Gay rights.
B	BX2347.8.A52	Catholic Church. Practical religion. Church work. Social service. Work with, and attitude towards, special groups, classes. AIDS patients.
B	BX2347.8.H65	Catholic Church. Practical religion. Work with, and attitude towards, special groups, classes. Homosexuals. Gay people. Sexual minorities.
B	BX2373.L46	Catholic Church. Christian life. Religious works for special classes of persons. Lesbians.
B	BX342.9.G38	Orthodox Easter Church. Other special topics. Gays.
B	BX5008.9.H65	Anglican Communion. Other special. Homosexuality.
B	BX5979.5.H65	Episcopal Church. Protestant Episcopal Church in the USA. Other special topics. Homosexuality.
B	BX8074.H65	Other Protestant denominations. Lutheran churches. Other special. Homosexuality.
B	BX8128.H67	Other Protestant denominations. Mennonites. Special topics. Homosexuality.
B	BX8349.H66	Other Protestant denominations. Methodism. Other special topics. Homosexuality.

B	BX8385.H65	Other Protestant denominations. Methodism. United Methodist Church (US), Methodist Church (US), Methodist Episcopal Church. Special topics. Homosexuality.
B	BX8643.H65	Other Protestant denominations. Mormons. Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-Day Saints. Special topics. Homosexuality.
B	BX8643.L55	Other Protestant denominations. Mormons. Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-Day Saints. Special topics. Lesbianism.
B	BX9423.H66	Other Protestant denominations. Reformed or Calvinistic churches. Special topics. Homosexuality.
D -- World History and History of Europe, Asia, Africa, Australia, New Zealand, etc.		
D	D639.G39	World War I (1914-1918). Other special topics. Gays.
D	D804.5.G38	World War II (1939-1945). Holocaust. Other victim groups. Gays.
D	D810.G39	World War II (1939-1945). Other special topics. Gays. Gay military participation.
E - History of the Americas		
E	E98.S48	Indians of North America. Other topics. Sexual behavior. Including homosexuality.
F - Local History of the Americas		
F	F2519.3.H66	South America. Brazil. Antiquities. Indians. Topics. Homosexuality.
G - Geology. Anthropology. Recreation.		
G	GN484.35	Anthropology. Sexual behavior. Sex customs. Homosexuality.
G	GV183.2	Recreation for special classes of persons. Gay men. Lesbians.
G	GV708.8	Sports. Sports for special classes of persons Gay men. Lesbians. Transgender people.
G	GV722.5.G36	Sports. Athletic contests. Sports events. Other contests and events. Gay Games.
G	GV1469.34.H66	Video games. Special topics. Homosexuality.
G	GV1749.5	Gay and lesbian dance parties. Including drag balls.
H - Social Sciences		
H	HD2359-2359.5	Industry. Other special categories of businesses. Gay business enterprises.

H	HD6285	Labor. Work. Working class. Classes of labor. Sexual minorities. Including individual groups, e.g. gays, lesbians, transgender people.
H	HD6285.5	Labor. Work. Working class. Classes of labor. Sexual minorities. By region or country, A-Z.
H	HE6183.H57	Postage stamps. Postmarks. By topic. Homosexuals.
H	HF5382.68 - HF5382.69	Business. Vocational guidance for specific (non-occupational) groups. Gays.
H	HF5415.332.G9	Business. Marketing research. Particular groups of consumers. Gays.
H	HF5549.5.S47	Business. Personnel management. Employment management. By topic. Sexual orientation (including homosexuality and bisexuality).
H	HF5827.82	Business. Advertising. Gays in advertising.
H	HQ18.32.K56	Kinsey, Alfred.
H	HQ18.5	Human sexuality. Sex. Sexual orientation.
H	HQ18.55	Human sexuality. Sex. Gender identity.
H	HQ73.8	Gender nonconformity. General works.
H	HQ73.85.A-Z	Gender nonconformity. By region or country, A-Z.
H	HQ73.9-.99	Asexuality (several call numbers)
H	HQ74	Bisexuality. General works.
H	HQ74.2	Bisexuality. By region or country, A-Z.
H	HQ74.4	Bisexuality. Bisexual women.
H	HQ74.7	Bisexuality. Bisexual men.
H	HQ75	Homosexuality. Lesbianism. Periodicals. Serials.
H	HQ75.115	Homosexuality. Lesbianism. Congresses.

H	HQ75.12	Homosexuality. Lesbianism. Societies.
H	HQ75.13	Homosexuality. Lesbianism. Dictionaries.
H	HQ75.14	Homosexuality. Lesbianism. Computer networks. Electronic information resources (including the Internet and digital libraries).
H	HQ75.15-75.16	Gay and lesbian studies.
H	HQ75.2	Homosexuality. Lesbianism. Biography (Collective).
H	HQ75.25-75.26	Homosexuality. Lesbianism. Travel.
H	HQ75.27-75.28	Homosexuality. Lesbianism. Gay parents.
H	HQ75.3	Lesbians. Biography. Collective.
H	HQ75.4	Lesbians. Biography. Individual, A-Z.
H	HQ75.5	Lesbians. General works.
H	HQ75.51	Lesbians. Sex instruction.
H	HQ75.5115	Lesbians. Sexual behavior.
H	HQ75.53	Lesbian mothers.
H	HQ75.55	Middle-aged lesbians. Older lesbians.
H	HQ75.6	Lesbians. By region or country, A-Z.
H	HQ75.7	Gay men. Biography. Collective.
H	HQ75.8	Gay men. Biography. Individual, A-Z.
H	HQ75.8.K35	Kameny, Frank.
H	HQ76	Gay men. General works.
H	HQ76.1	Gay men. Sex instruction.
H	HQ76.115	Gay men. Sexual behavior.

H	HQ76.13	Gay fathers.
H	HQ76.14	Middle-aged gay men. Older gay men.
H	HQ76.2	Gay men. By region or country, A-Z.
H	HQ76.25	Homosexuality. Lesbianism. General works.
H	HQ76.26	Homosexuality. Lesbianism. Juvenile works.
H	HQ76.27	Special classes of gay people, A-Z.
H	HQ76.27.A37	Special classes of gay people. African Americans.
H	HQ76.27.O44	Special classes of gay people. Older gays.
H	HQ76.27.R66	Special classes of gay people. Romanies.
H	HQ76.27.Y68	Special classes of gay people. Youth.
H	HQ76.3	Homosexuality. Lesbianism. By region or country, A-Z.
H	HQ76.34	Same-sex relationships. General works.
H	HQ76.35	Same-sex relationships. By region or country, A-Z
H	HQ76.4	Homophobia. Heterosexism. General works.
H	HQ76.45	Homophobia. Heterosexism. By region or country, A-Z.
H	HQ76.5	Gay rights movement. Gay liberation movement. Homophile movement. General works.
H	HQ76.8	Gay rights movement. Gay liberation movement. Homophile movement. By region or country, A-Z.
H	HQ76.85	Gay conservatives.
H	HQ76.9	Gay press publications. General works.
H	HQ76.95	Gay press publications. By region or country, A-Z
H	HQ76.96	Gay and lesbian culture. General works.

H	HQ76.965	Gay and lesbian culture. Special topics, A-Z.
H	HQ76.965.B38	Gay and lesbian culture. Bathhouses. Saunas. Steam baths.
H	HQ76.965.B45	Gay and lesbian culture. Bears.
H	HQ76.965.G38	Gay and lesbian culture. Gay pride parades.
H	HQ76.965.H35	Gay and lesbian culture. Handkerchief codes.
H	HQ76.965.O54	Gay and lesbian culture. Online chat groups.
H	HQ76.965.P67	Gay and lesbian culture. Pornography.
H	HQ76.965.R33	Gay and lesbian culture. Racism.
H	HQ76.97	Cross-dressing. Transvestism. Biography. Collective.
H	HQ76.98	Cross-dressing. Transvestism. Biography. Individual, A-Z.
H	HQ77	Cross-dressing. Transvestism. General works.
H	HQ77.2	Cross-dressing. Transvestism. By region or country, A-Z
H	HQ77.7	Transsexualism. Transgenderism. Biography. Collective.
H	HQ77.8	Transsexualism. Transgenderism. Biography. Individual, A-Z.
H	HQ77.8.J67	Jorgensen, Christine.
H	HQ77.9	Transsexualism. Transgenderism. General works.
H	HQ759.9145	Parents of gay men or lesbians.
H	HQ77.93	Transsexualism. Transgenderism. Transgender parents.
H	HQ77.94.S48	Transsexualism. Transgenderism—Special topics—Sexual behavior
H	HQ77.95	Transsexualism. Transgenderism. By region or country, A-Z.
H	HQ77.96	Transsexualism. Transgenderism. Transphobia. Transgender discrimination.

H	HQ77.965.A-Z	Transsexualism. Transgenderism. Transphobia. Transgender discrimination.. By region or country, A-Z.
H	HQ77.97	Intersex people. Intersexuality. Biography. Collective.
H	HQ77.98.A-Z	Intersex people. Intersexuality. Biography. Individual, A-Z.
H	HQ78	Intersex people. Intersexuality. General works.
H	HQ78.2.A-Z	Intersex people. Intersexuality. By region or country, A-Z.
H	HQ78.4	Intersex people. Intersexuality. Intersex discrimination. General works.
H	HQ78.42.A-Z	Intersex people. Intersexuality. Intersex discrimination. By region or country, A-Z.
H	HQ759.9145	Parents. Parenthood. Parents of gay men or lesbians.
H	HQ759.9147	Parents. Parenthood. Parents of transgender children.
H	HQ777.8	Children of gay parents.
H	HQ777.83	Children of transsexual parents.
H	HQ825	Same-sex divorce. Gay divorce.
H	HQ1033	Same-sex marriage. General works.
H	HQ1034	Same-sex marriage. By region or country, A-Z.
H	HQ1035-1035.5	Bisexuality in marriage.
H	HS3357.L47	Girls' societies (including Guides, Scouts, and Campfire). Special topics. Lesbianism.
H	HV875.715	Gay and lesbian adoption. General works.
H	HV875.72.A-Z	Gay and lesbian adoption. By region or country, A-Z.
H	HV1426	Protection, assistance and relief. Special classes. Sexual minority youth. Including gay, lesbian, bisexual, transgender, transsexual, and gender-nonconforming youth.
H	HV1449	Protection, assistance and relief. Special classes. Gay men. Lesbians.
H	HV2394	Protection, assistance and relief. Special classes. Deaf gays.

H	HV5139	Alcohol and gay people.
H	HV5824.G3	Drug habits. Drug abuse. Drugs and special classes of persons. Gays.
H	HV6250.4.H66	Criminology. Victims of crimes. Victimology. Special classes of persons as victims. Homosexuals.
H	HV6545.4	Suicide among special classes of persons. Gays.
H	HV8024	Gay, lesbian, and transgender police officers.
H	HV8838	Criminal justice administration. Prison methods and practice. Prison hygiene. Medical service. AIDS (Disease) in prisons.
H	HX550.H65	Communism/socialism in relation to other topics. Homosexuality.
J - Political Science.		
J	JJ1012.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. North America. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JK723.H6	United States. Government. Public administration. Executive branch. Civil service. Special classes of employees. Other Special, A-Z. Homosexual men and women.
J	JL206.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Canada. Newfoundland. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JL216.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Canada. Prince Edward Island. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JL226.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Canada. Nova Scotia. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JL236.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Canada. New Brunswick. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JL252.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Canada. Quebec. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JL272.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Canada. Ontario. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.

J	JL292.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Canada. Manitoba. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JL312.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Canada. Saskatchewan. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JL332.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Canada. Alberta. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JL432.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Canada. British Columbia. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JL472.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Canada. Northwest Territories. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JL486.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Canada. Nunavut. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JL495.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Canada. Yukon Territory. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JL596.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Bermuda. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JL599.2.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Greenland. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JL599.4.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Saint Pierre and Miquelon. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JL599.5.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. West Indies. Caribbean Area. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JL606.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. British West Indies. English-speaking Caribbean. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JL609.2.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Anguilla. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.

J	JL616.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Bahamas. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JL626.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Barbados. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JL629.5.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Cayman Islands. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JL629.6.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Grenada. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JL636.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Jamaica. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JL646.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Leeward Islands (General). Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JL649.2.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Antigua and Barbuda. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JL649.5.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Montserrat. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JL649.7.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Saint Kitts and Nevis. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JL656.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Trinidad and Tobago. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JL666.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Windward Islands (General). Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JL669.2.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Dominica. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JL669.5.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Saint Vincent and the Grenadines. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.

J	JL669.4.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Saint Lucia. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JL676.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Belize. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JL686.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Guyana. British Guiana. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JL696.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Falkland Islands. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JL766.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Netherlands Antilles. Dutch West Indies (General). Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JL769.3.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Aruba. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JL769.5.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Bonaire. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JL776.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Curacao. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JL779.2.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Saba. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JL779.5.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Saint Eustatius. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JL779.7.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Sint Maarten. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JL786.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Suriname. Dutch Guiana. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JL796.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. French West Indies (General). Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.

J	JL816.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. French Guiana. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JL826.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Guadeloupe. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JL836.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Martinique. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JL962.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Cuba. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JL1012.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Latin America. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JL1052.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Puerto Rico. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JL1092.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Haiti. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JL1132.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Dominican Republic. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JL1132.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Virgin Islands of the United States. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JL1249.H6	Political institutions and public administration. Mexico. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JL1412.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Central America (General). Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JL1452.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Costa Rica. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JL1492.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Guatemala. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.

J	JL1532.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Honduras. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JL1572.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. El Salvador. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JL1612.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Nicaragua. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JL1652.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Panama. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JL1676.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Panama Canal Zone. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JL1862.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. South America (General). Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JL2049.H6	Political institutions and public administration. Argentina. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JL2249.H6	Political institutions and public administration. Bolivia. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JL2449.H6	Political institutions and public administration. Brazil. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JL2649.H6	Political institutions and public administration. Chile. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JL2849.H6	Political institutions and public administration. Colombia. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JL3049.H6	Political institutions and public administration. Ecuador. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JL3249.H6	Political institutions and public administration. Paraguay. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.

J	JL3449.H6	Political institutions and public administration. Peru. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JL3649.H6	Political institutions and public administration. Uruguay. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JL3849.H6	Political institutions and public administration. Venezuela. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JL1862.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. South America (General). Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN96.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Western Europe. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN94.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Central Europe. Eastern Europe. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN97.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Balkan Peninsula. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN1156.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Wales. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN1176.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Isle of Man. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN1572.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Northern Ireland. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN1573.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Channel Islands. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN1576.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Gibraltar. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN1586.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Malta. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.

J	JN2201.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Slovenia. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN2202.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Croatia. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN2203.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Bosnia and Herzegovina. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN2222.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Czech Republic. Czechoslovakia. Bohemia. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN2240.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Slovakia. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN2282.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Liechtenstein. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN3112.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Andorra. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN3142.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Monaco. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN3971.5.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. German Democratic Republic, 1949–1990. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN4012.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Germany. Alsace-Lorraine. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN4032.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Germany. Anhalt. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN4089.H6	Political institutions and public administration. Germany. Baden. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN4139.5.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Germany. Baden-Württemberg. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.

J	JN4189.H6	Political institutions and public administration. Germany. Bavaria. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN4239.3.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Germany. Brandenburg. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN4239.5.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Germany. Brandenburg (State,1990-). Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN4252.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Germany. Bremen. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN4272.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Germany. Brunswick. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN4279.5.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Germany. Friesland. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN4292.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Germany. Hamburg. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN4299.5.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Germany. Hanover. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN4312.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Germany. Hesse. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN4332.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Germany. Lippe. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN4339.5.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Germany. Lower Saxony. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN4352.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Germany. Lubeck. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN4359.5.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Germany. Mainz. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.

J	JN4359.7.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Germany. Mecklenburg (State, 1990-). Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN4372.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Germany. Mecklenburg-Schwerin. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN4392.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Germany. Mecklenburg-Strelitz. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN4399.5.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Germany. Nassau. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN4399.7.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Germany. North Rhine- Westphalia. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN4412.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Germany. Oldenburg. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN4420.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Germany. Pomerania. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN4732.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Germany. Reuss (Younger Line). Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN4739.3.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Germany. Rhine Province. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN4739.5.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Germany. Rhineland-Palatinate. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN4739.7.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Germany. Ruhr Region. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN4739.8.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Germany. Saarland. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN4752.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Germany. Saxe-Altenburg. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.

J	JN4772.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Germany. Saxe-Meiningen. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN4832.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Germany. Saxony. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN4839.5.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Germany. Saxony (State, 1990-). Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN4839.7.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Germany. Saxony-Anhalt. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN4852.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Germany. Schaumburg-Lippe. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN4859.5.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Germany. Schleswig-Holstein. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN4872.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Germany. Schwarzburg- Rudolstadt. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN4892.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Germany. Schwarzburg- Sondershausen. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN4906.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Germany. Thuringia (1920- 1952). Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN4910.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Germany. Thuringia. (1990-). Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN4916.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Germany. Westphalia. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN4932.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Germany. Wurttemberg. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN4944.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Germany. Wurzburg. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.

J	JN5695.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. San Marino. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN5697.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Vatican City. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN5700.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Benelux Countries. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN6392.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Luxembourg. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN6549.H6	Political institutions and public administration. Soviet Union. Russia. Former Soviet Republics. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN6615.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Estonia. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN6636.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Ukraine. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN6646.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Belarus. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN6762.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Poland. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN6686.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Moldova. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN6696.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Russia (Federation). Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN6729.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Baltic States (General). Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN6736.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Latvia. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.

J	JN6745.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Lithuania. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN7376.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Greenland. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN7386.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Iceland. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN7396.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Finland. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN9112.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Switzerland. Aargau. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN9132.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Switzerland. Appenzell Inner Rhoden. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN9172.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Switzerland. Baseland. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN9192.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Switzerland. Basel-Stadt. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN9212.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Switzerland. Bern. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN9232.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Switzerland. Fribourg. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN9252.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Switzerland. Geneva. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN9272.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Switzerland. Glarus. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN9292.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Switzerland. Graubunden. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.

J	JN9299.5.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Switzerland. Jura. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN9312.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Switzerland. Lucerne. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN9332.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Switzerland. Neuchatel. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN9352.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Switzerland. St. Gall. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN9372.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Switzerland. Schaffhausen. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN9392.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Switzerland. Schwyz. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN9412.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Switzerland. Solothurn. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN9432.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Switzerland. Thurgau. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN9452.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Switzerland. Ticino. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN9472.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Switzerland. Unterwalden nid dem Wald. Nidwalden. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN9492.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Switzerland. Unterwalden nid dem Wald. Obwalden. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN9512.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Switzerland. Uri. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN9532.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Switzerland. Valais. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.

J	JN9552.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Switzerland. Vaud. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN9572.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Switzerland. Zug. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN9592.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Switzerland. Zurich. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN9606.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Bulgaria. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN9616.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Montenegro. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN9632.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Romania. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN9652.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Serbia. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN9672.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Yugoslavia. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN9679.5.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Macedonia. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JN9686.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Albania. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ98.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. South Asia (General). Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ249.H6	Political institutions and public administration. India (General). Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ332.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. India. Assam. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.

J	JQ379.5.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. India. West Bengal. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ412.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. India. Bombay (State). Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ372.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. India. Bengal. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ492.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. India. Madhya Pradesh. Central Provinces. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ532.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. India. Tamil Nadu. Madras. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ572.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. India. Punjab. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ612.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. India. Uttar Pradesh. United Provinces of Agra and Oudh. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ628.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Nepal. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ628.5.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Bhutan. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ629.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Pakistan. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ636.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Bangladesh. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ639.5.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Maldives. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ656.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Sri Lanka. Ceylon. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.

J	JQ750.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Southeast Asia. Indochina (General). Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ751.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Burma. Myanmar. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ772.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Indonesia. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ790.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Timor-Leste. East Timor. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ849.H6	Political institutions and public administration. Vietnam. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ936.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Cambodia. Kampuchea. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ956.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Laos. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ1062.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Malaysia. Malaya. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ1063.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Singapore. Executive branch.
J	JQ1064.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Brunei. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ1082.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Central Asia (General). Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ1090.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Kazakhstan. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ1092.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Kyrgyzstan. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ1093.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Tajikistan. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.

J	JQ1094.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Turkmenistan. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ1095.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Uzbekistan. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ1149.H6	Political institutions and public administration. Siberia (Russia). Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ1262.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Philippines (Spanish regime, to 1898). Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ1349.H6	Political institutions and public administration. Philippines (during United States rule, 1898–1946). Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ1412.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Philippines (Republic, 1946–). Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ1499.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. East Asia. Far East (General). Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ1512.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. China. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ1519.3.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Tibetan Government-in-Exile. Central Tibetan Administration-in-Exile. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ1519.5.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Macau. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ1532.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Taiwan. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ1539.5.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Hong Kong. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ1649.H6	Political institutions and public administration. Japan. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.

J	JQ1726.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Korea (including South Korea). Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ1729.5.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. North Korea. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ1730.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Mongolia. Outer Mongolia. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ1746.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Thailand. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ1758.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Middle East. Near East. Southwest Asia. Islamic Empire (General). Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ1759.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Caucasus (General). Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ1759.3.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Armenia. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ1759.5.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Azerbaijan. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ1759.7.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Georgia (Republic). Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ1766.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Afghanistan. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ1786.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Iran. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ1806.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Turkey. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ1811.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Cyprus. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.

J	JQ1826.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Syria. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ1828.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Lebanon. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ1830.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Israel. Palestine (including Gaza and West Bank). Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ1833.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Jordan. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ1841.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Saudi Arabia. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ1842.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Yemen. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ1843.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Oman. Muscat and Oman. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ1844.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. United Arab Emirates. Trucial States. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ1845.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Qatar. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ1846.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Bahrain. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ1848.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Kuwait. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ1849.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Iraq. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ1850.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Arab countries. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.

J	JQ1852.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Islamic countries. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ1876.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Africa (General). Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ1892.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. English-speaking Africa (General). Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ1949.H6	Political institutions and public administration. South Africa. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ2720.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Southern Africa. Central Africa (General). Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ2721.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Swaziland. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ2726.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Zimbabwe. Southern Rhodesia. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ2740.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Lesotho. Basutoland. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ2760.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Botswana. Bechuanaland. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ2786.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Rhodesia. Federation of Rhodesia and Nyasaland. British Central African Protectorate. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ2849.H6	Political institutions and public administration. Zambia. Northern Rhodesia. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ2941.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Malawi. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ2945.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. East Africa (General). Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.

J	JQ2947.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Kenya. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ2951.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Uganda. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ2998.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. West Africa (General). Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ3001.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. The Gambia. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ3032.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Ghana. Gold Coast. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ3092.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Nigeria. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ3121.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Sierra Leone. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ3158.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Indian Ocean islands (General). Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ3159.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Maldives. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ3172.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Mauritius. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ3185.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Seychelles. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ3188.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Kerguelen Islands. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ3198.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. North Africa (General). Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.

J	JQ3249.H6	Political institutions and public administration. Algeria. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ3332.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Tunisia. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ3346.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Libya. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ3362.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. French-speaking West Africa (General). Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ3376.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Benin. Dahomey. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ3381.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Guinea. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ3386.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Côte d'Ivoire. Ivory Coast. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ3389.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Mali. French Sudan. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ3391.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Mauritania. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ3394.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Niger. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ3396.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Senegal. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ3398.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Burkina Faso. Upper Volta. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ3403.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. French-speaking Equatorial Africa (General). Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.

J	JQ3404.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Central African Republic. Ubangi-Shari. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ3405.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Chad. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ3406.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Congo (Brazzaville). Middle Congo. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ3407.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Gabon. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ3421.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Djibouti. French Territory of the Afars and Issas. French Somaliland. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ3462.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Madagascar. Malagasy Republic. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ3486.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Reunion. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ3494.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Comoros. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ3495.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Mayotte. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ3506.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. German East Africa. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ3516.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Tanzania. Tanganyika. Zanzibar. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ3526.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Cameroon. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ3536.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Togo. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.

J	JQ3546.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Namibia. Southwest Africa. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ3566.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Burundi. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ3567.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Rwanda. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ3580.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Italian East Africa. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ3583.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Eritrea. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ3585.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Somalia. Italian Somaliland. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ3650.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Portuguese-speaking Africa. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ3651.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Angola. Portuguese West Africa. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ3661.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Cabo Verde. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ3671.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Mozambique. Portuguese East Africa. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ3681.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Guinea-Bissau. Portuguese Guinea. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ3685.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Sao Tome and Principe. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ3701.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Western Sahara. Spanish Sahara. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.

J	JQ3702.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Equatorial Guinea. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ3762.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Ethiopia. Abyssinia. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ3849.H6	Political institutions and public administration. Egypt. United Arab Republic. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ3926.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Liberia. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ3946.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Morocco. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ3980.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. South Sudan. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ3981.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Sudan. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ3981.5.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Atlantic Ocean islands (General). Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ3982.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Azores. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ3983.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Madeira Islands. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ3984.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Canary Islands. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ3986.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Saint Helena. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ3986.5.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Tristan da Cunha. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.

J	JQ3986.7.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Falkland Islands. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ3995.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Australasia. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ4049.H6	Political institutions and public administration. Australia (General). Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ4449.H6	Political institutions and public administration. Australia. Australian Capital Territory. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ4549.H6	Political institutions and public administration. Australia. New South Wales. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ4652.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Australia. Northern Territory. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ4749.H6	Political institutions and public administration. Australia. Queensland. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ4949.H6	Political institutions and public administration. Australia. South Australia. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ5149.H6	Political institutions and public administration. Australia. Tasmania. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ5349.H6	Political institutions and public administration. Australia. Victoria. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ5549.H6	Political institutions and public administration. Australia. Western Australia. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ5849.H6	Political institutions and public administration. New Zealand. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ6012.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Guam. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.

J	JQ6232.Z13H6	Political institutions and public administration. Samoan Islands. American Samoa. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ6240.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Trust Territory of the Pacific. Micronesia (Federated States). Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ6241.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Marshall Islands. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ6242.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Mariana Islands (including Northern Marianas). Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ6301.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Fiji. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ6311.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Papua New Guinea. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ6312.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Kiribati. Gilbert Islands. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ6313.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Tuvalu. Ellice Islands. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ6321.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Tonga. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ6340.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Cook Islands. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ6341.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Solomon Islands. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ6345.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Tokelau. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ6400.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Vanuatu. New Hebrides. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ6401.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. New Caledonia. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.

J	JQ6431.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. French Polynesia. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ6591.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Palau. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JQ6651.A69H6	Political institutions and public administration. Samoa. Western Samoa. Executive branch. Civil service. Special topics. Homosexual men and women.
J	JZ1253.2	International Relations. Relation to other disciplines and topics. Gender theory and feminist theory in international relations.
K - Law		
K	K3242.3	Comparative law. International uniform law Constitutional law. Human Rights. Civil and Political Rights. Gays.
K	K5196.S6	Comparative law. International uniform law. Criminal law and procedure. Criminal law. Individual crimes. Crimes against the person. Sex Crimes. Unnatural Sexual Intercourse. Special Offenses. Sodomy
K	KB529.7.H47	Religious Law in General. Comparative Religious Law. Jurisprudence. Interdisciplinary discussion of subjects. Persons. Hermaphrodites.
K	KB3082.A53	Religious Law in General. Comparative Religious Law. Jurisprudence. Interdisciplinary discussion of subjects. Public health. AIDS.
K	KB4172	Religious Law in General. Comparative Religious Law. Jurisprudence. Interdisciplinary discussion of subjects. Individual criminal offenses. Sodomy.
K	KBM496.9.H47	Jewish Law. Halakah. Sources. Rabbinic literature. Special topics. Hermaphroditism.
K	KBM529.7.H47	Jewish Law. Halakah. Mishpat Ivri. Natural persons. Personality, capacity and incapacity. Other types of natural persons. Hermaphrodites. Androgynos. Persons of uncertain gender.
K	KBM2467.G37	Jewish Law. Halakah. Mishpat Ivri. Constitutional law. Constitutional principles of the Jewish community. Equality before the law. Legal and social equality. Particular groups. Gays. Lesbians.
K	KBM3082.A53	Jewish Law. Halakah. Mishpat Ivri. Public Health. AIDS.
K	KBP3082.A53	Islamic law. Shari'ah. Furū' al-fiqh. Substantive law. Branches of law. Public health. AIDS.

K	KBP4216	Islamic law. Shari'ah. Furū' al-fiqh. Substantive law. Branches of law. Crimes and punishment. Offenses against sexual integrity. Sodomy.
K	KBR3774.S64	History of canon law. Penal (Criminal) law. De lege poenali. Individual offenses. De poenis in singula delicta. Sodomy.
K	KK1157	Law of Germany. Civil law. Bürgerliches Recht. Domestic relations. Family law. Familienrecht. Same-sex marriage (including quasi-marital relationships).
M - Music		
M	M1977.G38	Secular vocal music. Songs of specific groups or on specific topics. By topic A-Z. Collections. Gays.
M	M1978.G38	Secular vocal music. Songs of specific groups or on specific topics. By topic A-Z. Separate works. Gays.
M	ML102.G46	Literature on music. Dictionaries. Encyclopedias. By topic, A-Z. Gender in music.
M	ML156.4.G4	Literature on music. Bibliography. Discography. By topic, A-Z. Gay music.
N - Fine Arts		
N	N72.A34	Visual arts. Special topics. AIDS (Disease).
N	N72.H64	Visual arts. Special topics. Homosexuality.
N	N8012.G46	Christian art. Christian symbolism. Gender identity.
N	N8217.H67	Special subjects of art. Homosexuality.
N	N8217.G397	Special subjects of art. Gender identity
N	NA2543.H65	Architecture. Architecture in relation to special subjects. Architecture in relation to other subjects, A-Z. Homosexuality.
N	NC1849.G45	Posters. Special topics. Gender identity.
N	NX164.L47	Special classes of artists. Lesbians.
N	NX180.H6	The arts in relation to other subjects. Homosexuality.
N	NX650.G44	Arts in general. Special subjects or topics. Gender identity.
N	NX650.H6	Arts in general. Special subjects or topics. Homosexuality.

N	NX652.G38	Characters, persons, classes of persons, and ethnic groups. Gay artists. Lesbian artists.
P - Language and Literature		
P	P94.5.G38-.G382	Philology. Linguistics. Communication. Mass media. Special aspects. Relation to special groups of people, A-Z. Gays.
P	P94.5.S49-.S492	Philology. Linguistics. Communication. Mass media. Special aspects. Relation to special groups of people, A-Z. Sexual minorities.
P	P94.5.T73-.T732	Philology. Linguistics. Communication. Mass media. Special aspects. Relation to special groups of people, A-Z. Transgender people.
P	P96.A39-.A392	Philology. Linguistics. Communication. Mass media. Special aspects. Other, A-Z. AIDS (Disease)
P	P96.G44-.G442	Philology. Linguistics. Communication. Mass media. Special aspects. Other, A-Z. Gender identity.
P	P96.H63-.H632	Philology. Linguistics. Communication. Mass media. Special aspects. Other, A-Z. Homosexuality.
P	P96.S5-.S52	Philology. Linguistics. Communication. Mass media. Special aspects. Other, A-Z. Sex roles.
P	P96.S58-.S582	Philology. Linguistics. Communication. Mass media. Special aspects. Other, A-Z. Sexual minorities.
P	P120.H57	Philology. Linguistics. Language. Linguistic theory. Comparative grammar. Philosophy, origin, etc. of language. Other aspects, A-Z. Hispanic American sexual minorities.
P	PA3015.H58	Classical literature. Literary history. Knowledge, treatment, and conception of special subjects, A-Z. Homosexuality.
P	PA3624.H64	Greek literature. Translations. English. Poetry. By subject, A-Z. Homosexuality, Male.
P	PA4408-4409	Greek literature. Individual authors to 600 A.D. Sappho.
P	PA8030.H66	Medieval and modern Latin literature. History and criticism. Special topics, A-Z. Homosexuality.
P	PC4977.G39	Romance philology and languages. Spanish. Language. Linguistic geography. Dialects, etc. Slang. Argot. Special classes. Special groups of persons. Other, A-Z. Gays.
P	PE1127.S4	English philology and language. Modern English. Language. Grammar. Readers. Readers on special subjects, A-Z. Sex role.
P	PE1599.H65	English philology and language. Modern English. Language. Lexicology. Etymology. Particular words, A-Z. "Homo".
P	PE3727.G39	English language. Slang argot. Vulgarisms. Special groups of persons. Gay men.

P	PG1412.6.G46	Slavic. Baltic. Albanian. Serbo-Croatian literature. History. Prose. Special topics, A-Z. Gender identity.
P	PG3205.H65	Slavic. Baltic. Albanian. Russian literature. Collections of Russian literature. Special topics, A-Z. Homosexuality. Gays.
P	PG5006.3.G46	Slavic. Baltic. Albanian. Czech. Literature. History. 19th century. Special topics, A-Z. Gender identity.
P	PG7053.H66	Slavic. Baltic. Albanian. Polish. Literature. History. By period. 19th-20th centuries. Special topics, A-Z. Homosexuality.
P	PG7102.G45	Slavic. Baltic. Albanian. Polish. Literature. History. Prose. Special topics, A-Z. Gender identity.
P	PG7148.A36	Slavic. Baltic. Albanian. Polish. Literature. Collections. Prose. Special. By form or subject, A-Z. AIDS (Disease).
P	PJ5030.H65	Oriental philology and literature. Hebrew. Literature. Literary history and criticism. History. Special forms. Prose. Fiction. Special topics, A-Z. Homosexuality.
P	PJ7542.H6	Oriental philology and literature. Arabic literature. History and criticism. Special forms. Poetry. Special topics, A-Z. Homosexuality.
P	PJ7632.H6	Oriental philology and literature. Arabic literature. Collections. Special forms. Poetry. Special topics, A-Z. Homosexuality.
P	PL210.S36	Languages of Eastern Asia, Africa, Oceania. Ural-Altaic languages. Turkic languages. Southwestern (Oghuz) group. Turkish (Osmanic or Ottoman). Literature .History and criticism. History. Treatment of special subjects, classes, etc., A-Z. Sexual orientation.
P	PL721.G44	Languages of Eastern Asia, Africa, Oceania. Japanese language and literature. Japanese literature. History and criticism. History. Special aspects and topics. Special topics, A-Z. Gender identity.
P	PL721.H59	Languages of Eastern Asia, Africa, Oceania. Japanese language and literature. Japanese literature. History and criticism. History. Special aspects and topics. Special topics, A-Z. Homosexuality.
P	PL721.S515	Languages of Eastern Asia, Africa, Oceania. Japanese language and literature. Japanese literature. History and criticism. History. Special aspects and topics. Special topics, A-Z. Sex differences.
P	PL722.L47	Languages of Eastern Asia, Africa, Oceania. Japanese language and literature. Japanese literature. History and criticism. History. Special aspects and topics. Treatment of special classes, races, etc., A-Z. Lesbians.
P	PL957.5.S48	Languages of Eastern Asia, Africa, Oceanic. Korean language and literature. Korean literature. History and criticism. History. Special aspects and topics. Treatment of special subjects, A-Z. Sex. Sex role.

P	PL957.5.S49	Languages of Eastern Asia, Africa, Oceanic. Korean language and literature. Korean literature. History and criticism. History. Special aspects and topics. Treatment of special subjects, A-Z. Sexual minorities.
P	PN56.G45	Literature (General). Theory. Philosophy. Esthetics. Relation to and treatment of special elements, problems, and subjects. Other special. Topics, A-Z. Gender identity.
P	PN56.H57	Literature (General). Theory. Philosophy. Esthetics. Relation to and treatment of special elements, problems, and subjects. Other special. Topics, A-Z. Homosexuality (including male homosexuality).
P	PN56.L45	Literature (General). Theory. Philosophy. Esthetics. Relation to and treatment of special elements, problems, and subjects. Other special. Topics, A-Z. Lesbianism.
P	PN56.S52	Literature (General). Theory. Philosophy. Esthetics. Relation to and treatment of special elements, problems, and subjects. Other special. Topics, A-Z. Sex differences.
P	PN56.T683	Literature (General). Theory. Philosophy. Esthetics. Relation to and treatment of special elements, problems, and subjects. Other special. Topics, A-Z. Transgender people.
P	PN56.T69	Literature (General). Theory. Philosophy. Esthetics. Relation to and treatment of special elements, problems, and subjects. Other special. Topics, A-Z. Transvestism. Cross-dressing.
P	PN491.3	Literature (General). Literary history. Biography. Other classes of authors. Gay authors.
P	PN682.H65	Literature (General). Literary history. Medieval (to 1500). Special topics, A-Z. Homosexuality.
P	PN682.S37	Literature (General). Literary history. Medieval (to 1500). Special topics, A-Z. Sex. Sex role.
P	PN682.S38	Literature (General). Literary history. Medieval (to 1500). Special topics, A-Z. Sexual deviation.
P	PN1009.5.S48	Literature (General). Literary history. Juvenile literature. Special topics, A-Z. Sexism. Sex role.
P	PN1009.5.S483	Literature (General). Literary history. Juvenile literature. Special topics, A-Z. Sexual minorities.
P	PN1083.H66	Literature (General). Poetry. Relations to, and treatment of, special subjects. Other special, A-Z. Homosexuality.
P	PN1590.G39	The performing arts. Show business. Special topics, A-Z. Gays.
P	PN1650.H66	Drama. Philosophy, aesthetics, scope, relations, etc. Relation to, and treatment of, special subjects. Other special, A-Z. Homosexuality.

P	PN1650.S48	Drama. Philosophy, aesthetics, scope, relations, etc. Relation to, and treatment of, special subjects. Other special, A-Z. Sex role.
P	PN1990.9.H64	Drama. Broadcasting. Special topics, A-Z. Homosexuality. Gays.
P	PN1991.8.S46	Drama. Broadcasting. Radio broadcasts. Special topics. Other special topics, A-Z. Sex role.
P	PN1992.8.G39	Drama. Broadcasting. Television broadcasts. Special topics. Other special topics, A-Z. Gay men.
P	PN1992.8.G46	Drama. Broadcasting. Television broadcasts. Special topics. Other special topics, A-Z. Gender nonconformity.
P	PN1992.8.H64	Drama. Broadcasting. Television broadcasts. Special topics. Other special topics, A-Z. Homosexuality.
P	PN1992.8.L47	Drama. Broadcasting. Television broadcasts. Special topics. Other special topics, A-Z. Lesbianism.
P	PN1992.8.S44	Drama. Broadcasting. Television broadcasts. Special topics. Other special topics, A-Z. Sex role.
P	PN1992.8.S45	Drama. Broadcasting. Television broadcasts. Special topics. Other special topics, A-Z. Sexual minorities.
P	PN1993.44.G39	Drama. Motion pictures. Museums, archives, exhibitions, festivals, etc. Special topics, A-Z. Gay and lesbian film festivals.
P	PN1995.9.A435	Drama. Motion pictures. Other special topics, A-Z. AIDS (Disease).
P	PN1995.9.B57	Drama. Motion pictures. Other special topics, A-Z. Bisexuality.
P	PN1995.9.G35	Drama. Motion pictures. Other special topics, A-Z. Gay pornographic films.
P	PN1995.9.H55	Drama. Motion pictures. Other special topics, A-Z. Homosexuality (including male homosexuality). [Gay men points here]
P	PN1995.9.L48	Drama. Motion pictures. Other special topics, A-Z. Lesbianism.
P	PN1995.9.S47	Drama. Motion pictures. Other special topics, A-Z. Sex role. [Gender points here]
P	PN1995.9.T684	Drama. Motion pictures. Other special topics, A-Z. Transgender people.
P	PN1995.9.T69	Drama. Motion pictures. Other special topics, A-Z. Transvestism. Cross-dressing.
P	PN2270.G39	Drama. Dramatic representation. The theater. Special regions or countries. America. North America. United States. History. By period. Twentieth century. Other special topics, A-Z. Gay theater.
P	PN2270.L47	Drama. Dramatic representation. The theater. Special regions or countries. America. North America. United States. History. By period. Twentieth century. Other special topics, A-Z. Lesbian theater.

P	PN2286.5	Drama. Dramatic representation. The theater. Special regions or countries. America. North America. United States. Biography. Collective. Gays.
P	PN3352.A52	Prose. Prose. Prose fiction. Philosophy, theory, etc. Relation to and treatment of special subjects. Other special, A-Z. AIDS (Disease).
P	PN3352.H65	Prose. Prose. Prose fiction. Philosophy, theory, etc. Relation to and treatment of special subjects. Other special, A-Z. Homosexuality.
P	PN3426.T73	Prose. Prose. Prose fiction. Special topics. Special races, classes, types, etc., in fiction.. Other, A-Z. Transvestites. Cross-dressers.
P	PN4888.G38	Journalism. Journalism. The periodical press, etc. By region or country. America. North America. United States. Special topics. Other special topics, A-Z. Gay parents (including children of gay parents). [Children of gay parents points here]
P	PN4888.H65	Journalism. Journalism. The periodical press, etc. By region or country. America. North America. United States. Special topics. Other special topics, A-Z. Homophobia.
P	PN4888.H66	Journalism. Journalism. The periodical press, etc. By region or country. America. North America. United States. Special topics. Other special topics, A-Z. Homosexuality.
P	PN4914.A44	Journalism. Journalism. The periodical press, etc. By region or country. Canada. Special topics, A-Z. AIDS (Disease).
P	PN4914.H55	Journalism. Journalism. The periodical press, etc. By region or country. Canada. Special topics, A-Z. Homosexuality.
P	PN4974.A44	Journalism. Journalism. The periodical press, etc. By region or country. Latin America. Mexico. Special topics, A-Z. AIDS (Disease).
P	PN4974.H55	Journalism. Journalism. The periodical press, etc. By region or country. Latin America. Mexico. Special topics, A-Z. Homosexuality.
P	PN5124.A44	Journalism. Journalism. The periodical press, etc. By region or country. Europe. Great Britain. England. Special topics, A-Z. AIDS (Disease).
P	PN5124.H55	Journalism. Journalism. The periodical press, etc. By region or country. Europe. Great Britain. England. Special topics, A-Z. Homosexuality.
P	PN5184.A44	Journalism. Journalism. The periodical press, etc. By region or country. Europe. France. Special topics, A-Z. AIDS (Disease).
P	PN5184.H55	Journalism. Journalism. The periodical press, etc. By region or country. Europe. France. Special topics, A-Z. Homosexuality.

P	PN5214.A44	Journalism. Journalism. The periodical press, etc. By region or country. Europe. Germany. Special topics, A-Z. AIDS (Disease).
P	PN5214.H55	Journalism. Journalism. The periodical press, etc. By region or country. Europe. Germany. Special topics, A-Z. Homosexuality.
P	PN6071.H724	Collections of general literature. Collections, extracts, etc. By subject, A-Z. Homosexuality.
P	PN6071.L47	Collections of general literature. Collections, extracts, etc. By subject, A-Z. Lesbians.
P	PN6084.G35	Collections of general literature. Quotations. English. Special topics, A-Z. Gays.
P	PN6084.L45	Collections of general literature. Quotations. English. Special topics, A-Z. Lesbians.
P	PN6109.95.A75	Collections of general literature. Poetry. Special categories of authors. Other special groups, A-Z. Asexual people.
P	PN6110.H65	Collections of general literature. Poetry. Special. By subject or form, A-Z. Homosexuality.
P	PN6120.G34	Collections of general literature. Drama. Special. By subject or form, A-Z. Gay men.
P	PN6231.H57	Collections of general literature. Wit and humor. Collections on special topics, A-Z. Homosexuality.
P	PN6231.L43	Collections of general literature. Wit and humor. Collections on special topics, A-Z. Lesbians.
P	PN6231.S542	Collections of general literature. Wit and humor. Collections on special topics, A-Z. Sex differences.
P	PQ145.1.H66	French literature. Literary history and criticism. History of French literature. Special subjects, classes, etc., not limited to one period or form. A-N. Homosexuality.
P	PQ155.L47	French literature. Literary history and criticism. History of French literature. By period. Medieval. Old French. Special subjects, A-Z. Lesbians.
P	PQ155.S48	French literature. Literary history and criticism. History of French literature. By period. Medieval. Old French. Special subjects, A-Z. Sex. Sex role. Gender identity.
P	PQ295.H65	French literature. Literary history and criticism. History of French literature. By period. Modern. 19th century, ca. 1789-1900. 1850/70-1900. Special topics, A-Z. Homosexuals.
P	PQ307.A52	French literature. Literary history and criticism. History of French literature. By period. Modern. 20th century. Special topics, A-Z. AIDS.
P	PQ307.G35	French literature. Literary history and criticism. History of French literature. By period. Modern. 20th century. Special topics, A-Z. Gender identity.

P	PQ307.H6	French literature. Literary history and criticism. History of French literature. By period. Modern. 20th century. Special topics, A-Z. Homosexuals.
P	PQ307.L48	French literature. Literary history and criticism. History of French literature. By period. Modern. 20th century. Special topics, A-Z. Lesbianism.
P	PQ637.G35	French literature. Literary history and criticism. History of French literature. Prose and prose fiction. Special. Prose fiction. Special topics, A-Z. Gender identity.
P	PQ637.H65	French literature. Literary history and criticism. History of French literature. Prose and prose fiction. Special. Prose fiction. Special topics, A-Z. Homosexuality.
P	PQ4181.H65	Italian literature. Literary history and criticism. Prose. Special. Prose fiction. Special forms and topics, A-Z. Homosexuality.
P	PQ4203.5.H65	Italian literature. Collections of Italian literature. Special classes of authors, A-Z. Homosexuals, Male.
P	PQ4209.5.H65	Italian literature. Collections of Italian literature. Poetry (General and lyric). Special classes of authors. Other, A-Z. Homosexuals.
P	PQ4249.6.G39	Italian literature. Collections of Italian literature. Prose. By subject, A-Z. Gays.
P	PQ6073.H65	Spanish literature. Literary history and criticism. History of Spanish literature. By period. Modern. 19th-20th centuries. Special topics, A-Z. Homosexuality.
P	PQ6073.L47	Spanish literature. Literary history and criticism. History of Spanish literature. By period. Modern. 19th-20th centuries. Special topics, A-Z. Lesbians.
P	PQ6140.H64	Spanish literature. Literary history and criticism. History of Spanish literature. General. Prose fiction. General works. Special topics, A-Z. Homosexuality.
P	PQ6208.H65	Spanish literature. Collections of Spanish literature. Poetry. By subject, A-Z. Homosexuality.
P	PR120.G38	English literature. History of English literature. Special classes of authors. Other classes of authors, A-Z. Gays.
P	PR120.L45	English literature. History of English literature. Special classes of authors. Other classes of authors, A-Z. Lesbians.
P	PR149.G46	English literature. History of English literature. Special topics not limited to, or identified with, one period or form. Treatment of special subjects. Other, A-Z. Gender identity.
P	PR149.L47	English literature. History of English literature. Special topics not limited to, or identified with, one period or form. Treatment of special subjects. Other, A-Z. Lesbianism.

P	PR179.H65	English literature. History of English literature. By period. Anglo-Saxon (Beginnings through 1066). Special topics, A-Z. Homosexuality.
P	PR275.G44	English literature. History of English literature. By period. Medieval. Middle English (1066–1500). Special topics, A-Z. Gender identity.
P	PR275.S49	English literature. History of English literature. By period. Medieval. Middle English (1066–1500). Special topics, A-Z. Sex differences.
P	PR408.H65	English literature. History of English literature. By period. Modern. General. Special topics, A-Z. Homosexuality.
P	PR408.H65	English literature. History of English literature. By period. Modern. General. Special topics, A-Z. Sex role.
P	PR418.T75	English literature. History of English literature. By period. Modern. Renaissance and Reformation. 16th century. Special topics, A-Z. Transgender people.
P	PR428.G43	English literature. History of English literature. By period. Modern. Elizabethan era (1550–1640). Other special topics, A-Z. Gender identity.
P	PR428.H66	English literature. History of English literature. By period. Modern. Elizabethan era (1550–1640). Other special topics, A-Z. Homosexuality.
P	PR448.H65	English literature. History of English literature. By period. Modern. 18th century. Special topics, A-Z. Homosexuality.
P	PR448.S45	English literature. History of English literature. By period. Modern. 18th century. Special topics, A-Z. Sex differences.
P	PR468.H65	English literature. History of English literature. By period. Modern. 19th century. Special topics, A-Z. Homosexuality.
P	PR478.H65	English literature. History of English literature. By period. Modern. 20th century. Special topics, A-Z. Homosexuality.
P	PR508.H6	English literature. History of English literature. Poetry. Special topics. Other, A-Z. Homosexuality.
P	PR525.H65	English literature. History of English literature. Poetry. By period. 15th-16th centuries (1485-1550). Special topics, A-Z. Homosexuality, Male.
P	PR535.H65	English literature. History of English literature. Poetry. By period. Elizabethan era (1550– 1640). Special topics, A-Z. Homosexuality, Male.
P	PR545.H65	English literature. History of English literature. Poetry. By period. 17th century. General. Special topics, A-Z. Homosexuality, Male.

P	PR555.H65	English literature. History of English literature. Poetry. By period. 18th century. General. Special topics, A-Z. Homosexuality, Male.
P	PR565.H65	English literature. History of English literature. Poetry. By period. Restoration and Augustan era (1660-1750). Special topics, A-Z. Homosexuality, Male.
P	PR575.H65	English literature. History of English literature. Poetry. By period. 18th century. Romanticism. Return to nature (1750-1830). Special topics, A-Z. Homosexuality, Male.
P	PR585.H65	English literature. History of English literature. Poetry. By period. 19th century. General. Special topics, A-Z. Homosexuality, Male.
P	PR595.H65	English literature. History of English literature. Poetry. By period. 19th century. Victorian era. General. Special topics, A-Z. Homosexuality, Male.
P	PR605.H65	English literature. History of English literature. Poetry. By period. 20th century. General. Special topics, A-Z. Homosexuality, Male.
P	PR635.H65	English literature. History of English literature. Drama. Special topics and forms. Other, A-Z. Homosexuality
P	PR658.H58	English literature. History of English literature. Drama. By period. Elizabethan era (1550- 1640). Special topics, A-Z. Homosexuality, Male.
P	PR678.H58	English literature. History of English literature. Drama. By period. 17th century. General. Special topics, A-Z. Homosexuality, Male.
P	PR698.H58	English literature. History of English literature. Drama. By period. Restoration (1660-1700). Special topics, A-Z. Homosexuality, Male.
P	PR708.H58	English literature. History of English literature. Drama. By period. 18th century. General. Special topics, A-Z. Homosexuality, Male.
P	PR728.H58	English literature. History of English literature. Drama. By period. 19th century. General. Special topics, A-Z. Homosexuality, Male.
P	PR739.H65	English literature. History of English literature. Drama. By period. 20th century. Special topics, A-Z. Homosexuality.
P	PR739.S45	English literature. History of English literature. Drama. By period. 20th century. Special topics, A-Z. Sex role.
P	PR830.G34	English literature. History of English literature. Prose. By form. Prose fiction. The novel. Special topics. Other special topics, A-Z. Gay men.
P	PR830.G35	English literature. History of English literature. Prose. By form. Prose fiction. The novel. Special topics. Other special topics, A-Z. Gender identity.

P	PR830.H67	English literature. History of English literature. Prose. By form. Prose fiction. The novel. Special topics. Other special topics, A-Z. Homosexuality.
P	PR830.L46	English literature. History of English literature. Prose. By form. Prose fiction. The novel. Special topics. Other special topics, A-Z. Lesbians.
P	PR1110.G39	English literature. Collections of English literature. General collections. Special classes of authors, A-Z. Gays.
P	PR1111.H57	English literature. Collections of English literature. General collections. Special topics (prose and verse), A-Z. Homosexuality.
P	PR1178.G39	English literature. Collections of English literature. Poetry. Special classes of authors, A-Z. Gay men.
P	PR1195.A44	English literature. Collections of English literature. Poetry. Special forms and subjects. Other special. By subjects or class, A-Z. AIDS (Disease).
P	PR1195.H58	English literature. Collections of English literature. Poetry. Special forms and subjects. Other special. By subjects or class, A-Z. Homosexuality.
P	PR1259.H65	English literature. Collections of English literature. Drama. Special. Other, A-Z. Homosexuality.
P	PR1259.L47	English literature. Collections of English literature. Drama. Special. Other, A-Z. Lesbianism.
P	PR1309.H57	English literature. Collections of English literature. Prose (General). Special subjects and forms, A-Z. Homosexuality.
P	PR1309.L47	English literature. Collections of English literature. Prose (General). Special subjects and forms, A-Z. Lesbianism.
P	PR1875.H66	English literature. Anglo-Norman period. Early English. Middle English. Individual authors and works. Chaucer, Geoffrey. Separate works. Canterbury tales. Criticism. Special topics, A-Z. Homosexuality.
P	PR1933.S35	English literature. Anglo-Norman period. Early English. Middle English. Individual authors and works. Chaucer, Geoffrey. Criticism and interpretation. Treatment and knowledge of special subjects, A-Z. Sex. Sex role.
P	PR3069.S45	English literature. English renaissance (1500-1640). The drama. Individual authors. Shakespeare, William. Criticism and interpretation. Treatment and knowledge of special subjects. Other special subjects, A-Z. Sex role.
P	PS153.G38	American literature. History of American literature. Special classes of authors. Other classes of authors, A-Z. Gays.
P	PS153.L46	American literature. History of American literature. Special classes of authors. Other classes of authors, A-Z. Lesbians.

P	PS153.S39	American literature. History of American literature. Special classes of authors. Other classes of authors, A-Z. Sexual minorities (General).
P	PS169.G45	American literature. History of American literature. Treatment of special subjects. Other, A-Z. Gender identity.
P	PS169.H65	American literature. History of American literature. Treatment of special subjects. Other, A-Z. Homosexuality.
P	PS217.H65	American literature. History of American literature. By period. 19th century. Special topics, A-Z. Homosexuality.
P	PS228.G38	American literature. History of American literature. By period. 20th century. Special topics, A-Z. Gay culture.
P	PS228.L47	American literature. History of American literature. By period. 20th century. Special topics, A-Z. Lesbianism.
P	PS310.H66	American literature. History of American literature. Special forms. Poetry. Special topics, A-Z. Homosexuality.
P	PS310.S44	American literature. History of American literature. Special forms. Poetry. Special topics, A-Z. Sex. Sex role.
P	PS338.H66	American literature. History of American literature. Special forms. Drama. Special topics, A-Z. Homosexuality.
P	PS366.P37	American literature. History of American literature. Special forms. Prose. Special topics. Passing (Identity).
P	PS374.H63	American literature. History of American literature. Special forms. Prose. Prose fiction. Special forms and topics, A-Z. Homosexuality.
P	PS374.S46	American literature. History of American literature. Special forms. Prose. Prose fiction. Special forms and topics, A-Z. Sex role.
P	PS508.G39	American literature. Collections of American literature. Special classes of authors, A-Z. Gays.
P	PS508.L47	American literature. Collections of American literature. Special classes of authors, A-Z. Lesbian authors.
P	PS508.S49	American literature. Collections of American literature. Special classes of authors, A-Z. Sexual minorities.
P	PS508.T73	American literature. Collections of American literature. Special classes of authors, A-Z. Transsexuals.
P	PS509.H57	American literature. Collections of American literature. Special topics (Prose and verse), A-Z. Homosexuality.
P	PS509.L47	American literature. Collections of American literature. Special topics (Prose and verse), A-Z. Lesbianism.
P	PS591.G38	American literature. Collections of American literature. Poetry. Special. Special groups of authors, A-Z. Gay authors.
P	PS591.L47	American literature. Collections of American literature. Poetry. Special. Special groups of authors, A-Z. Lesbians.

P	PS591.S47	American literature. Collections of American literature. Poetry. Special. Special groups of authors, A-Z. Sexual minorities.
P	PS595.H65	American literature. Collections of American literature. Poetry. Special. By subject, A-Z. Homosexuality.
P	PS595.L46	American literature. Collections of American literature. Poetry. Special. By subject, A-Z. Lesbianism.
P	PS595.S76	American literature. Collections of American literature. Poetry. Special. By subject, A-Z. Sodomy.
P	PS627.H67	American literature. Collections of American literature. Drama. Special forms and topics, A-Z. Homosexuality.
P	PS627.L48	American literature. Collections of American literature. Drama. Special forms and topics, A-Z. Lesbians.
P	PS647.G39	American literature. Collections of American literature. Prose (General). Special classes of authors, A-Z. Gays.
P	PS648.B57	American literature. Collections of American literature. Prose (General). Special forms and topics, A-Z. Bisexuality.
P	PS648.H57	American literature. Collections of American literature. Prose (General). Special forms and topics, A-Z. Homosexuality.
P	PS648.L47	American literature. Collections of American literature. Prose (General). Special forms and topics, A-Z. Lesbianism.
P	PS648.T72	American literature. Collections of American literature. Prose (General). Special forms and topics, A-Z. Transgender people.
P	PS3242.H56	American literature. Individual authors. 19th century. Whitman, Walt. Criticism and interpretation. Treatment and knowledge of special subjects, A-Z. Homosexuality.
P	PT134.H73	German literature. History of German literature. Special subjects not limited to one period or form, A-L. Homosexuality.
P	PT1340.G39	German literature. Collections of German literature. Prose Fiction. Short stories. "Novellen." Special forms, subjects, etc., A-Z. Gay men.
P	PT1340.Q44	German literature. Collections of German literature. Prose Fiction. Short stories. "Novellen." Special forms, subjects, etc., A-Z. Queer fiction.
P	PT2200.H65	German literature. Individual authors or works. 1700-ca. 1860/70. Goethe, Johann Wolfgang von, 1749-1832. Biography and criticism. Criticism and interpretation. Relation to special subjects. Sociology. Special, A-Z. Homosexuality.
P	PT5085.H6	Dutch literature. Literary history and criticism. History of Dutch literature. Treatment of special subjects. Special topics, A-Z. Homosexuality.
P	PT7073.L47	Scandinavian literature. Literary history and criticism. History of Scandinavian literature. Special topics, A-Z. Lesbianism.

P	PT7762.H65	Danish literature. Literary history and criticism. History of Danish literature. Special periods. 20th century. Special topics, A-Z. Homosexuality.
P	PT8437.H65	Norwegian literature. Literary history and criticism. History of Norwegian literature. Special periods. 19th century. Special subjects, A-Z. Homosexuality.
Q - Science		
Q	QP81.6	Physiology. Phenomena of animal life (General). Sexual orientation. Homosexuality.
Q	QR189.5.A33	Immunology. Vaccines. By disease or type. AIDS (Disease).
Q	QR201.A37	Immunology. Pathogenic microorganisms. By disease. AIDS (Disease). HIV infections.
R - Medicine		
R	RA564.87	Public health. Hygiene. Preventive medicine. By age group, class, etc. Women. Lesbians.
R	RA564.9.H65	Public health. Hygiene. Preventive medicine. By age group, class, etc. Homosexuals.
R	RA564.87	Public health. Hygiene. Preventive medicine. By age group, class, etc. Sexual minorities.
R	RA564.9.T73	Public health. Hygiene. Preventive medicine. By age group, class, etc. Transsexuals.
R	RA643.75-643.86	Public health. Hygiene. Preventive medicine. Communicable diseases and public health. AIDS. HIV infections.
R	RA644.A25	Public health. Hygiene. Preventive medicine. AIDS. HIV infections.
R	RA778.2	Public health. Hygiene. Preventive medicine. Personal health and hygiene. Personal health and grooming guides for classes of people. Women. Lesbians.
R	RC200.7.G38	Internal medicine. Infectious and parasitic diseases. Individual diseases. Sexually transmitted diseases. Venereal diseases. By age group, class, etc. Gay men.
R	RC440.84	Internal medicine. Neurosciences. Biological psychiatry. Neuropsychiatry. Psychiatry. Psychiatry as a profession. Gay psychiatrists. Gay psychotherapists. Lesbian psychiatrists. Lesbian psychotherapists.
R	RC451.4.B57	Internal medicine. Neurosciences. Biological psychiatry. Neuropsychiatry. Psychiatry. By age group, profession, etc. Bisexuals.
R	RC451.4.G39	Internal medicine. Neurosciences. Biological psychiatry. Neuropsychiatry. Psychiatry. By age group, profession, etc. Gay men and lesbians.

R	RC451.4.S52	Internal medicine. Neurosciences. Biological psychiatry. Neuropsychiatry. Psychiatry. By age group, profession, etc. Sexual minorities.
R	RC451.4.T725	Internal medicine. Neurosciences. Biological psychiatry. Neuropsychiatry. Psychiatry. By age group, profession, etc. Transgender people.
R	RC455.4.S45	Internal medicine. Neurosciences. Biological psychiatry. Neuropsychiatry. Psychiatry. Special aspects of mental illness. Sex-role aspects of mental illness. Gender role.
R	RC552.A45	Internal medicine. Neurosciences. Biological psychiatry. Neuropsychiatry. Psychiatry. Neuroses. Other neuroses, A-Z. AIDS phobia.
R	RC558-558.5	Internal medicine. Neurosciences. Biological psychiatry. Neuropsychiatry. Psychiatry. Psychiatric aspects of personality and behavior conditions. Sexual and psychosexual conditions. Homosexuality. General works. (Class here works on the psychiatric issues associated with homosexuality).
R	RC558.3	Internal medicine. Neurosciences. Biological psychiatry. Neuropsychiatry. Psychiatry. Psychiatric aspects of personality and behavior conditions. Sexual and psychosexual conditions. Homosexuality. Male homosexuality.
R	RC558.5	Internal medicine. Neurosciences. Biological psychiatry. Neuropsychiatry. Psychiatry. Psychiatric aspects of personality and behavior conditions. Sexual and psychosexual conditions. Homosexuality. Female homosexuality. Lesbianism.
R	RC560.B56	Internal medicine. Neurosciences. Biological psychiatry. Neuropsychiatry. Psychiatry. Psychiatric aspects of personality and behavior conditions. Sexual and psychosexual conditions. Other special problems, A-Z. Bisexuality.
R	RC560.C4	Internal medicine. Neurosciences. Biological psychiatry. Neuropsychiatry. Psychiatry. Psychiatric aspects of personality and behavior conditions. Sexual and psychosexual conditions. Other special problems, A-Z. Change of sex. Transsexualism.
R	RC560.G45	Internal medicine. Neurosciences. Biological psychiatry. Neuropsychiatry. Psychiatry. Psychiatric aspects of personality and behavior conditions. Sexual and psychosexual conditions. Other special problems, A-Z. Gender dysphoria. Gender identity disorders. Transsexualism.
R	RC564.5.G39	Internal medicine. Neurosciences. Biological psychiatry. Neuropsychiatry. Psychiatry. Psychiatric aspects of personality and behavior conditions. Drug abuse. Substance abuse. By age group, profession, etc. Gay men and lesbians.
R	RC606.5-606.7	Internal medicine. Specialties of internal medicine. Immunologic diseases. Immunodeficiency. AIDS. HIV infections.
R	RC607.A26	Specialties of internal medicine. Immunologic diseases. Immunodeficiency. Individual diseases, A-Z. AIDS

R	RD54.3.H58	Surgery. Surgical care in special medical conditions, emergencies, and the at- risk patient. Special conditions, A-Z. HIV patients. AIDS patients.
R	RF511.T73	Otorhinolaryngology. Laryngology. Diseases of the throat. Diseases of the larynx, vocal cords, epiglottis, and trachea. By age group, class, etc., A-Z. Transsexuals.
R	RG580.A44	Gynecology and obstetrics. Obstetrics. Pregnancy. Diseases and conditions in pregnancy. Other diseases and conditions in pregnancy, A-Z. AIDS (Disease).
R	RJ101.3	Pediatrics. Child health. Child health services. Preventive health services for children. By class, etc. Gay and lesbian teenagers.
R	RJ387.A25	Pediatrics. Diseases of children. Immunologic disease. Other diseases, A-Z. AIDS.
R	RJ506.G35	Pediatrics. Diseases of children. Mental disorders of children and adolescents. Child psychiatry. Child mental health services. Specific disorders, A-Z. Gender dysphoria. Gender identity disorders
R	RK55.H58	Dentistry. By age group, class, etc., A-Z. HIV patients. AIDS patients.
R	RT82.9	Nursing. Nursing as a profession. Gay nurses. Lesbian nurses.
R	RX226.A35	Homeopathy. Diseases, injuries, treatment, etc. Diseases due to specific infections. Individual diseases, A-Z. AIDS.
T - Technology		
T	TR681.A38	Photography. Artistic photography. Portraits. Special classes of persons. AIDS patients.
T	TR681.H65	Photography. Artistic photography. Portraits. Special classes of persons. Homosexuals.
T	TR681.S44	Photography. Artistic photography. Portraits. Special classes of persons. Sexual minorities.
T	TR681.T68	Photography. Artistic photography. Portraits. Special classes of persons. Transgender people.
T	TR681.T7	Photography. Artistic photography. Portraits. Special classes of persons. Transvestites. Cross-dressers
U - Military Science		
U	UB418.G38	Military administration. Minorities, women, etc. in armed forces. By region or country. United States. Individual groups. Gays.
U	UB418.T72	Military administration. Minorities, women, etc. in armed forces. By region or country. United States. Individual groups. Transgender people.

V - Naval Science		
V	VB324.G38	Naval administration.Minorities, women, etc. in navies. By region or country. United States. Individual groups. Gays.
Z - Bibliography, Library Science		
Z	Z675.L48	Libraries. Library science. Information science. Classes of libraries, A-Z.. Lesbian libraries.
Z	Z682.4.G39	Libraries. Library science. Information science. Personnel. Special groups, A-Z. Gay men and lesbians.
Z	Z682.4.T73	Libraries. Library science. Information science. Personnel. Special groups, A-Z. Transgender people.
Z	Z688.S47	Libraries. Library science. Information science. The collections. The books. Special collections. Special. By subject, A-Z. Sexual minorities.
Z	Z695.1.H67	Libraries. Library science. Information science. The collections. The books. Cataloging. By subject, A-Z. Homosexuality.
Z	Z695.1.S43	Libraries. Library science. Information science. The collections. The books. Cataloging. By subject, A-Z. Sexual minorities.
Z	Z711.92.G37	Libraries. Library science. Information science. Public services. Reference services. Library service to special groups. Other, A-Z. Gays.
Z	Z711.92.S49	Libraries. Library science. Information science. Public services. Reference services. Library service to special groups. Other, A-Z. Sexual minorities.
Z	Z1229.G25	National bibliography. America. United States. American literature. Special classes or groups of writers, A-Z. Gays.
Z	Z1623.5.G39	National bibliography. America. South America. Latin America. By region or country. Argentina. Literature (General). Special classes or groups of writers, A-Z. Gays.
Z	Z1653.5.G39	National bibliography. America. South America. Latin America. By region or country. Bolivia. Literature (General). Special classes or groups of writers, A-Z. Gays.
Z	Z1683.5.G39	National bibliography. America. South America. Latin America. By region or country. Brazil. Literature (General). Special classes or groups of writers, A-Z. Gays.
Z	Z1743.5.G39	National bibliography. Colombia. Special classes or groups of writers. Gays.
Z	Z1773.5.G39	National bibliography. Ecuador. Special classes or groups of writers. Gays.
Z	Z1833.5.G39	National bibliography. Paraguay. Special classes or groups of writers. Gays.

Z	Z1863.5.G39	National bibliography. Peru. Special classes or groups of writers. Gays.
Z	Z1713.5.G39	National bibliography. Chile. Special classes or groups of writers. Gays.
Z	Z1893.5.G39	National bibliography. Uruguay. Special classes or groups of writers. Gays.
Z	Z1923.5.G39	National bibliography. Venezuela. Special classes or groups of writers. Gays.
Z	Z2113.5.G39	National bibliography. Austria. Special classes or groups of writers. Gays.
Z	Z2173.5.G39	National bibliography. France. Special classes or groups of writers. Gays.
Z	Z2233.5.G39	National bibliography. Germany. Special classes or groups of writers. Gays.
Z	Z2293.5.G39	National bibliography. Greece. Special classes or groups of writers. Gays.
Z	Z2353.5.G39	National bibliography. Italy. Special classes or groups of writers. Gays.
Z	Z24433.5.G39	National bibliography. Netherlands. Special classes or groups of writers. Gays.
Z	Z2573.5.G39	National bibliography. Denmark. Special classes or groups of writers. Gays.
Z	Z2603.5.G39	National bibliography. Norway. Special classes or groups of writers. Gays.
Z	Z2633.5.G39	National bibliography. Sweden. Special classes or groups of writers. Gays.
Z	Z2693.5.G39	National bibliography. Spain and Portugal. Spain. Special classes or groups of writers. Gays.
Z	Z2783.5.G39	National bibliography. Portugal. Special classes or groups of writers. Gays.
Z	Z2723.5.G39	National bibliography. Switzerland. Special classes or groups of writers. Gays.
Z	Z2843.5.G39	National bibliography. Turkey and the Balkan states (General works). Special classes or groups of writers. Gays.
Z	Z4023.5.G39	National bibliography. Australia (General). Special classes or groups of writers. Gays.
Z	Z4053.5.G39	National bibliography. Australia. New South Wales. Special classes or groups of writers. Gays.
Z	Z4113.5.G39	National bibliography. New Zealand. Special classes or groups of writers. Gays.
Z	Z4173.5.G39	National bibliography. Australia. Northern Territory. Special classes or groups of writers. Gays.

Z	Z4263.5.G39	National bibliography. Australia. Queensland. Special classes or groups of writers. Gays.
Z	Z4203.5.G39	National bibliography. Australia. South Australia. Special classes or groups of writers. Gays.
Z	Z4323.5.G39	National bibliography. Australia. Tasmania. Special classes or groups of writers. Gays.
Z	Z4383.5.G39	National bibliography. Australia. Victoria. Special classes or groups of writers. Gays.
Z	Z4443.5.G39	National bibliography. Australia. Western Australia. Special classes or groups of writers. Gays.
Z	Z5866.L4	Subject bibliography. Erotic literature, facetiae, curiosa, etc. Special topics. Lesbianism.
Z	Z5956.H64	Subject bibliography. Fine arts (Visual arts). The arts (General). Special topics. Homosexuality.
Z	Z6664.A27	Subject bibliography. Medicine. Internal medicine. Diseases and manifestations. AIDS.
Z	Z6675.H73	Subject bibliography. Medicine. Other. Homosexual men and women, and health.
Z	Z6675.7.G44	Subject bibliography. Medicine. Psychiatry. Psychopathology. Special topics, A-Z. Gender dysphoria. Gender identity disorders
Z	Z7164.H74	Subject bibliography. Political and social sciences. Special topics. Homosexuality. Lesbianism. Gay and lesbian studies.

6.4.2.2. Dewey Decimal Classification Numbers

Last Updated: 06-14-2024

Main Class	Full Classification	Description	Notes from DDC Manual
000 - Computer Science, Information & General Works			
0	004.69308664	Gay people--discussion groups (computer communications)	
0	070.4081	Journalism by people by gender or sex	Do not use for journalism for people by gender or sex; class in 070.483
100 - Philosophy & Psychology			
100	150.19508664	Gay people - psychoanalysis...	
100	155.3	Sex psychology; psychology of people by gender or sex, by sexual orientation	Class here sex psychology of adults in general; relations between the sexes, sex, sexual love
100	155.33	Psychology of people by gender or sex	Including display of behavior characteristics of both sexes or genders (androgynous behavior); gender non-conforming people, intersex people, transgender people, transsexual people Class here adults by gender or sex, gender identity, gender role, sex differences, sex role, the sexes; comprehensive works on psychology of males and females, comprehensive works on psychology of men and women.
100	155.34	Psychology of people by sexual orientation	Including asexual people, heterosexual people Class here adults in general by sexual orientation
100	155.343	Bisexual people	Class here bisexuality
100	155.344	Gay people (gay men and lesbians)	

100	155.3441	General topics of psychology of gay people (gay men and lesbians)	
100	155.3442	Gay Men	†Add as instructed under 155, except class evolutionary psychology in 155.7, ethnopsychology and national psychology in 155.8, environmental psychology in 155.9
100	155.3443	Lesbians	Add as instructed under 155, except class evolutionary psychology in 155.7, ethnopsychology and national psychology in 155.8, environmental psychology in 155.9
100	155.43	Children by gender or sex	Class here sex psychology of children.
100	155.508664	Gay adolescents -- psychology,...	
100	155.50867	For transgender and intersex young people twelve to twenty	
100	155[.334]	Psychology of people by gender or sex - [unassigned]	
100	155.53	Young people twelve to twenty by gender or sex	Class here sex psychology of young people twelve to twenty
100	176.4	Sexual relations	Including celibacy, chastity, homosexual relations, lust, premarital relations and extramarital relations, promiscuity. Class here comprehensive works on ethics of sex.
200 - Religion			
200	200.866	LGBT people--religion, . . .	
200	200.8664	Gay people--religion	
200	200.86642	Gay men - religion	
200	200.86643	Lesbians - religion	
200	200.867	Transgender people--religion	
200	201.615533	(Sex differences \$x Religious aspects)	
200	201.7	Attitudes of religions toward social issues (Gender identity \$x Religious aspects) (Sex role \$x Religious aspects)	

200	204.408664	Gay people--religion--guides to life	
200	204.4086642	Gay men--religion--guides to life	
200	204.41	204.41 Same-sex marriage \$x Religious aspects" and "Polygamy \$x Religious aspects" both show up as 204.41 in WebDewey Results	"Same-sex marriage \$x Religious aspects" and "Polygamy \$x Religious aspects" both show up as 204.41 in WebDewey Results
200	204.41	Polygamy \$x Religious aspects	"Same-sex marriage \$x Religious aspects" and "Polygamy \$x Religious aspects" both show up as 204.41 in WebDewey Results
200	205.664	Sexual relations--ethics--religion, . . .	
200	206.108664	Gay people--clergy, . . .	
200	206.1086643	Lesbians--clergy, . . .	
200	220.608664	Bible--gay interpretations	
200	220.83053	Gender identity \$x Bible	
200	220.8306766	Homosexuality--Bible	
200	241.664	Sexual relations--ethics--religion--Christianity, . . .	
200	248.8081	People by gender or sex (Guides to Christian life for specific groups of people)	
200	259.08664	Gay people--religion--Christianity--pastoral theology, . . .	
200	259.086642	Gay men--religion--Christianity--pastoral theology, . . .	
200	259.086643	Lesbians--religion--Christianity--pastoral theology	
200	261.835736	Extramarital relations--social theology--Christianity, . . .	
200	261.835766	Homosexuality--social theology--Christianity	
200	262.1408664	Ordination of gay people--Christianity	

200	262.14086643	Ordination of lesbians--Christianity	
200	270.08664	Gay people--religion--Christianity, . . .	
200	270.086642	Gay men--religion--Christianity, . . .	
200	270.086643	Lesbians--religion--Christianity, . . .	
200	294.35664	Sexual relations--ethics--religion--Buddhism, . . .	
200	294.548664	Sexual relations--ethics--religion--Hinduism, . . .	
200	296.08664	Gay people--religion--Judaism, . . .	
200	296.3664	Sexual relations--ethics--religion--Judaism, . . .	
200	297.5664	Sexual relations--ethics--religion--Islam	
300 - Social Sciences			
300	302.2308664	Gay people--mass media	
300	305.3	People by gender or sex	Class here interdisciplinary works on men and women, gender identity, gender role, sex role, the sexes.
300	305.308997	North American Native Peoples	Class Two-Spirit people in 306.7608997
300	305.309	Gender identity--history	
300	305.30973	Sex role--United States	
300	306.4408664	Gay men--language--sociology	
300	306.76	Sexual orientation, transgender identity, intersexuality	Class here people by sexual orientation; interdisciplinary works on LGBT identity (Lesbian gay bisexual transgender identity), SOGI (Sexual orientation and gender identity). Class interdisciplinary works on gender identity in 305.3

300	306.7601	Sexual orientation - philosophy	
300	306.7602	Sexual orientation - miscellany	
300	306.7603	Sexual orientation - encyclopedias	
300	306.7608997	North American Native Peoples	Class here Two-Spirit people
300	306.765	Bisexuality	
300	306.76508421	Young bisexual men	
300	306.760844	Middle-aged people -- sexual orientation	
300	306.760846	Older people -- sexual orientation	
300	306.7608995073	Asian Americans--sexual orientation	
300	306.762	Asexuality	
300	306.766	Homosexuality	
300	306.76608	Minority gay people	
300	306.7660835	Gay adolescents	
300	306.7660846	Older gay people	
300	306.766087	Gay people with disabilities	
300	306.7660872	Gay people with hearing impairments	
300	306.76608827	Gay Christians	
300	306.766089996073	Gay African Americans	
300	306.766092	Gay people--biography	
300	306.7660922	Gay people--collected biography	
300	306.7660973	Gay people--United States	

300	306.7662	Male homosexuality	
300	306.76620842	Young gay men	
300	306.76620844	Middle-aged gay men	
300	306.76620872	Gay men with hearing impairments	
300	306.766208827	Chrisitan gay men	
300	306.766208909	White gay men	
300	306.7662089924	Jewish gay men	
300	306.766208996	Black gay men	
300	306.766208996073	African American gay men	
300	306.7662092	Gay men--biography	
300	306.7663	Lesbianism	Class here lesbians
300	306.768	Transgender identity and intersexuality	
300	306.7680835	Transgender adolescents	
300	306.7680846	Older transgender people	
300	306.76808827	Transgender Christians	
300	306.76809	Transgender people -- history	
300	306.77086642	Gay men--sexual practice	
300	306.8423	Polygamous marriages, partnerships, unions	
300	306.848	Same-sex marriages, partnerships, unions	
300	306.850866	Families of LGBT people	
300	306.8740866	LGBT parents	

300	306.87408664	Gay parents	
300	306.874208664	Gay fathers	
300	306.874308664	Lesbian mothers,...	
300	306.8740867	Transgender parents	
300	320.562	Ideologies by gender or sex	
300	323.3264	Gay people--civil and human rights	
300	323.33	People by gender or sex	Standard subdivisions are added for either civil or political rights or both For transgender and intersex people, see 323.327
300	331.2576308664	Gay people (Gay men and lesbians)	
300	331.53	Gay men	
300	331.56	Workers by gender or sex	Class transgender and intersex people in 331.5 . For women, see 331.4
300	338.708664	Gay business enterprises	
300	344.0153	Gay workers--labor economics--law	
300	346.01308664	Gay people--legal status	
300	346.013086642	Gay men--legal status	
300	346.0168	*Same-sex marriages, partnerships, unions	*Add as instructed under 342-347
300	346.01708664	Gay parents--law	
300	346.017808664	Gay adoption--law	
300	346.7301308664	Gay people--legal status--United States	
300	352.6308664	Gay people--civil service	

300	355.008664	Gay people--armed services	
300	355.0086640973	Gay people--armed services--United States	
300	359.0086640973	Gay people--naval forces--United States	
300	359.0086642	Gay people--naval forces	
300	361.308664	Gay people--social work	
300	362.108664	Gay people--medical care	
300	362.1969792008663	AIDS (Disease)- Bisexual people	
300	362.1969792008664 2	AIDS (Disease)- gay men	
300	362.408664	Gay people with disabilities--social welfare	
300	362.4208664	Gay people with hearing impairments--social welfare	
300	362.69664	Older gay people--social welfare	
300	362[.70867]	Transgender and intersex young people	Do not use; class in 362.785
300	362.78	Transgender and intersex young people, young people by sexual orientation, young people in intrafamily relationships	
300	362.785	*+Transgender young people and intersex young people	Including female-to-male transgender young people, male-to-female transgender young people. Class here gender nonconforming young people, transsexual young people. Subdivisions are added for transgender young people and intersex young people together, for transgender young people alone. *Add as instructed under 362-363.

			†Do not use notation T1--08 from Table 1 to indicate services rendered by groups of people; class in base number
300	362.786	*†Young people by sexual orientation	Including asexual young people. †Do not use notation T1--08 from Table 1 to indicate services rendered by groups of people; class in base number
300	362.7866	Gay adolescents--social welfare	
300	362.8292	*† abuse with the family	*Add as instructed under 362-363 †Do not use notation T1--08 from Table 1 to indicate services rendered by groups of people; class in base number
300	362.8396	*† Women by sexual orientation	Including asexual women. †Do not use notation T1--08 from Table 1 to indicate services rendered by groups of people; class in base number
300	362.8808664	Gay people--victims of crimes	
300	362.8855086642	Gay men--victims of abuse	
300	362.896	*† People by sexual orientation	Including asexual people; †Do not use notation T1--08 from Table 1 to indicate services rendered by groups of people; class in base number

300	362.8962	*† Heterosexual people	†Do not use notation T1--08 from Table 1 to indicate services rendered by groups of people; class in base number
300	362.8963	*† Bisexual people	†Do not use notation T1--08 from Table 1 to indicate services rendered by groups of people; class in base number
300	362.8964	*† Gay men	†Do not use notation T1--08 from Table 1 to indicate services rendered by groups of people; class in base number
300	362.897	*† Transgender people and intersex people	Including female-to-male transgender people, male-to-female transgender people. Class here gender nonconforming people, transsexual people. Subdivisions are added for transgender people and intersex people together, for transgender people alone. *Add as instructed under 362-363 †Do not use notation T1--08 from Table 1 to indicate services rendered by groups of people; class in base number
300	368.454008664	Gay people (gay men and lesbians)	Class here parental leave taken by same-sex partners
300	370.8664	Gay people in education	
300	371.821	Students by gender or sex	Class here gender identity, gender role, sex role For transgender and intersex people, see 371.8267
300	371.8266	LGBT students	
300	371.82663	Bisexual people--education	
300	371.8267	Transgender students	
300	373.182663	Bisexual people--secondary education	

300	373.182664	Gay people--secondary education	
300	373.1826643	Lesbians -- secondary education	
300	378.008664	Gay people in higher education	
300	378.198266	LGBT college students	
300	384.544308664	Radio programs--gay people	
300	384.5544308664	Television programs--gay people	
300	391.0081	People by gender or sex	
300	395.1	Etiquette for people by gender or sex; for age groups	
300	395.14	Etiquette for people by gender or sex	
400 - Language			
400	408.6642	Gay men--language	
500 - Science			
500	571.886	Hermaphroditism	Add as instructed under 571.5-571.9
500	599.936	Sex characteristics	Class here secondary sexual characteristics
600 - Technology			
600	610.8664	Gay people in medicine	
600	616.694	*Intersexuality	Class here hermaphroditism, comprehensive medical works on sex differentiation disorders Class interdisciplinary works on intersexuality in 306.7685 Class a specific sex differentiation disorder with the disorder, e.g., congenital adrenal hyperplasia 616.45, congenital adrenal hyperplasia in children 618.9245. *Add as instructed under 616.1-616.9

600	616.8583 (manual note)	Homosexuality	Use 616.8583 for homosexuality only when the work treats homosexuality as a medical disorder, or focuses on arguing against the views of those who consider homosexuality to be a medical disorder. Class works about gay men and lesbians in relation to other topics in medicine with the topic plus notation T1--08664 from Table 1, e.g., advice to gay men and lesbians about finding psychotherapy for a variety of psychiatric problems 616.891408664. Class most works about gay men and lesbians outside medicine, e.g., Christian attitudes to homosexuality 270.08664, interdisciplinary works on homosexuality 306.766, gay men and lesbians in armed forces 355.008664. If in doubt, prefer a number other than 616.8583.
600	616.8583	*Sexual disorders	Including homosexuality treated as a medical disorder. Class interdisciplinary works on homosexuality in 306.766 See Manual at 616.8583
600	616.8527	*Depressive disorder and dysphoria	Including seasonal affective disorder. Class here comprehensive works on depression, on mood disorders. Subdivisions are added for either or both topics in heading
600	616.85277	*Gender dysphoria	See also 616.694 for intersexuality *Add as instructed under 616.1-616.9
600	616.8917087	Gay people - Psychoanalysis - Psychiatry	
600	618.2008664	Gay people - Obstetrics	
600	629.227506	Motorcycles--engineering--organizations	
600	647.9508664	Gay bars	
600	647.95086643	Lesbian Bars	

600	649.10867	Transgender and intersex people	Do not use for rearing of transgender and intersex children; class in 649.1564
600	649.13	Children by gender or sex	"Standard subdivisions are added for either or both topics in heading. Class here gender identity, gender role, sex role. Class children of specific sexes belonging to specific age group in 649.12. For transgender and intersex children, see 649.1564. See manual at 649.12-649.15 vs. 649.1024, 649.108."
600	649.156	Children by social and economic levels; children by sexual orientation; transgender and intersex children; children with status defined by changes in residence; children with social disadvantages	
600	649.1563	Children by sexual orientation	"Add to base number 649.1563 the numbers following T1--0866 in notation T1--08662-T1--08664 from Table 1, e.g., gay children 649.15634"
600	649.15634	Gay children-Home care	
600	649.1564	Transgender and intersex children	Standard subdivisions are added for transgender and intersex children together, for transgender children alone
700 - Arts & Recreation			
700	700.4521	Gender identity -- arts...	
700	700.453808664	Gay erotica	
700	700.4538086643	Lesbian erotica	
700	704.04	People by gender or sex	Class groups of misc. specific groups of people of a specific gender or sex in 704.08 For transgender people, see 704.0867
700	778.92808664	Gay erotica--photography	

700	780.81	Gender identity -- music	
700	790.208664	Gay people--performing arts	
700	791.4308664	Homosexuality and motion pictures	
700	791.43086642	Gay men and motion pictures	
700	791.43086643	Lesbians and motion pictures	
700	791.4365266	LGBT people--motion pictures	
700	791.43652664	Gay people -- motion pictures	
700	791.436526642	Gay men--motion pictures	
700	791.436526643	Lesbians--motion pictures	
700	791.4365267	Transgender people--motion pictures	
700	791.43652694	Socially disadvantaged people--motion pictures	
700	791.43653	Human characteristics--motion pictures, . . .	
700	791.436538	Sex--motion pictures	
700	791.43653808664	Gay erotic films	
700	791.456526642	Gay men--television programs	
700	791.45653	Human characteristics--television programs, . . .	
700	791.45653808664	Gay erotica--video recordings	
700	792.08664	Gay people--theater	
700	792.808664	Gay people--dance, . . .	
700	793.3	Social, folk, national dancing	
700	793.308664	Gay people--social dancing	

700	796.08664	Gay people in sports	
800 - Literature			
800	808.8035266	LGBT people--literature	
800	808.80352664	Gay people--literature	
800	808.803526643	Lesbians--literature	
800	808.8035267	Transgender people--literature	
800	808.80353808664	Gay erotica--literature	
800	808.803538086643	Lesbian erotica--literature	
800	808.82935388664	Gay erotica--drama	
800	809.8920663	Bisexual authors (Literature)--history and criticism	
800	809.8928308664	Gay adolescent literature--history and criticism	
800	809.8928708664	Lesbian authors (Literature)--history and criticism	
800	808.89920663	Bisexual authors (Literature)	
800	809.89928308664	Gay adolescent literature	
800	808.89928708664	Lesbian authors (Literature)	
800	809.9335266	LGBT people--literature--history and criticism	
800	809.93352664	Gay people--literature--history and criticism	
800	809.933526643	Lesbians--literature--history and criticism	
800	809.9335267	Transgender people--literature--history and criticism	
800	809.93353808664	Gay erotica--literature--history and criticism	
800	809.933538086643	Lesbian erotica--literature--history and criticism	

800	813.0080358086643	Lesbian erotica--fiction--American literature--collections	
800	813.0093538086643	Lesbian erotica--fiction--American literature--history and criticism	
900 - History & Geography			
900	910.8664	Gay travelers	
900	920.008 vs. 305-306, 362 (manual note)	Biography as a discipline with respect to groups of people; general collections of biography by groups of people with specific attributes vs. Groups of people and social problems of and services to groups of people	<p>Use 920.008 for collected biographies of a social group. However, use 305 or 306, plus notation T1--0922 from Table 1, for biographies that focus on the sociological aspects of the group. Use 362, plus notation T1--0922 from Table 1, for biographies that focus on the social problems of a group and their solutions. If in doubt, prefer 920.008.</p> <p>For example, use 920.0086642 for a collection of biographies of gay men. However, use 306.76620922 if the biographies focus on these men as leaders in the gay-rights movements and or on other sociological aspects. Use 920.00871 for a collection of biographies of famous persons who are blind. However, use 362.410922 if the biographies focus on the problems of being blind and social services provided.</p> <p>Apply the same policy for collected biographies of members of a specific ethnic or national group; however, use 920.0092 (not 920.0089). Apply the same policy also for collected biographies of men and of women; however, use 920.71 and 920.72, respectively (not 920.00811 or 920.0082).</p>
900	920[.0081]	People by gender or sex	Do not use; class in 920.7
900	920[.0082]	Women	Do not use; class in 920.72

900	920.00866	LGBT people--biography, . . .	
900	920.00867	For collected biography of transgender or intersex people	
900	920.7	People by gender or sex	Class here individual biography of people not associated with a specific subject, collected biography by gender or sex; class general collections of biography in 920.02; for collected biography of transgender or intersex people, see 920.00867; (Option: Class here all individual biography: prefer specific subject, plus notation T1-092 from table 1, e.g. biography of a female scientist 509.2)
900	940.5308664	Gay people--World War II	
900	940.5318087	Gay people--Holocaust, 1933-1945	
T1 - Table 1 - Standard Subdivisions			
T1	T1-081	*People by gender or sex	Class here gender identity, gender role, sex role Subdivisions are added for either or both topics in heading For women, see T1--082 For transgender and intersex people, see T1--0867 See Manual at T1--081 and T1--08351, T1--08352, T1--08421, T1--08422 *Add as instructed under T1--08
T1	T1--08659	*Polygamists	*Add as instructed under T1--08
T1	T1-0866	*People by sexual orientation	Including asexual people Class here comprehensive works on LGBT People For transgender people, see T1--0867 *Add as instructed under T1--08
T1	T1-08663	*Bisexual people	*Add as instructed under T1--08
T1	T1--08664	*Gay people (Gay men and lesbians)	*Add as instructed under T1--08

T1	T1--086642	*Gay men	*Add as instructed under T1--08
T1	T1--086643	*Lesbians	*Add as instructed under T1--08
T1	T1--0867	*Transgender people and intersex people	Including female-to-male transgender people, male-to-female transgender people Class here gender nonconforming people, transsexual people Subdivisions are added for transgender people and intersex people together, for transgender people alone Class comprehensive works about LGBT people on T1--0866
T1	T1--08675	Intersex People	*Add as instructed under T1--08
T1	T1--0925	Collected biography of people by specific gender of sex; age groups; relationships	Add to base number T1--0925 the numbers following T1--08 in notation T1--081-T1--085 from Table 1, e.g., biography of women T1--09252 For collected biography of transgender and intersex people, see T1--09267
T1	T1--0926	Collected biography of people by miscellaneous social attributes	Add to base number T1--0926 the numbers following T1--086 in Table 1, e.g., biography of gay people (gay men and lesbians) T1--092664
T3B - Table 3B - Subdivisions for Works by or about More than One Author			
T3B	T3B-0803521	Gender identity--literature--specific literatures	
T3B	T3B-093521	Gender identity--literature--specific literatures--history and criticism	
T3C - Table 3C - Additional Notation for Arts and Literature			
T3C	T3C-3521	Gender identity--arts	
T3C	T3C--8-T3C-9	Literature for and by groups of people	

T3C	T3C-35266	LGBT people-arts	
T3C	T3C-352664	Gay people--arts	
T3C	T3C-3526643	Lesbian--arts	
T3C	T3C-35267	Transgender people--arts	
T3C	T3C--353808664	Gay erotica--arts	
T3C	T3C-35388086643	Lesbian erotica--arts	
T3C	T3C--9286-TSC-9287	People by gender or sex	Class comprehensive works in T3C--928 For transgender and intersex people, see T3C--92067